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The Challenge of the EU

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INTRODUCTION. THE EU IN HUNGARIAN MEDIA AND POLITICS: POLITICIZATION, INSTRUMENTALIZATION, POLARIZATION

GABRIELLA ILONSZKI – GYÖRGY LENGYEL¹

ABSTRACT: *A research team from Corvinus University studied the image of European integration in Hungarian media and among the elite between 2021 and 2024. This volume presents selected results from this research. The introduction first outlines the social and institutional background and then analyses the phenomena of politicization, instrumentalization, and polarization, with a special focus on asymmetric polarization. It describes the methods used and the logic of the volume and concludes with questions about the social implications of polarization.*

KEYWORDS: *asymmetric polarization, politicization, instrumentalization, media pluralism, elite*

In this volume, we aim to shed light on the image of the EU in the Hungarian media and among the elite in the first half of the 2020s. The lessons of the Hungarian case go beyond local experience: they offer perspectives on an emerging authoritarian regime within the EU. The Hungarian regime represents a test for the EU, and how domestic public actors perceive external constraints as a challenge is also an important issue.

Between 2021 and 2024, in the framework of international cooperation, we conducted an empirical study,² the main components of which involved content and discourse analysis of the domestic media, elite interviews, and a representative public opinion survey. In this volume, we present some of the experiences from this research.

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The introductory chapter has two purposes. The first is to contextualize the contributions of the volume, drawing on the research background, and the second is to give a brief overview of the research methods and the structure of the volume.

FRAME AND BACKGROUND

The peaceful and smooth institutional transformation during the systemic change in the early 1990s was paved by three features of the Hungarian version of state socialism. *First*, the dominant political discourse of the 1980s was that of pragmatic liberal market reforms, which helped to persuade reluctant politicians and public opinion of the necessity of institutional change and highlighted the advantages of entrepreneurship. The *second* political component was that elite change preceded systemic change: the pace of cadre changes accelerated in the second half of the 1980s, especially in ministries and banks. The *third* aspect was that the oppressed democratic opposition kept the human rights version of liberal discourse that had existed since the 1970s on the agenda.

The consensual unity of the elites associated with the roundtable discussions that accompanied the system change meant that the main political forces (the governing socialists as well as the populist and liberal camps of the political opposition) accepted each other as legitimate partners and agreed upon the rules of the game of regular, free and fair elections, Euro-Atlantic geopolitical priorities, and institutional guarantees of human rights and property rights. What happened reveals that the systemic change followed the pattern of elite settlements (Higley-Burton 2006; Higley-Lengyel 2000). By elites, we mean here those who, through their personal choices and opinions, can exert a decisive influence on social reproduction processes.

In spite of the fact that the first free elections in 1990 were won by the conservative MDF and the second in 1994 by the socialist MSZP, the dominant political discourse in the 1990s was liberal, most clearly represented by two parties that emerged from the democratic opposition: SZDSZ (Alliance of Free Democrats), with a decade of experience in political life, and the freshly formed FIDESZ (Alliance of Young Democrats). SZDSZ reached an agreement with the first conservative government in exchange for the presidency, while in 1994, it entered into a coalition with the winning socialists. The socialist-liberal coalition achieved a two-thirds majority but refrained from changing the constitution and the cardinal laws.

Liberal political discourse with the slogan of “the third way leads to the third world” pushed aside “third-way” ideology, the recently reactivated but marginalized discourse frame associated with the populist tradition (Gombos 1992). In the liberal vision, European integration and the virtualization of borders were supposed to provide answers to other favorite topics of populists: problems of detrimental historical decisions, repressed national conflicts, and the grievances of the Hungarian minority in neighboring countries.

In addition to building new institutions, the political elite faced the challenges of inherited debt burdens and a rolling economic crisis. It also had to deal with the fact that, in addition to the desire for the promised freedom, insecurity, a fear of unemployment, outrage at economic crimes, and dissatisfaction with growing inequalities also gained ground in public thinking.

The general trend in support of European integration that has been identified (Haller 2008; Best et al. 2012; Hooghe-Marks 2005) is that national political elites are more supportive of integration, find it more useful, and are more attached to Europe than the populations of the respective countries. This is why experts talk about the “Europe of elites” and describe the integration as an elite-driven process. The picture is somewhat nuanced by the Hungarian experience. This shows that the elite and the public were closer to each other in terms of their European attachment than in the average of EU countries. Furthermore, in the case of both the elite and the population, European attachment was stronger than average in the Hungarian case. This was also true of trust in European institutions. Research on collective identity has helped to clarify one more thing: supranational and national attachment are not contradictory but are positively correlated. Therefore, it is merely the result of a special cognitive construction of collective identity that presupposes an image of the enemy in relation to which it defines itself, consequently assuming that various collective attachments are mutually exclusive. There are social conditions when the latter situation prevails, but they are frequently traps created by mobilizing elite ideology.

Although the pre-accession period can rightly be seen as a period of “under-politicization” – a time when the elite did not address society or the EU either in terms of its practical or identity aspects – the 2004 issue of the journal *JEL-KÉP* is noteworthy for its portrayal of social knowledge, expectations, and opinions. For example, concerning knowledge of the EU, it found that, while knowledge of the functioning of the EU was at a low level, knowledge of the related institutions was better (Tardos, 2004, p.16). International comparisons also provide important information. Fifty-eight percent of Hungarian respondents knew how many Member States made up the EU, above the international average.

Research on accession-related expectations has found (Lengyel-Blaskó 2002) that a more favorable social situation was generally associated with more positive expectations, while a disadvantaged social situation did not explicitly imply a rejection of accession. It also showed that material resources played a more important role in explaining expectations than cultural resources. However, material and cultural resources together generally had weaker explanatory power than orientation efforts and political engagement, i.e., cognitive and political mobilization skills.

A comprehensive media survey in 2000 (three national dailies, six regional dailies) showed that the media were generally dominated by news about the EU, with barely a tenth of the coverage dealing with general and substantive issues or past experiences (Terestyéni, 2002). The domestic internal debate was also reported in the press: one view was that over-emphasis on the national interest could be an obstacle to accession, while the other side claimed the lack of protection of the latter. However, there was a clear desire for balanced information, which is of paramount importance in society's image of the EU. It is worth recalling Viktor Orbán's comment in 2002 that "there is life outside the European Union," although it should be added that this was motivated and justified as much by frustration at the delay in accession negotiations as by criticism of the EU.³

Before EU accession, the expectations of the Hungarian population about this process were strongly positive. A much larger proportion of Hungarians than the EU average thought that EU membership would be a good thing and would benefit the country. After accession in 2004, this proportion started to decline and fell below the EU average. In 2001, 59% of Hungarians thought membership could be a good thing, and 71% thought it would benefit the country. Five years after accession, in 2009, 31% and 38%, respectively, thought that accession was a good thing and benefitted the country. It should be added that in this critical year, a period of economic crisis, there was still a significant gap between the two indicators: 52% thought that the benefits of accession were not visible, but only a minority (22%) thought that accession was a bad thing overall. Euroscepticism was negatively correlated with cultural resources, trust in domestic institutions, personal expectations for the future, and overall satisfaction (Lengyel – Göncz 2010).

In 2007, 2009, and 2014, empirical surveys of Members of the Hungarian Parliament (MPs) investigated the pragmatic and symbolic aspects of the political elite's views on European integration.⁴ Regarding the political

3 <https://uj szo.com/velemen y/orban-van-elet-az-eu-n-kivul-is>

4 The technical information and results of these surveys are available in Best et al. 2012 and Vogel-Teruel 2016.

background, it should be noted that in 2007 and 2009, a socialist-liberal coalition was in government, and the conservative-populist FIDESZ was in opposition, which party at that time was already denying the legitimacy of the incumbent government. Due to the economic crisis and the deteriorating elite consensus, the 2010 elections led to a two-thirds majority for FIDESZ, which eventually used this majority to change the constitution, the electoral law, and media law – among others. Analysts identified the chance of an emerging electoral authoritarian regime (Kornai 2016; Körösi-Patkós 2015; Lengyel-Ilonszki 2016; Magyar 2013; Magyar 2019; Ilonszki-Vajda 2021) whereby incumbents misuse their position to concretize their power. While in 2007 and 2009, the proportion of governing and opposition, left- and right-wing MPs, was more balanced, in 2014, the overwhelming majority of MPs were associated with the governing right-wing conservative-populist FIDESZ and its Christian Democrat satellite. Among the opposition parties was a newly emerging (at that time) extreme-right populist formation called Jobbik. FIDESZ leader Viktor Orbán, in a secret speech in Kötöcs, ⁵ declared that the aim was to establish a “central field of force,” and he seemingly succeeded concerning this tactical step. The 2014 elite survey context was thus different from the earlier two. This should be kept in mind in relation to the results of the surveys, briefly summed up below. We may rightly conclude that both the changing composition of the elite and the changing elite discourse are reflected in the evaluations of the EU.

In 2007 and 2009, the vast majority (85-89%) of Hungarian MPs thought that the country benefited from EU membership. Although there were differences between left and right in this respect, the differences were not statistically significant due to the ceiling effect. By 2014, the positive evaluations had dropped to 79%, and the differences between parties became significant. However, this did not involve the governing FIDESZ MPs changing their mind, as one might expect – the vast majority of them still thought that EU membership was beneficial for the country. The drop in the average was due to the (at that time) opinions of hard Eurosceptic extreme-right party (Jobbik) representatives. In 2014, with regard to pragmatic elite orientation, the dividing line was drawn between the extreme-right populist opposition party Jobbik and the rest of the parliamentary parties.

As mentioned already, such divergence may be traced to the solutions preferred for crisis management. In 2009, the majority of MPs sought the intervention of international financial institutions and the EU. By 2014, however, the majority already stated a preference for the autonomous action of the national government and the intergovernmental coordination of national governments. In this respect,

5 http://2010-2015.miniszterelnok.hu/cikk/megorizni_a_letezes_magyar_minoseget

both the changing composition of the political elite and the changing discourse of FIDESZ had an impact. While previously, roughly only one-third of MPs preferred a sovereigntist solution, this proportion had grown to over three-quarters of MPs. Socialist MP's preferences did not change in this respect, but their overall proportion decreased in the parliament, and among FIDESZ MPs, the sovereigntist discourse became the dominant expressible version. This was the period when the prime minister could proudly declare that the government had repaid the IMF loan and got rid of this undesirable constraint.

In 2007, a 52-58% majority of Hungarian MPs (just like other East-European ones) favored economic competitiveness above better social security. At that time, in this respect, there was no significant difference between conservative and socialist political elites; both preferred competitive economic liberalism to solidarity and social welfare. In 2014, however, 78% of FIDESZ and 13% of socialist MPs agreed that sustaining competitiveness was the most desirable function of the EU.

In 2007, a 56% majority supported further unification, and differences between the parties were visible but statistically insignificant. In 2014, only 26% of Hungarian MPs supported further unification. The proportion was 86% among socialists and 7% among FIDESZ MPs.

In 2007, in terms of tax redistribution, the Hungarian political elite considered it would be fair to distribute 17 euros of a 100-euro tax at the EU level. This proportion had decreased to 13% in 2014, but the figure was still six times as high as the actual EU-level redistributed tax. In this respect, again, there were differences between FIDESZ and the socialists, but these were not statistically significant.

As for identity-related components, in 2007, almost half of the Hungarian political elite felt “very attached” and slightly fewer “somewhat attached” to Europe. The proportion of those who said that they were “not attached” remained below 10%. In this respect, there were no statistically significant differences between the socialists and conservatives.

In 2014, 32% of Hungarian MPs declared that they were “very attached,” 54% said that they were “somewhat attached” to Europe, and 14% said that they were “not attached.” This means that the majority of the Hungarian parliament still remained engaged in terms of identity, although the intensity of attachment had decreased somewhat. This was mainly to do with the changing composition. Two-thirds of socialists (and a tiny liberal fraction) declared their high level of attachment, and in this respect, Christian Democrats had the same attitude. High-level attachment characterized 25% of FIDESZ MPs (and a further 65% were “somewhat attached.” More than half of Jobbik politicians declared that they were “not attached” to the EU.

After the fourth electoral victory of FIDESZ in 2018, one could observe some new developments in the elite framework and related media discourses (Janky 2020; Kolosi-Hudácskó 2020). FIDESZ had created a dominant sovereigntist discourse in the public media and externalized the source of threats. All the opposition parties tried to build up a rival and joint discourse in the understanding that separately, as individual parties against the powerful governing force, they would be unable to change the discourse or even influence it to some degree. Their strategic aim was to usher in a new regime change to overcome the authoritarian one. Jobbik moved toward a center-right populist position, accepted that European integration was beneficial for the country, and stated that the party was ready to join a coalition of unified opposition to challenge FIDESZ in the 2022 elections (Göncz-Lengyel 2021). In contrast, FIDESZ strengthened the sovereigntist ideology and tried to create an international platform that discredited liberal values and blocked integration.

POLITICIZATION, INSTRUMENTALIZATION, POLARIZATION

In the following section, we will first discuss international trends in the politicization of the EU and then discuss its domestic developments. Following Kriesi (2016), the process of politicization can be characterized by three features: the phenomenon becomes *more visible*, more and more *actors* are involved, and opinions and positions become increasingly *polarized*. Kriesi also adds that in the case of full politicization, all three dimensions of the latter phenomena can be observed. It is fair to say that the EU is attracting significant international and domestic attention in all three areas and thus undergoing a comprehensive politicization process. The presentation of the changing views of political elites and media discourse is crucial in this respect, as these actors are determining the extent and tools of politicization.

Although the EU is being politicized at the level of the Member States, and this phenomenon is the focus of most research, the EU itself is also being transformed, which is a crucial part of the politicization process. Comparison with our previous research allows us to assess the impact of politicization on European identity and pragmatic opinions and expectations about the EU. In many places, including Hungary, the issue of European integration is becoming a tool of domestic political battles associated with varying degrees of intensity. Based on our research results, we predict that, although the consequences of this politicization and instrumentalization process are visible, they are leading

more to the narrowing of Hungary's options in relation to the EU than to a fundamental change in society's perceptions of the EU.

The starting point for recognizing the new phase of the EU's transformation may be the Maastricht Treaty when it became clear that solutions initiated by the elite would not necessarily (or not at all) obtain support – the failed and dubious fate of national referenda can be seen as a response to this. Years of permissive consensus became replaced by the escalation of conflicts around European integration (Hooghe-Marks 2009), and the importance of domestic political processes, including the perceptions of political actors and public opinion, increased. This highlights the importance of identity in contentious issues; the conclusion is that it is a mistake to look solely at rational economic considerations as the background to disputes and conflicts, as was the case in the earlier phase of integration. In the past, national political elites might rightly have felt that voters were less concerned about European integration than rationally calculating business groups. Since the 1990s, integration-related issues have become more important in public opinion, and conversely, the *vox populi* in integration policy has become more important.

The gap between elite and public support for the EU has widened in many Member States, and this is part of the populist turn. Along with the transformation of the national party-political scene, populist parties have become the vehicles of the politicization process internationally, on both the left and the right. In line with research that has highlighted the differences between left- and right-wing critiques of the EU (Braun et al. 2019), it can be said, with some simplification, that the former have tended to be critics of pragmatic implementation, while the latter have been advocates of national and identity-based reservations. The literature points out that the degree of politicization varies from country to country. Although there is a growing recognition of the EU's role, this is not always accompanied by increasing polarization and an expansion in the number of agents.

As outlined above, crises have led to increased politicization and institutional responses beyond economic instruments. These crises have involved the explicit threat and risk of disintegration (Schimmelfenning 2018). However, they have also marked the way for reform through 'more integration,' and the EU has continued to move in this direction.

At the European level, the EU has gradually become a political issue for political actors and society. Reasons include the series of crises that have (also) shaken the EU, as EU responses to European (and sometimes global) processes made the EU's role increasingly clear to society. The EU has had to respond to the financial crisis, the migration problem, the COVID-19 epidemic, and Russia's aggression against Ukraine.

As far as the domestic political process is concerned, the overall picture is that the elite consensus that existed during the 1989-90 regime change regarding the main institutions and values, including freedoms, consolidated parliamentary democracy, and Euro-Atlantic orientation, has eroded since the mid-2000s.

The elites first pretended to follow the patterns of liberal democracy, but then some even questioned whether they needed to do this at all (Lengyel—Illonszki 2010, 2016). Political elite groups questioned each other's legitimacy regarding important issues. Even these areas were permeated by the rhetoric of the ruling elite based on conflict ideology.

Our study provides a cross-section of a context in which the incumbent political elite seeks to adapt the institutions of parliamentary democracy to the conditions of electoral autocracy, creating a media environment and thematizing public opinion accordingly. However, these efforts are complicated by the fact that, as a member of the EU and NATO, the ruling elite's capacity for action is limited, so their words and actions can often be out of sync. The institutional transformation of the media is the subject of a separate chapter below, but we simply anticipate that, using Hallin and Mancini's (2004) terminology, the media has become polarized in parallel with politics.

The politicization phenomenon has been identified in international literature in several other countries. The specificity of our case is the strong presence of instrumentalization. Its content is that the EU is seen as an instrument of domestic political power and election, subordinated to these goals. Politicization can also include this content itself since the broad focus on a particular issue can lead to increased political confrontation between different positions and political exposure to the latter. However, instrumentalization is more than this: it can become dominated by power and party politics, while public policy issues can become marginalized, government communication can become dominated by the propagandistic treatment of the EU, and the use of fake news can become entrenched.

Three distinct phases of politicization can be distinguished. We do not consider the year of accession as the end of the first phase, but rather 2002. The second, short but more turbulent phase ended in 2010 and marks the beginning of the third phase, which continues to this day. The dates point to the permanent internal political fixity of the relationships, with varying content: both 2002 and 2010 were years of changes in government. The decade after the regime change was one of duality. On the one hand, an identity discourse was present: What are Hungary's options in the new political situation? What does EU accession mean in terms of historical heritage and national identity? Could there be other paths? On the other hand, the pragmatic aspects of reform-applicability or, as it was often called, reform-necessity, were often present (Ágh 2004). Overall,

however, the EU was a terrain for the continuation of domestic conflicts regarding one aspect or another and often became a means of transferring responsibility: it was easier to refer to the expectations, norms, rules to be fulfilled in relation to EU accession than to argue, debate and explain (Lakner 2004). This dual discourse – i.e., identity-based versus pragmatic, involving weighing up advantages and disadvantages and social and economic impacts – is still dominant in the public policy perspective on the relationship with the EU. It concerns what political actors and decision-makers emphasize and what citizens consider important when they formulate their views on the EU. We will see that identity aspects dominate in the toolbox of politicization and especially instrumentalization. This is true of the image of the EU that the media presents to the public. Because what emerges from the elite interviews is that when the elites interpret the relationship with the EU for themselves, in their own terms, the identity issues are less divisive.

This dichotomy – the relationship between pragmatic and symbolic aspects – and the changes we have noted in relation to the EU did not escape the attention of domestic analysts of the period. The asymmetrical duality of politics and public policy had to change because the politicization of the EU also affects public policy insofar as emerging European governance can make public policy practice more effective (Ágh 1999). What seemed to be decided at the European level was, therefore, a question on the domestic scene – the emphasis on this would be decisive in the relationship between Hungary and the EU. However, it is particularly crucial for the subsequent and still ongoing processes that the historically changing role of Hungary in Europe and its relationship with Europe have not been ‘discussed’ and interpreted.

Apart from the general processes of European politicization, which are based on events related to crises or political reforms within the EU, the literature argues that the internal political processes of the Member States prominently impact politicization, and from this point of view, the Hungarian situation is necessarily a case in point. What is decisive from this point of view, therefore, are the responses and proposals for solutions to the problems facing the EU at the country level.

The accession negotiations – and the intervening elections and change of government in 2002 – are particularly noteworthy regarding the subsequent processes. Looking at the background, there were two changes in the behavior of the elites: the 1990s were characterized by a pattern of conformity with democratic consolidation, which was replaced by a kind of norm-breaking behavior from the end of the decade onwards, and became predominant among leading elite groups after 2010. This process, with elite change as the dominant background, is a good description of the dichotomy, although the authoritarian

regime that is emerging goes beyond norm-breaking, both in its motivation and process.

From 2006 onwards, the elite consensus in domestic politics broke up, but the shared position on the EU still persisted. From the perspective of domestic politics, the change in parliamentary behavior is noteworthy, for example, as it has led to a change in the behavior of relevant political elite actors (Várnagy–Ilonszki, 2018). This has been reflected in a significant decrease in the willingness of government and opposition actors to vote in unanimity and a radical decrease in activity (bills, interpellation) in parliament.

International experience has shown that one of the first signs of politicization is the polarization of the elite and the consequent emergence of new party political fault lines due to the rise of populist parties. This process has also become visible in our country. The opinions of the parliamentary elite show that the position of FIDESZ, which came into government in 2010, changed between 2007 and 2014 (Göncz-Lengyel, 2016), shifting towards a sovereigntist position on several key issues, such as competitiveness, the economic crisis, and migration, but remained positive in terms of its recognition of the benefits and usefulness of the EU.

The first truly politicizing moment could have been the referendum prior to accession in 2004, but this did not become a cornerstone of politicization; there was no governmental interest or will for this. In any case, the referendum attracted a much more modest turnout than others have in recent years – although it may be added that it was still relatively high (at 38.5%) compared to the post-socialist accession countries. This two-fifths turnout rate fell below 30% in 2014 but then increased significantly, reaching three-fifths in 2024.⁶ Thus, in terms of politicization, visibility, multiple actors, and polarization are prominent. National consultations and the instrumentalization of media and poster campaigns reinforce this trend.

The inclusion of the EU in national consultations is an example of instrumentalization. In the 2023 national consultation, all the questions were linked, if not to the EU, then to Brussels. In the pro-government media, Brussels is presented as an eponym for a bureaucratic EU elite. In this interpretation, Brussels poses a threat in two contradictory ways. *As a strong threat*, Brussels represents the oppressive European empire. In this narrative, the Hungarian ruling elite is represented through a David-and-Goliath analogy. *As a weak threat*, Brussels is a helpless, ineffective scapegoat, a symbol of the disintegrating, decaying West.

6 <https://www.valasztas.hu/europai-parlamenti-valasztasok>

RESEARCH METHODS AND STRUCTURE OF THE VOLUME

As mentioned above, the papers published here provide an insight into *the Hungarian experience of* an international research project.⁷ The methods and sources of the research are briefly described below. Following an extensive literature review, we first conducted content and discourse analysis of the media. We collected articles (and, in the case of TV, transcripts of talks and interviews) on the EU from eight media sources from 1 July 2021 to 31 March 2022. The sources were *Magyar Nemzet* (MN); *Népszava* (NSZ); *Heti Világgazdaság* (HVG); Origo.hu (ORIGO); Magyar Televízió Esti Híradó (M1); RTL Klub Esti Híradó (RTL); ATV Egyenes beszéd (ATV); Hír TV Híradó, and Csörte (HÍR TV).

From these sources, all items were collected that included one or more of the following keywords: *European Union, EU, Brussels, European Parliament, European Commission, European Council*. The corpus consisted of 14,424 units from the above-mentioned four newspapers and four TV stations. Within this, the proportion of information provided by TV-based sources was one-fifth. About half of the items appeared in two pro-government newspapers, MN and ORIGO. If we add to this the news and talks on public television (M1) and on HÍR TV, we find that about *two-thirds* of the items were published in *pro-government* and one-third in government-critical or neutral *outlets*.

Because of the use of keywords to drive the selection process, all pieces in the corpus are related to the EU. However, we were also interested in how this topic is intertwined with other issues of interest in the domestic media. In other words, how the EU emerged as a main theme and at the intersection of other discourses that were of particular concern to the public. Behind these intersections, the agenda-setting intentions of the ruling elite can be discerned, as well as how they reflect on international political events and their political communication.

In the next step of the media analysis, we made further selections by using additional keywords per macro-topic. While micro-topics are discernible from the texts, macro-topics enable the analysis of the relationship(s) between the text and the social context (Wodak-Meyer 2016, 27). The macro-topics were ascertained based on preliminary research and test coding among the issues of public interest in the examined period. These macro-topics (analyzed in detail below) are the following: European identity, the future of Europe, migration, the pandemic, environment, varieties of war (including geopolitics, disinformation, and hybrid war), and “child protection” according to the LGBTQ issue frame.

⁷ The Mediatized EU research was conducted in seven countries – Ireland, Portugal, Spain, Belgium, Hungary, Estonia, and Georgia.

Table 1. Structure of the corpus used in media analysis

Media Outlets	Abbreviated name	Television	Newspaper	News-paper online	Political position (pro-government: G; government-critical: C; Neutral: N)	Distribution of articles/talks (%; N=14,424)
Magyar Televízió Esti Híradó, V4 Híradó, Unió27	MI	+			G	10
RTL Klub Esti Híradó, Fókusz	RTL	+			N	4
<i>Magyar Nemzet</i> , magyarnemzet.hu	MN		+	+	G	31
<i>Népszava</i> , nepszava.hu	NSZ		+	+	C	14
<i>Heti Világgazdaság</i> , hvg.hu	HVG			+	C	16
origo.hu	ORIGO			+	G	18
ATV Egyenes beszéd	ATV	+			C	3
Hír TV Híradó, Csörte	HÍR TV	+			G	4

Source: MEDEU Research, authors' compilation

On average, the corpus contains around 1,600 articles and talks per month, and the topics had a certain periodicity over the nine months under study. Treatment of LGBTQ, the environment, and the COVID-19 epidemic was more frequent at the beginning of the period, in the summer of 2021, while that of disinformation and war was more frequent at the end of the period. The problem of hybrid war came to the fore in November 2021, with the wave of migrants emerging on the Belarusian-Polish border. Migration as a separate issue was present in high density throughout the whole period of investigation.

The distribution of macro-topics varied according to media outlets as well. Migration aroused significant interest in both the pro-government and the government-critical media, and compared to other topics, it was also covered by TV in relatively large proportions. Still, COVID-19 preoccupied public television even more than migration. Disinformation was the only macro-topic that was analyzed, and this was dominated by the government-critical press, but it could not break through and did not significantly influence the political agenda. The pro-government ORIGO and HÍR TV covered the disinformation topic only sporadically. Although disinformation and hybrid war are content-related in many respects, they still attracted the interest of different media

outlets. The hybrid war was an especially frequent topic in the pro-government MN. War and LGBTQ-related topics were somewhat overrepresented in the pro-government press as well. HÍR TV was particularly (above average) interested in the latter topic, being as preoccupied with it as much as with the future of Europe. About three-fifths of the analyzed articles dealing with the discourses of *identity and the future of Europe* appeared in MN and ORIGO, two strongly pro-government newspapers. These newspapers, therefore – at least in terms of the number of articles – dominated the media discourse dealing with the symbolic issues associated with the EU.

The research included 60 interviews with members of the political and media elite carried out between November 2022 and March 2023 using so-called Q-methodology. Interviewees were confronted with statements about the EU derived from the media and asked to indicate how much they agreed with each one and to justify their answers. The sources and methodology are described in more detail in the article on elites. In addition, a national survey was conducted in July-August 2023 on a sample of 1,022 adults, measuring public attitudes towards the EU, elites, and the media.

The structure of the book follows the order and logic of the research. The majority of the papers deal with the discourse on the EU in the domestic media. The institutional conditions of discourses taking shape in an asymmetrically polarized media structure are presented in the first study, which describes the process of media capture and thus helps to interpret the actors' room for manoeuvre. The subsequent discourse analysis opens with a paper that directly addresses the symbolic and pragmatic aspects of discourses on European integration. One natural apropos of this is the domestic confluence of international debates about the future of Europe. This helps to make sense of how sovereigntist and integrationist views are articulated in an asymmetrical media space and how instrumentalized identity-based views eclipse pragmatic arguments. Subsequent studies relate to the EU by cross-linking at the intersection of priority public issues: they focus on the macro-topics that were of particular interest to the domestic media in the period 2021-22. These include migration, pandemics, varieties of war, LGBTQ, and the climate crisis. Their emergence, as we have seen, occurs with different periodicity and intensity in terms of the contribution to asymmetric media polarization. In each case, these macro-themes must be interpreted here in the context of the metaphors of EU-related discourses, bearing in mind that the first filter of the corpus was generated by the keywords associated with the EU. The question is, therefore, how these macro-topics are linked to EU discourses, how the EU appears in the interpretations of macro-themes, and how this shapes the public sphere of domestic media. The paper that discusses

the experiences of the elite survey, based on Q methodology outlines the characteristics of dominant and marginal EU discourses, with a particular focus on the pro and con arguments associated with Huxit and the emergence of normative and contemplative discourse styles.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

Our content analysis of two dailies (MN and NSZ) in 2021 highlighted the instrumental role of EU discourse in the politicization and polarization of the media. We examined the positive, negative, neutral, or balanced character of articles in which the EU is a dominant theme. It is clear from this comparison that *the difference is not in the proportion of positive images*; this is equal in the two outlets and characterizes a minority (8%) of the pieces of writing. *The main difference lies in the negative EU representations.* The absolute majority (55%) of pro-government MN articles that dealt with the EU as a dominant topic had a negative framing. In the government-critical NSZ, the absolute majority of the pieces adopted a neutral or balanced character (56 and 24%, respectively), while a negative framing represented a 12% minority of the articles.

A further important aspect that we must mention is that the presence of EU politicians in the media analyzed is asymmetrical. They are present as *actors* whose actions and decisions are discussed, but they are rarely present as *speakers* – principals whose words are quoted and animated. The same can be said about the representatives of international NGOs, such as the Hungarian-born philanthropist George Soros, whose name appears in the Hungarian pro-government press in a negative context as the eponym of globalization. Incumbent Hungarian politicians, on the other hand, often appear as speakers whose words – even on websites or Facebook posts – are presented in newspaper articles. Their actions are relatively rarely subjected to critical analysis, and if so, this occurs almost exclusively in the opposition press. The public intellectuals and journalists who appear in the analyzed corpus mainly have pro-government attitudes. Their positions are, therefore, close to those of incumbent politicians, in relation to whom they use an apologetic tone. Their criticism is mostly sharp in their assessment of the EU and international partners and devastatingly sharp in relation to the opposition and civil organizations. The opportunity for opposition politicians to speak was significantly constrained by the asymmetrically polarized media. Furthermore, they had to simultaneously demonstrate unity and present their specific image within the electoral alliance, which meant an additional limitation.

The Hungarian media conditions fit the classification of *polarized pluralism* (Hallin-Mancini 2004; Bátorfy-Urbán 2020; Urbán 2022; Martin 2019; Mancini, 2015). A specific feature is that the current Hungarian media conditions are *asymmetrically* polarized: public media has been captured, and a significant proportion of the resources are in the hands of the governing elite. Opportunities for the opposition (socialists, liberals, greens, and right-wing populists) to appear in the mainstream media, especially on public TV, are much more limited. Due to the politics-media parallelism, the political views of newspapers, TV, and radio stations are clearly identifiable, which strengthens the external pluralism of the media. All in all, *external pluralism is strong and asymmetric, while internal pluralism is weak and also asymmetric.*

Epistemic trust – the expectation that the communicated knowledge will present social reality faithfully (Campbell et al. 2021) – in the media has plummeted in Hungary: in 2016, more than half of the population rejected the proposition that national media provide trustworthy information.⁸ Hungarians have thus become the fourth most skeptical in this respect, following Greek, French, and Spanish audiences.

Another survey concerning the war in Ukraine adds to this picture. The majority of EU citizens, including Hungarians, trusted the European authorities regarding information about the ongoing war. However, the majority of Europeans also trusted their own authorities, but the relative majority of Hungarians did not. Further, the majority of Europeans did trust journalists, and the majority of Hungarians did not.⁹

According to our population survey in August 2023, more than two-fifths of the population is dissatisfied with the government's management of EU affairs, and half of the population is dissatisfied with the state of the economy. The majority think that the media is polarized and distorts reality. The media consumption patterns of the public are divided along government versus non-government lines, and this divide re-appears in their EU-related attitudes: those who are exclusively informed by pro-government media are more likely than average to think that EU membership is not beneficial for the country.

Developments in the first half of the 2020s can be interpreted as a political experiment, with the ruling elite systematically criticizing European integration in order to turn public opinion around and align it with their own ideological orientation. According to this ideological framework, the EU is an empire whose center dictates without legitimacy and oppresses and exploits sovereign

8 Special Eurobarometer 452, 2016 <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/media-pluralism-and-democracy-special-eurobarometer-452>

9 Flash Eurobarometer 506, 2022 https://search.gesis.org/research_data/ZA7871

nation-states. The empire imposes on us – so the claims go – aliens, migrants, and LGBTQ customs that are alien to national traditions and public taste. If the ethnicization of crime and the reinstatement of the death penalty were also on the agenda, the populist far-right rhetoric would be almost complete. There is no doubt that far-right groups outside parliament, less visible to the public during the illiberal years of order and discipline, could now re-emerge. Expressions of xenophobia, discrimination against minorities, and homophobia may be amplified in public discourse and action.

In this discourse, the ruling elite cast themselves in the role of freedom fighters, reactivating the traditions of the 1848 and 1956 revolutions, which generate widespread positive sentiment in memory politics. However, there are glaring gaps and contradictions in this interpretation. One is the narrow interpretation of the ultimate goals: unlike the historical examples, the ultimate goal is not to achieve independence but to maintain a sovereign position within the EU. The call is for an EU structure based on sovereign nation-states with veto power over strategic issues (it is for this reason that the governing elite wants to delete the phrase “ever closer union” from the founding documents). Another confusing factor in this discourse is the relationship of the Hungarian ruling elite with the Russian ruling elite. The ruling elite of the former Russian empire played a decisive role in the suppression of the 1848 War of Independence. In family traditions, there is a typically negative image of Soviet soldiers’ behavior during World War II, and the Soviet elite played a decisive role in the suppression of the 1956 revolution. It is true that historical reminiscences are not the only determinant of current mass sympathies. But for opinion formers, the contradiction may be disturbing, especially because the Hungarian ruling elite, according to the press, has such intimate relations with the Russian elite that it has received devastatingly sharp criticism even from the Polish political elite, which was otherwise sympathetic to the Hungarian governing forces.

International research and theories point to the negative impact of European integration on domestic party convergence and elite-public congruence (Devine-Ibenskas 2021). In this respect, the Hungarian experience may shed light on the other side of the coin: how the polarization of domestic party politics affects efforts towards (and perceptions of) European integration and how incongruence between a government and its voters affects dissatisfaction with politics. The researchers recall that, in addition to the static aspect of elite-public congruence, responsiveness can help bridge the gap between elites and the public. It may be assumed that elites resonate intensely with the needs of the public. Again, the Hungarian experience is different: instead of changing its position more responsively, the governing elite is trying to change the hard identity-related attitudes of the population towards European integration.

Conflict-driven agenda-setting, illiberal framing, communication traps for the domestic opposition and fellow European politicians, and redefining what is sayable – these are the key elements in the toolbox of the political experiment.

How agenda-setting and government can influence public opinion is illustrated by the sentiment towards other countries. In 2018, Hungarians' sympathy for Western countries (the US, UK, Germany, and France) still exceeded their sympathy for Russia and China. However, compared to a decade ago, sympathy for Western countries has decreased, while sympathy for Russia and China has increased. The explanatory models clarify that historical panels associated with collective memory and socio-demographic background had little to do with the changes. The Hungarian public's sentiments towards Russia have been more directly influenced by party politics, with a significant improvement in the latter's image among supporters of the ruling party (Krekó 2019).

Will the incumbent elite be able to transform these wavering attitudes – initially enthusiastic, then softly Eurosceptic, then cautiously Euro-optimistic – into hard Euroscepticism? Will they manage to increase the proportion of those who do not care about European identity and think that Hungarian and European identities exclude and do not reinforce each other? By what means are they trying to achieve this goal, and what role does the media play in this? Our research tried to answer these questions. The ruling elite can mobilize its followers, clients, and supporters, for whom the internal compulsion to support their leader has not conflicted with a positive attitude towards the EU. If the prime minister's statements clarify the picture and stress the division between whether one supports either the leader or the EU, this could erode the commitment to European integration among the ruling party's supporters. However, the reverse may also happen, and opposition to EU decisions may reduce public support for the ruling elite.

Reactivating the rhetorical arsenal of the freedom fighter image may also be effective among those susceptible to emotionally based politics. Others are more receptive to the street fighter image articulated by the Prime Minister. However, the mixing of freedom fighter and street fighter roles can lead to confusion, especially if the street fighter tactic is used exclusively against those who are used to mutually beneficial arrangements, while the relationship with strong autocrats is characterized by the erosion and relativization of the values of the freedom struggle. Will a counter-discourse emerge that can effectively shape the agenda and a counter-elite emerge that can credibly represent a balance between responsibility and responsibility?

The question is whether social actors are aware that the challenge lies with the EU discourse. Can the political elite thematize the public discourse so that it is clear to the electorate that the stakes are *isolation or EU integration*?

The symbolic and pragmatic starting points of this process may be the fact that, as our survey from 2023 shows, only a minority (19.5%) think that Hungary should leave the EU sooner or later, a majority (59%) think that EU membership is beneficial for the country and an absolute majority of 72% of the population is still attached to the EU.

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THE RESTRUCTURING OF THE HUNGARIAN MEDIA SYSTEM

ÁGNES URBÁN¹

ABSTRACT: *The history of the Hungarian media system over the past decade and a half can be described as the decline of the market economy, the restriction of competition, and the capture of the media. State intervention has taken many forms, ranging from ownership restructuring to the market-distorting effect of state advertising and pressure on independent media outlets. Individually, these would be noteworthy developments in an EU Member State, but in Hungary, state intervention in the media market has become systemic.*

The paper describes the main elements of this systemic intervention and their interaction. The transformation of the Hungarian media system is not due to any one factor alone but rather to the fact that media policy actions have been unidirectional, and over time, the state has become a major player even where market conditions have prevailed. The current Hungarian media system is worryingly similar to what it was before the political transformation, but with the notable difference that administrative instruments have been replaced by less visible market interventions.

KEYWORDS: *Media market, media capture, media ecosystem*

INTRODUCTION

The transformation of the Hungarian media market and the capture of the media scene have been the subject of several studies, research, and international reports. Due to the small size of the country and its linguistic specificities, it

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is highly unusual that Hungarian developments should be so prominent in the literature in the context of an economic or social phenomenon. Hungary is only used as an example in most analyses of the Central and Eastern European region, but its media capture is unique in that for many authors today, it is Hungary that is one of the most interesting cases (Dragomir, 2019; Griffen, 2020).

This particular attention is probably due to two factors. On the one hand, an unparalleled wealth of instruments has been used to capture the media in Hungary, with strong state intervention in every element of the media system. On the other hand, the fact that Hungary is a member of the European Union makes the situation special. The EU provides a stable, value-based institutional environment where strong restrictions on the public sphere seem unthinkable. Yet the Hungarian case has made many people realise that this can happen in the European Union. Truly effective institutional responses are still to come, but many have already recognised that the Orbán regime's media policy contains innovations that have never been tried before.

There are countless examples in history of when a media system has come under strong political control. Without analysing the specific historical examples, these often involve dictatorial political powers and administrative means of power, such as institutionalised censorship, the closure of newsrooms, imprisonment or, in the worst cases, the killing of journalists, which factors have all played an important role in restrictions on the public sphere. If we look at the countries where press freedom has been most violated, such as Russia or China, censorship and restrictions on access to global online platforms also play a major role. Of course, there is no such thing in Hungary, which is what makes the Hungarian situation so special.

The study shows how the systemic nature of market interventions has captured the Hungarian media. There is no central censorship; online platforms are freely available, and people can write anything they want. There is no element of Hungarian media regulation that would attract serious international criticism, and the European Union has been unable to get a grip on individual decisions on competition grounds for many years. However, the system that has been built up since 2010 has, on the whole, resulted in a situation that has attracted criticism from international organisations and has been a major focus of the European Union's rule of law investigation (Reporters Without Borders, 2024; European Commission, 2024).

KEY FEATURES OF THE EVOLUTION OF THE MEDIA SYSTEM

Hungary regained its freedom with the regime change in 1989/1990. The transformation of the whole political system naturally went hand in hand with the transformation of the media system. With the collapse of the Soviet bloc, a market economy began to emerge, foreign investors appeared, and economic processes that it was hoped at the time would lead to the emergence of a free and economically viable media industry were set in motion.

The first signs of change came from the major newspaper publishers. As in many countries of the region, spontaneous privatisation appeared in Hungary. This consisted of journalists collectively resigning from their previous publishers and collectively signing new contracts with the publishers they had founded. Later on, managed privatisation became more and more prevalent, but journalists and editors were often involved in this process. It soon became clear that publishing companies were not much good without journalistic knowledge or the brand names of the newspapers, which were typically easy to acquire because of the shortcomings of media regulation (Gálik, 1997).

In the print media, the new structure was established quite quickly. Investors with capital were needed, and the big international publishing companies saw business potential in the Hungarian market, so a significant number of newspapers were taken over by foreign owners. At the same time, the publishers and editorial offices were headed by Hungarian managers who had both local knowledge and language skills. As Galambos (2008) has pointed out, the influence of foreign investors in the media, including journalism, was limited. In other industries, Western European or American investment was associated with the adoption of Western standards, while this was not the case in journalism. Foreign investors did not pay attention to bringing the newspapers they bought up to the professional standards of their own publishers' home countries or to establishing their editorial standards, systems and methods. Professional investors in journalism essentially behaved as simple financial investors.

In the radio and television market, the party-state structure formally remained in place for much longer. The new media law entered into force in 1996, and the frequency tenders were held in 1997, allowing the launch of national commercial radio and television stations. Legally, the 1996 Media Law also created the institutional framework for public service broadcasting, but it was, of course, based on the former state radio and television broadcasters.

Even if slowly, in the nineties, the possibility of a democratic media system emerged in the Hungarian media environment. The golden age of the media came at the turn of the millennium: It took a decade after the fall of communism

for the most important institutions and features of the democratic system and the market economy to take root. Tabloids flourished, as did commercial media. The economy grew, and advertisers were happy to spend and increase their advertising revenues. The internet was already a threat to traditional media companies, and this brought a new set of challenges. Google emerged and quickly became dominant on the entire internet by acquiring the video-sharing portal YouTube in 2006. Facebook became available in Hungarian in 2008 and has since seen an explosion in the number of Hungarian users.

The economic crisis of 2008 marked a turning point in the development of the media. Economic growth in the vulnerable countries of Central and Eastern Europe stalled, and advertising revenues plummeted dramatically. The economic downturn did not leave foreign investors unscathed, with many large companies leaving the region because the returns were no longer as high as before.

Whether growing or declining, the development of the Hungarian media system followed regional trends until 2010. The real change came with the coming to power of the Orbán government and the adoption of new media laws. In 2010, Parliament adopted the two laws most relevant to the media. Act CIV of 2010 on Freedom of the Press and on the Basic Rules Relating to Media Content (Smtv) established the framework, while Act CLXXXV of 2010 on Media Services and on the Mass Media (Mttv) contains the specific regulation. A completely new regulatory environment emerged, which allowed for much greater state intervention than before and, thus, a transformation of the media system (Polyák-Nagy, 2015).

The most important feature of the post-2010 transformation is its systemic nature: the interventions of the Orbán governments have pointed in the same direction and been integrated into a coherent whole (Polyák, 2022; Benedek, 2024). Another characteristic is that, besides the obvious instruments of political intervention, such as the media authority and the political control of public media, there is a very strong market intervention. Instead of administrative instruments, market instruments predominate, such as market distortion, interference in market processes, and giving some actors a competitive advantage and others a competitive disadvantage.

CHANGES IN OWNERSHIP

As we have already mentioned, after the fall of communism, the emergence of the market economy brought foreign investors, but no one expected foreign

ownership to remain dominant in the Hungarian market for only two decades. There were two main reasons for the exodus of investors.

After the crisis of 2008 and the start of the growth of digital platforms, some foreign investors started to sell their investments in Central and Eastern Europe, and with this, there was a change of ownership structure in the region (Dragomir, 2019). The situation in Hungary was unique in that the adoption of the new media laws in 2010 led to uncertainty in the regulatory environment, so there was a country-specific reason for the change in ownership strategies in addition to global developments.

Studies that have analysed the Hungarian media system after 2010 all focus on media ownership and changes in the market environment (Bátorfy, 2022; Polyák, 2022; Kovács et al., 2021). Overall, the pattern is clear; foreign professional investors have been replaced by Hungarian investors loyal to the government, but there are differences in how and in what ways this has happened. In some cases, a media authority decision had to be made to persuade an investor to sell a significant part of its stake, but typically, business rationality prevailed. Every media company has its own history, but the exit of most foreign investors has led to an unprecedented concentration of ownership.

One of the biggest investors in the print newspaper market, Finland's Sanoma, has exited the market, along with two smaller publishers: the Swedish Metro International SA, which publishes the free *Metro* newspaper, and Funke Gruppe, which also had the prestigious political weekly *HVG* in its portfolio. The biggest exit from the online media market was Deutsche Telekom, which sold Origo Zrt., a leading news portal. An important development in the television market was the sale of the TV2 commercial channel by the German ProSiebenSat1 (Urbán, 2016).

The history of the Ringier and Axel Springer portfolios, the fate of the former Simicska media empire and, of course, the creation of KESMA are particularly relevant to our topic.

History of the merger between Axel Springer and Ringier

The merger of the German Axel Springer and Swiss Ringier paved the way for pro-government investors to take over the Hungarian media market. The two companies, both dominant in the European newspaper market, announced the merger in 2010, and it was foreseeable that this might be problematic in Hungary as both publishers had significant market shares. It was particularly noteworthy that the new media law included the Media Council of the National Media and Infocommunications Authority in the examination of mergers

involving media companies and required a so-called position paper to assess the impact of the merger on media diversity. On the basis of its expert opinion, the Media Council rejected the merger application of the Hungarian subsidiaries of Ringier and Axel Springer in spring 2011. The interesting aspect of the case was that the Media Council employed no methodology concerning how such media concentration investigations should be conducted and what should be taken into account in the process (Gálik-Vogl, 2011).

The two companies then withdrew their application, but of course, they did not give up on merging their interests in Hungary. It was announced in January 2014 that Vienna Capital Partners (VCP), owned by Austrian businessman Heinrich Pecina, would acquire a significant part of the media portfolio of Ringier and Axel Springer, including the county newspapers, popular daily newspapers, as well as sports, women's and youth magazines. The publishing rights for the remaining newspapers, such as the tabloid *Blikk* and popular magazines, remained with Ringier Axel Springer Hungary, which obtained the merger licence. A regulatory decision thus forced two important professional investors in the Hungarian media market to sell valuable parts of their portfolios to a new player.

The VCP later took the name Mediaworks and became well-known in the autumn of 2016 when it suspended the print and online editions of the leading political daily *Népszabadság* overnight on 8 October. Heinrich Pecina cited business rationality, but given the way the procedure was carried out (closing down an online archive, humiliating staff), essentially everyone immediately suspected political motivation (Fabók et al., 2016). The political background became apparent when the sale of Mediaworks to Opimus Press, which turned out to be linked to Lőrinc Mészáros, a friend of the Prime Minister, was announced a few weeks later.

A later development was that Ringier-Axel Springer, which has a less publicly relevant portfolio, also changed: in 2021, Axel Springer sold its stake, so the major German publishing company, which is also of major importance at the European level, completely relinquished its presence in Hungary.

The Simicska media empire

Perhaps the most spectacular scandal to occur during the Orbán regime erupted in February 2015. Lajos Simicska, an old friend of the prime minister and the ruling party's economic mastermind, broke years of silence and gave numerous interviews in the space of an afternoon. In these, he used obscene language towards the prime minister and broke with Fidesz.

It was immediately clear that the media empire owned by Lajos Simicska would not be left untouched by the scandal. On the one hand, the formerly legendarily pro-government editorial offices changed direction and became critical of the government, and on the other hand, the state advertising that had previously brought these companies significant revenue dried up.

Simicska financed the media companies until the 2018 elections, but then he made some quick decisions: In the week after the election, he closed the conservative daily *Magyar Nemzet*, although a few months later, it was relaunched as a pro-government newspaper. Lánchíd Radio was closed down, and soon afterwards, the weekly *Heti Válasz* too. HírTV was sold to Simicska's former business partner, Zsolt Nyerges, who remained loyal to the prime minister. Simicska's poster (billboard) companies, which became an important political communication tool in the Orbán regime, also went to Zsolt Nyerges.

Interestingly, after the demise of the right-wing, conservative-leaning newspapers, some journalists started a new project. Part of the editorial staff of *Magyar Nemzet* started the weekly *Magyar Hang*, while journalists from *Heti Válasz* created *Válasz Online*. The popular podcast channel *Az élet, meg minden* (Life and Everything) is also produced by a former journalist of *Magyar Nemzet*. These media products have since found their audience and seem to be able to operate sustainably.

The creation of KESMA

Perhaps the most symbolic event in the Hungarian media system was the creation of the Central European Press and Media Foundation (abbreviated as KESMA in Hungarian).

KESMA was founded in August 2018 by Gábor Liszkay, a well-known media personality close to PM Viktor Orbán. The initial board of trustees of the foundation elected well-known Fidesz-affiliated individuals, and although the names have changed, the Fidesz affiliation has remained unchanged since then. According to its Articles of Association, the aim of KESMA is “(...) *to promote those activities of the print, radio, TV and online sections of the Hungarian mass media which serve to build values and strengthen Hungarian national consciousness*” (CEPMF, 2018).

When KESMA was founded, almost all major media owners close to Fidesz (including Lőrinc Mészáros, Árpád Habony, Zsolt Nyerges, Mária Schmidt, and Ádám Matolcsy) donated their companies to KESMA free of charge. Bátorfy (2018) calculates that a total of 476 media brands became part of KESMA and that this move significantly increased the concentration of media ownership in Hungary.

Under real market conditions, the regulators would have had to investigate the merger, and this concentration of ownership could hardly have occurred after a fair investigation. On the one hand, the Hungarian Competition Authority would have had to investigate whether the merger would reduce competition in the relevant market, and on the other, the Media Council would have had to assess the proposed transaction from the point of view of media plurality. This did not happen: On 5 December 2018, a government decree declared the creation of KESMA to be of national strategic importance and thus exempted it from the examination and approval process (Kovács et al., 2021).

Ownership concentration has become significant in the Hungarian media market. KESMA is a particularly strong player in the print daily newspaper market, with all county dailies (18 in total), a political daily (*Magyar Nemzet*), a tabloid (*Bors*) and a free daily (*Metropol*). The KESMA empire also has very strong brands in other media sectors, such as Origo (online), HírTV (television), and Retro Radio.

Of course, there are also media companies that are not part of KESMA, but many are notoriously tied to pro-government investors, as proven by fact-finding journalists (e.g., TV2, Rádió1). According to a calculation based on 2023 revenue data in news and public market, 73.6 per cent of revenues went to the pro-government private media and the strongly pro-government public media (Horváth et al., 2024).

The concentration of media ownership in Hungary has undoubtedly become the basis for the capture of the media. There was no question of the ruling party acquiring media companies illegally by administrative means. There are no legal proceedings in connection to this, and there are no known former investors who had had to buy their companies against their will or at a price. In addition, the pro-government media empire was built not only by squeezing out foreign investors and acquisitions but also by launching new products (e.g. 888.hu, pestisracok.hu, Ripost). On the surface, everything was done according to the framework of market transactions. However, the end result was the exit of most foreign investors, the continued growth of the pro-government media empire and strong ownership concentration.

THE ROLE OF THE MEDIA AUTHORITY

The functioning of the Hungarian media authority (Media Council) has been the subject of criticism for many years, but our present analysis is limited to issues related to market regulation. The licensing of mergers, on the one hand,

and the conduct of radio frequency tenders, on the other, are the two instruments with which the Media Council can directly influence market developments.

As mentioned earlier, the Media Council has the power to authorise or prohibit mergers in the media market by means of a resolution of the competent authority (Mttv. § 216 (5)). The practice of the Media Council has proven to be very selective over the past decade and a half. It has allowed acquisitions and mergers involving pro-government players, thus allowing the pro-Fidesz media empire to grow (only the creation of KESMA prevented the Media Council from opening an investigation, as was previously the case).

Interestingly, in two cases, the Media Council decided that the proposed merger would harm media diversity. First, in 2011, it blocked the merger of two major foreign newspaper publishers, Axel Springer and Ringier, thus making it impossible for a major foreign professional investor to play a leading role in the Hungarian newspaper market. A few years later, in 2017, the Media Council again felt the need to protect the diversity of the Hungarian media: it blocked the merger of Magyar RTL Televízió Zrt. and Central Digital Média Kft. with the obvious aim of preventing German-owned RTL from strengthening its digital business in Hungary.

It is telling that the Media Council has not developed a methodology for assessing diversity in the last 14 years. The task is by no means an easy one, but it would clearly have taken that much time to study the best practices from abroad and to develop a methodology that takes into account the specificities of the Hungarian market. The failure to do so implicitly sends the message that the Media Council does not necessarily want to judge merger cases in a uniform way and that the procedures of the authorities are based on ad hoc decisions.

The role of the Media Council in shaping the radio market is of paramount importance because of the frequency tenders. The process is very well documented, and it has been spectacular to see the winners of radio spectrum tenders change with the political winds. Several of the players associated with pre-2010 radio have disappeared from the market, but others have been so successful that they have achieved essentially national coverage. One of the biggest success stories, with significant expansion of the area of coverage, was Lánchíd Radio, owned by Lajos Simicska until the owner came into conflict with the Prime Minister (Nagy, 2016). A review of the radio tenders for 2023 showed that 21 of the 24 closed tenders were valid. Of these, eight frequencies were acquired by Lőrinc Mészáros' interests, and another six by religious radio stations. Of particular importance is the fact that in 20 out of 24 tenders – 83% – only one bidder submitted a bid, i.e. the tender was conducted without competition (Horváth et al., 2024).

THE PUBLIC SERVICE MEDIA

It is beyond the scope of this paper to describe the criticisms of public service media (PSM) in Hungary, but they are typically related to content. There is no doubt that the news production practices of public service media are very far from what the literature tends to describe as balanced and objective (OSCE, 2022; Urbán et al., 2023; Szávai et al., 2024). We also do not discuss here the leaked materials and audio recordings that demonstrate the overt political interference in the operation of public service media and the marginalisation of professional decisions (Keller-Alánt, 2020; Wirth, 2022).

However, it is important to examine the extent to which the institutional system itself covers the illegal financing of PSM. The role of a special service, the news blocks produced for radio stations, also deserves attention.

The current regulatory environment for public service media was created by the adoption of the Media Act 2010 (Mttv) and the amendment of this Act, which entered into force in the summer of 2015. The regulation is characterised by a split institutional system, which has led to a lack of transparency and a blurring of responsibilities.

According to the Media Act, the Media Service Support and Asset Management Fund (hereinafter MTVA) is the manager of public service assets and finances the production of public service content. The CEO of MTVA is appointed by the President of the Media Council without a competitive tender procedure and can be dismissed at any time without giving any reason, but is not subject to any control by any supervisory body. Also under the Media Act, the public service media is Duna Media Service Nonprofit Ltd. (hereinafter Duna), which is the provider of all public service television, radio and online content services and public service news agency activities. While Duna's operations are subject to institutional control (Board of Public Service Foundation, Public Service Fiscal Council, Public Service Council), MTVA is controlled exclusively by the Media Council.

Duna is really just a facade; it has no real resources, and it does not produce or buy content. Its annual budget for 2023 was HUF 2.2 billion, with an average staff of 92, and nearly 80% of its costs went on personnel (Duna, 2024). Then there is MTVA, which has no meaningful external control but had a budget of HUF 127.8 billion for 2023, with an average staff of 2,144 (MTVA, 2024).

In the European Union, there are rules on the funding of public service media precisely to ensure that competition is not distorted by unlawful state aid (European Commission, 2009). It is highly questionable how well the Hungarian public service media system complies with these rules. Mérték Media Monitor, a think tank, filed a complaint with the European Commission in 2016 concerning

unlawful state aid, but the Commission closed the investigation in 2024. It is highly doubtful that the Commission fully understood the problems associated with the Hungarian public service media (Horváth et al., 2024).

Also, as a result of the specific Hungarian situation, news blocks produced by public service media are broadcast on commercial radio stations, and this is one of the most important means by which public service media can influence the public. In practice, this works in such a way that the news blocks are recorded hourly at MTVA and distributed to the contracted partners, and the radio stations concerned do not have to employ their own news editors. Given the high cost of news production, many commercial radio stations broadcast the news blocks produced at MTVA.

Very little is known about this service; MTVA's annual report for 2021 only contains a half-sentence about it: "We also provide audio news content for 32 radio frequencies" (MTVA, 2021, pp. 115-116.) The 2023 annual report says even less: "[The M1] channel directorate also produces the news blocks that are heard on several rural and metropolitan radio stations" (MTVA, 2024, p. 78). This solution is a good example of how, instead of censoring content by administrative means, a media system can be created in which financial incentives ensure that content is centrally produced and thus highly controlled.

STATE ADVERTISING SPENDING

The market distortion of state advertising spending has been well-researched over the past decade, and indeed, political preferences have been unprecedented in the decisions of state advertisers. However, the problem is not a Hungarian one, and there are plenty of examples in the literature about governing parties rewarding media loyal to them by buying advertising space.

According to Bátorfy (2022), market distortion through state advertising spending is a rational phenomenon from the point of view of political economy, but its dangers can be compensated by a healthy media market. However, this requires both a large, multi-player market and democratic control over the government that ensures transparency and accountability, and thus a kind of constraint. The author concludes that the logic of traditional economics does not apply when a government has access to almost unlimited and uncontrolled resources.

Indeed, the practice of state advertising spending in Hungary is spectacularly distorting the market, and there is a wealth of data and calculations available to support this claim. The phenomenon can be analysed from four main angles: (1) the

increase in the volume of state advertising spending, (2) the increasing concentration of spending since the 2010s, (3) the positioning of pro-government players in different media segments and lack of state spending of independent players, and (4) the extremely large share of state advertising spending in some media.

The first issue is the increase in the volume of state advertising spending. The joint data visualisation project of Mérték Media Monitor and the Átlátszó investigative portal examined spending between 2006 and 2018. The figures clearly show a spectacular increase in the amount of spending, but this did not start in 2010, but later, in the 2014 government term (Bátorfy-Urbán, 2019). This may be surprising at first sight, but it is not really, as the media landscape changed significantly after the 2014 elections, with the ruling party creating a much more diversified portfolio after the previous Simicska era. With the Simicska rupture, Fidesz lost a significant part of its media background and had to build up several new media brands, and the cost of financing also increased. The more the pro-government media empire expanded, the more it cost.

The second important phenomenon is the increasing concentration of spending. Urbán (2015) examined the Herfindahl-Hirschman Index (HHI) and the C4 concentration coefficient of state advertising spending in six media segments between 2006 and 2013. A sharp increase in concentration was observed in the daily newspaper market, the magazine market, the radio market and the outdoor advertising market after 2010, i.e. while under the socialist government, state advertisers advertised in a wide range of media, under the Fidesz government state resources in these sectors have mainly been channelled to a few selected media. During this period, no such change was observed in the television market, while the online market showed a slightly different, wave-like trend in terms of concentration indicators.

The third well-described phenomenon is the market distortion effect. This is the basis of the complaint that the Mérték Media Monitor, together with other complainants, submitted to the European Commission in 2018. Among other things, the submission made comparisons between media brands that are roughly similar in size and attract similar audiences, suggesting that their advertising value should be roughly similar according to formal logic. The research used the Kantar Hungary advertising monitoring database, which shows list-price advertising spend. Below are two time-series plots associated with the complaint, with updated data.

Figure 1 shows data about two Budapest talk radio stations, Inforádió and Klubrádió. The two stations had similar reach and listenership (when they were still participating in the radio audience measurement, Klubrádió's listenership was even greater), and before 2010, the two stations had similar revenues from state advertising. Klubrádió is a left/liberal radio station and is highly critical of

the Fidesz government that has been in power since 2010, while Inforádió is right-wing oriented and quite loyal to the Fidesz government. This probably explains the fact that from 2011 onwards, Klubrádió hardly received any state advertising, while at the same time, the advertising decisions of state institutions spectacularly favoured Inforádió. Klubrádió lost its frequency in 2021, after which it was removed from the Kantar database. Interestingly, the state advertising budget for Inforádió started to decrease after Klubrádió lost its frequency.

Figure 1: Klubrádió and Inforadio's revenue from state advertising at list price (2006-2023)

Source: author's editing based on Kantar Hungary data

Figure 2: RTL and TV2 revenue from state advertising at list prices (2006-2023)

Source: author's editing based on Kantar Hungary data

RTL and TV2 are the two leading commercial television channels in Hungary, with similar audience shares and revenues in the years under review. RTL was the market leader for a long time, but TV2 took the lead first in terms of revenue in 2017 and then, unsurprisingly, in terms of audience share in 2018. Even more interesting is what can be seen in the competition for state advertising: the two channels had similar revenues from this source until the early 2010s, but then the trends diverged. RTL was owned by the international RTL Group throughout the whole period, while TV2 was taken over by a pro-government investor at the end of 2013 and has remained with them ever since. As can be seen from the graph, after 2013, state advertising money started flowing to TV2, and RTL was put at a competitive disadvantage as a result.

The above examples are illustrative, but the pattern is clearly identifiable: among companies with similar audience reach and in close competition with each other, advertising goes to media that demonstrably support the interests of the ruling party (TV2) or at least in terms of editorial principles are loyal to the ruling party (Inforádió).

Finally, and this is the fourth clearly identifiable phenomenon in relation to state advertising, there are media companies for which the share of state advertising in their total advertising revenue is significant.

Figure 3: Some media brands with a large state advertising revenue share (2023)

Source: Horváth et al., 2024

Figure 3 clearly shows that there are media that obtain a significant share of advertising revenue from state sources. These are typically pro-government media, part of KESMA (9 out of 10 media brands), and would obviously face a

serious challenge if they had to compete on fair market terms. Under real market conditions, it is inconceivable that a media company would obtain a significant part of its advertising revenue from the state: the state advertising revenue share is typically a few per cent.

It may be striking that the left-wing *Népszava* also features prominently on this list. There is a duality with *Népszava*: the content is critical of the government, and there have been some good journalistic achievements, but there is a clear governmental intention to maintain the paper, and thus journalistic freedom has its limits. If state resources were to dry up, *Népszava* would probably face difficulties similar to those of the pro-government papers.

All of the factors examined above, i.e. the increase in the volume of state advertising spending, the high concentration of spending, the strong preference for pro-government media products, and the extremely high exposure of some media to the state, provide evidence of the market-distorting effect of state advertising. Bátorfy and Urbán (2020) have described how the arbitrary use of public resources distorts competition, and firms that are truly market-oriented cannot compete with those backed by essentially unlimited public resources. This can easily lead to the disappearance of market-based news sources and, through this, to a loss of diversity and a loss of democracy.

THE ROLE OF THE MEDIA ECOSYSTEM

One of the peculiarities of the Hungarian media system is that state intervention is much broader than simple ownership and the state financing of media loyal to the government. A real feature of the system is that, in addition to the media industry, the role of pro-government investors in the so-called media ecosystem has become significant, further increasing the vulnerability of independent media companies. The media ecosystem refers to companies and sectors that are not involved in content production but still have a significant impact on the operations of media companies (Kovács et al., 2021).

Media agencies act as intermediaries between media companies and advertisers. The agencies are entrusted by advertisers with campaign planning, i.e. media agencies buy advertising space from media companies. It is therefore a typical commercial market in which the state does not, in principle, have a significant role.

In Hungary, the management of state advertising became really concentrated after 2014, when the government established the National Communications Office (abbreviated as NKOH in Hungarian). This office is responsible for state

communication: all public institutions can only buy advertising space through NKOH; thus, the system has been centralised. Under the scheme, NKOH issues a public procurement notice and concludes a framework agreement with the winning media agencies, and the entire public sector communication activity is conducted through these framework agreements. The specificity of the situation is that the NKOH has not concluded an agreement with a media agency that is well-known among commercial advertisers but with an operator that is demonstrably close to the government.

It is not possible in this paper to analyse in depth the history of NKOH's tenders and framework agreements, but in any case, since 2018, the New Land Media – Lounge Design consortium has been NKOH's only contracting partner. Both companies in the consortium have the same owner, Gyula Balásy, which puts one player in an extremely strong position in the media agency market.

Distribution companies are very important in the ecosystem. This is another area where changes have been made in recent years. In the television broadcasting market and, in parallel, in the internet service-providing market, ownership concentration has increased significantly. The government-owned 4iG had already acquired stakes in the broadcasting companies Antenna Hungária and Digi, but the real acceleration occurred in January 2023. The Hungarian state and 4iG acquired Vodafone Hungary, which has 3.8 million subscribers, leaving two large groups in the previously relatively diverse Hungarian market: 4iG and the German-owned Magyar Telekom. This gives the pro-government group of investors and the state itself a very strong position in the infrastructure through which content consumption and communication take place (Madzin, 2022).

The importance of the ecosystem can also be observed in the print market. There are two major players in the field of the subscription distribution of newspapers: the state-owned Magyar Posta and MédiaLOG-DMHM, a subsidiary of Mediaworks and thus part of the government-owned KESMA. Of the two players, the latter is increasingly dominant: In 2021, Magyar Posta stopped delivering daily newspapers to the door, and in 2023, it stopped selling printed newspapers in post offices. This makes access to newspapers more difficult, especially in smaller municipalities, and gives a company close to the government a particularly strong position in newspaper distribution.

In the market for printed sheets, printing itself came under strong control, with KESMA taking over the printing plants capable of producing large numbers of sheets. The weekly Magyar Hang, which was launched in 2018 and is critical of the government, has to be printed in Slovakia because the publisher could not sign a contract with any printer in Hungary.

PRESSURE ON INDEPENDENT MEDIA

The capture of the Hungarian media and market distortion not only involves strengthening the pro-government media companies but at least as important is the weakening of independent media. This includes putting pressure on independent actors, initiating systematic smear campaigns and making journalistic work more difficult.

Legal proceedings, harassment by public authorities

In Hungary, the most recent and most worrying instrument of pressure is the Sovereignty Protection Act² passed in 2023, from which the Sovereignty Protection Office (SPO) was set up as a result. Editorials, professional organisations and NGOs alike have expressed their concern about the law and in 2024, the SPO launched its first investigations. A report published by the SPO about the investigative portal Átlátszó included untruths that led the publisher to sue the SPO (Átlátszó, 2024).

In the coming years, it will become clear what tools the SPO will have to deal with the media and civil society: will it try to influence them primarily through intimidation and the production of defamatory material, or will its activities have even more serious consequences?

Hungarian newsrooms already have experience of what it is like when the state treats journalists as enemies and tries to obstruct their work by any means. The Pegasus scandal revealed that the Hungarian secret services had used spy weapons against journalists and a media owner. A series of articles launched in the summer of 2021 uncovered the Hungarian threads of an international investigation, revealing the names of those involved, including well-known Hungarian investigative journalists (Panyi-Pethő, 2021). The use of intelligence tools not only directly affects journalists' work but also has an indirect effect. Sources will become very cautious if they do not believe that meetings and conversations with journalists will really remain secret. This makes it more difficult to obtain information and uncover cases.

A less serious practice, but one that nonetheless has a major impact on the lives of editorial offices, is the filing of lawsuits asking for corrections. This is, of course, something that a media company must accept and, in line with professional journalistic standards, strive to avoid. It is also possible, however, that lawsuits may be brought without any basis, with the express purpose of

² Act LXXXVIII of 2023 on the Protection of National Sovereignty

draining a journalist's resources so that they cannot continue to work as a journalist. A legendary case was when, following a series of articles on parking-related corruption activity described in the 444 online portal, the Municipality of Ferencváros challenged the articles on 50 points. In the end, the paper was ordered to make three corrections, but none of them related to the substance of the articles. Dániel Ács, a journalist who investigated the parking corruption, summarised the aim of the lawsuits as follows. "Rather, it was to wear down, distract and cover up. They calculated, correctly by the way, that the municipality, courtesy of the taxpayers of the district, could mobilise orders of magnitude more capacity, more financial resources, many more lawyers and PR professionals with experience in remedial cases than 444" (Ács, 2018).

Stigmatisation of journalists

The hostile portrayal of the independent media was already present in the ruling party's communication before the Sovereignty Protection Act: independent journalists are often called foreign agents and traitors. The "Sorosing" started as early as in the 2010s, but in recent years independent media have more commonly been referred to as the "dollar media".³ Research from the 2024 election campaign shows that 47 per cent of political ads on Facebook and Google conveyed a hostile narrative, including one that was clearly identified as aimed at discrediting government critics, including journalists. It is noteworthy that the majority of political ads were not placed by political parties or politicians, but by government-linked organisations and pro-government media (Political Capital et al., 2024).

Despite years of incitement, Hungary is still a fundamentally safe place for journalists: there are no physical attacks on journalists, and there have been no murders of journalists. There are examples of harassment and threats against journalists, and of course, these also have an impact on journalistic work.

The most comprehensive study on the subject is by Tófalvy (2022), although his paper is a summary of Hungarian research originally published in 2017. In total, 20 online journalists (14 men and 6 women) were interviewed in the form of in-depth interviews and focus group discussions. The article distinguishes

³ On the website of the pro-government daily *Magyar Nemzet*, the first article under the tag "dollarmedia" was published on 13 December 2022, and by January 2025, altogether, 81 articles had been given this tag. Origo, the pro-government news site, published its first article with this tag on 12 December 2022, and since then, the counter has reached 91.

eight basic forms of online aggression: rhetorical aggression, trolling, bullying, threats, public shaming, cyber-attack or hacking, invasion of privacy and malicious social media activities. The most common types of harassment encountered by the journalists surveyed were rhetorical aggression and bullying, which almost all respondents had experienced. It is noteworthy that 40% of the respondents had experienced threats. Attila Varga, a former journalist for Index, has received numerous threatening messages in the course of his work, “including death threats and those in which his child was threatened or his wife was threatened with sexual violence”.

Harassment can affect journalists in three ways. First, there is a kind of chilling effect (even self-censorship), which tends to make both readers and journalists avoid interaction and dialogue. The second effect is the so-called desensitisation effect, i.e. journalists gradually become desensitised to offensive and aggressive messages. A particularly damaging consequence of this is that totally unacceptable behaviour becomes the norm and is accepted both by journalists (“it’s part of the job”) and by the social environment. The third main problem is the intensity of aggression against traditionally disadvantaged social groups, which, in the case of this research, involves violence against female journalists. Women are more often the target of harassment than male journalists, and this often manifests itself in threats of sexual violence (Tófalvy, 2022).

There is good reason to believe that the situation has deteriorated rather than improved in recent years. A memorable story was when the pro-government media published scurrilous articles one after the other about Gábor Miklósi, a journalist for Index, because he did not stand up before the Hungarian national team’s match while singing the song *Nélküled*, a favourite song of football fans. A few days later, antisemitic messages appeared on the streets of Budapest, with a photo of Miklósi and another Index journalist, András Dezső (Narancs.hu, 2019).

It is easy to see that such harassment is very damaging, even if it has not yet led to a direct physical attack. Journalists who suffer harassment are affected by what happens to them; it takes time and energy to deal with the harassment, and they have to cope psychologically.

Obstruction of journalists’ work

Editors have to face the fact that doing journalistic work means more and more legal work and, at the same time, higher legal costs. A common case of this is when a public institution refuses to disclose public interest data requested by a journalist, and the journalist pursues the matter through legal action. This

incurs both time costs, as it can take years to extract the data and financial costs for media companies.

It is now almost a truism that journalists' work is hampered in many ways by the ruling party. Government politicians, except in some very special cases, do not give interviews, ministries do not answer questions sent to them, and employees of institutions (including schools and hospitals) are not allowed to provide information. It is common for independent media to be denied access to important events, including press conferences (TASZ, 2020). An emblematic example of the difficulties journalists face is the fact that during the COVID-19 epidemic outbreak, journalists were denied access to basic information, and essential data was not available. The situation was also special because, in that situation, it would have been in the public interest to share information: it was not only a matter of controlling public power but also of helping fight the epidemic and protect human lives.

In recent times, editorial teams have also had to face new challenges. Cyber-attacks against independent media are a regular occurrence, often rendering websites inaccessible. Readers perceive this as a passing inconvenience, but the situation is more serious, as publishers have to increase the resources they devote to IT security, which, of course, means increased costs. The situation is so serious that the International Press Institute (2023) has already identified such a series of attacks as a form of digital censorship.

CONCLUSION

The transformation of the Hungarian media system in the 2010s is a sad example of how a development path can be reversed. At the time of regime change, it seemed self-evident that democratic institutions and a market economy would provide a framework for long-term stability and prosperity in Hungary.

Today, both in professional discourse and in public debate, it is often said that the current Hungarian media system resembles, in many respects, the public sphere of the communist era. In addition to the obvious differences, such as the state of technology, it is important to point out that while the communist party controlled the public through administrative bans and direct intervention and censorship, today, it is much more characterised by market intervention.

These market interventions can take many forms. Some of them guarantee access to resources for certain actors, such as the financing of public service media, the tendering practice associated with radio frequencies, the ownership expansion of political investors or state advertising spending. These are solutions

similar to those found in other countries, but the Hungarian situation is more specific in terms of the degree of intervention and the market-distorting effect.

There are also instruments that intervene in market mechanisms in ways that are not at first glance obvious and, therefore, play a much smaller role in both the literature and the policy discourse. A good example of this is the way in which mergers in the media market are authorised or how intervention in the media ecosystem is allowed. These are less visible but still crucial instruments of contemporary Hungarian government media policy.

Last but not least, there is the shrinking independent media. The remaining independent players are inherently at a competitive disadvantage because of the unjustified economic and competitive advantage that pro-government players enjoy, and fair competition is therefore being undermined. Moreover, political, legal or even psychological pressures further weaken the independent media simply by tying up corporate and individual resources and distracting attention from the core activity of journalism.

The specificity of the Hungarian media system is partly due to the fact that the tools presented here were built in an unparalleled short period of time; a decade was enough to change the media landscape. The tools would not individually be suitable for transforming the media system, but together, they prove to be sufficient and very effective. The captured Hungarian media system as a whole is no longer serving the public good but is representing private interests by placing a large part of the corporate sector under the influence of a politically well-defined group.

Another peculiarity of the transformation is that it has taken place within the European Union. It is difficult to say why the EU institutions did not use the tools at their disposal, but there is no doubt that no meaningful attempt was made to prevent the Hungarian media market from being captured. The complexity of the system and the lack of clarity about the real purpose of the individual steps that were taken in many cases may have played a role in this.

For the time being, no one can say when there will be an opportunity to transform the current media system. Sooner or later, that time will come, but for the time being, there is no real professional debate on the purpose, the main elements thereof, or the way to implement a new media policy. Accepting the specificities of Hungary (small market, isolated language), it would be necessary to outline the contours of a media system that is resistant to future attempts at capture and capable of defending the fundamental values of democratic public life.

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IDENTITY, PRAGMATISM, AND THE FUTURE OF EUROPE. AN EXPLORATION IN HUNGARIAN MEDIA DISCOURSES

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ABSTRACT: *In this paper we summarize the experiences of Hungarian media discourse analysis related to different symbolic and pragmatic aspects of Europeanization. First, we review the discourses concerning national identity and different understandings of Europe. Secondly, we present the lessons learned from the Hungarian debates on the future of Europe shading more light on how the European Union should develop and the representation of these debates in the media. In our analysis we rely on the corpus of articles selected within the MEDIATIZED EU project between July 2021 and March 2022. In a highly polarized discursive field our results identified opposing media discourses depending on the media outlets: the government's discourse about national sovereignty with constituting elements of a cultural/ primordial identity based on Christianity, the importance of the nation and family, placing member-states at the heart of the European construct with different degrees of rejection of the EU; and one, less prominent discourse presents in the independent media about European values and a rather integrationist stance.*

KEYWORDS: *national sovereignty, identity, European Union, , European values, integrationism, intergovernmentalism*

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INTRODUCTION

The aim of the of the current paper is to study the media framing of the symbolic and pragmatic elements related to Europeanization. It analyses media discourses about national identity different understandings of Europe, and different conceptions about the European Union, its institutional construct. The topics are obviously interconnected, but they are linked to different conceptual contexts. Issues related to the connection between national identity and the meanings of Europe are part of a tradition that deals with issues of collective identity and multiple identities and often result in a symbolic discourse. Questions related to the actual or ideal functioning of the European Union on the other hand are more of pragmatic character, although often shaped by the previous ideas and ideals.

National and European identity began to attract academic interest in the 1990s, and the impact of affective attachment to Europe or the nation on attitudes towards the European integration project has been investigated (e.g. Duchesne-Frogner 1995, Hooghe-Marks 2005, Bruter 2005, Risse 2010). According to the post-functionalist approach to European integration, group membership or loyalty provides a successful alternative framework for understanding and interpreting European integration, as opposed to the complex task of rational evaluation, where a certain level of cognitive ability, knowledge and effort would need to be mobilised in order to relate to an abstract construct such as the EU (Hooghe and Marks 2009). The different understandings of the European Union draw on the tradition of deliberative research and is informed by the EU-wide debate on the issue during the period under review. Between March 2021 and May 2022, a series of deliberative events based on a multilingual digital platform was held to ask questions and make suggestions about the future of Europe (Council of the European Union 2022). The proposals received were discussed and processed in panels of mixed composition of citizens, following the methodology of balanced deliberative debates. Our media corpus covered a significant part of this period and therefore the macro-themes that emerged in the press reflected the events indirectly, as the deliberative initiative itself did not receive much press coverage.

According to previous studies on discourses on the EU in the Hungarian media, the pre- and post-accession period was characterised by a more pragmatic and technocratic approach to the topic (Terestyéni 2004). Nevertheless, discourses on Hungary's 'return' to Europe, the debates around Hungarian land, the Hungarian ethnic minorities or the EU issue, the defender of certain norms and values, but also the EU challenged by the identity crisis, were present as more symbolic discourses from the beginning (Vidra 2006). However, the change

of government in 2010, together with the change of the political and economic context, also brought a symbolic change in symbolic discourses, with the rise of populism and the characteristics of ‘illiberal democracy’ (Köröseyi and Patkós 2015, Enyedi 2015). The technocratic rhetoric gave way to revolutionary metaphors about Hungary not becoming a colony of the EU or the opening to the East (Martin 2013). Identity, and even more so national identity, became a very important theme that framed the general perception of Europe. However, despite these negative, governmental campaigns targeting the EU, positive public perceptions of the EU still managed to increase. Data show a general tendency of ‘disillusionment’ of the Hungarians until 2012, while since then the share of positive perceptions follows an increasing trend. In 2004 Hungary was around the EU average in terms of positive perception of the EU, it dropped below the EU average and became one of the less positive one and by 2012, just to increase around the average again by 2020. In terms of the attachment to the European project Hungarians were among the most Europhile countries together with Poland, Latvia, and Luxemburg by 2021 (Göncz -Lengyel 2021). In order to better understand how public perceptions were seemingly not affected by negative media discourses it is important to study media discourses on the subject in detail.

Our results reflect the polarized character of the Hungarian media landscape in general as opposing media discourses were indeed identified on the themes of national identity and different understandings of the European Union depending on the media outlets. Two main discourses were identified, the government’s discourse about national sovereignty with constituting elements of a cultural/primordial identity based on Christianity, the importance of the nation and family, placing member-states at the heart of the European construct with different degrees of rejection of the EU; and one, less prominent discourse in general, present in the independent media about superior European values and a rather integrationist stance.

The samples were based on a corrected quota of the MEDIATIZED EU corpus, filtering out mere news items and repetitions if they did not contain substantial new information. The sample on national identity and different understandings of Europe contained 71, and the sample on the future of Europe, i.e. different understandings of the European Union 120 items. Two thirds of the items on identity issues and three quarters of the items on the future of Europe appeared in the pro-government media.

NATIONAL IDENTITY DISCOURSES AND DIFFERENT UNDERSTANDINGS OF EUROPE

The problem of European identity raises the question of how attachments to different territorial levels are interconnected. Do national and European identities reinforce or weaken each other, or can European identity be understood as a ‘thinner’ identity, a secondary attachment, which is shaped by universal norms, political and legal principles, democratic rights, as opposed to ‘thick’, inherited contents (Habermas 1998; Delanty 1995; Cederman 2001 Bruter 2004, Favell 2005, Risse 2010, Göncz and Lengyel 2016).

Perceptions of Europe are embedded in national contexts, so the meaning of Europe may vary from nation to nation. The ‘frame’ in which Europe appears is based on the different cultural reserves of nations, including knowledge, habits, histories, memories and worldviews that follow national specificities of state-building (Díez Medrano 2003).

Risse argues that beyond a Europeanism based on modernist values and inclusiveness, which remains the prerogative of a highly educated minority, exclusive nationalism does not necessarily lead to anti-Europeanism, but to a more exclusive, ‘nationalist’ concept of Europe (i.e. ‘Fortress Europe’). He refers to this ‘transposition’ of the concept of the nation when he argues that European identities are increasingly embedded in national identities (Risse 2010).

In addition to historical theories of nation and state formation, group theories in social psychology also provide a way of interpreting certain aspects of national identity issues. Social identity theory (Tajfel 1981) defines social identity as that part of the self that arises from belonging to a group and the values and emotions associated with it.

Two *main discourses* were identified, the government’s discourse about *national sovereignty* with constituting elements of a cultural/ primordial identity based on Christianity, the importance of the nation and family with different sub-discourses, and one, much less prominent in general, present in the independent media about *superior European values*. Part of the articles in the independent media could not break out of the frame of the dominant discourse and developed a critical stance towards its elements.

Discourses on national or European identity were often triggered by certain events: a national or international conference on the subject, a book launch, a decision of the European Court of Justice, a declaration of a European party, the publication of the European migration strategy, but there was also the Hungarian elections with a referendum attached (03/04/2022), the war in Ukraine, references to different public opinion polls. Pro-government media rather commented on public opinion polls of pro-government polling institutions (KINCS or

Századvég), whereas independent media mentioned international sources such as the Eurobarometer, nevertheless, placing the results in a European context was present both in *origo.hu* and *hvg.hu*. From May to November 2021 Hungary was president of the Committee of Ministers of the Council of Europe (which is not an EU institution) with the main mission to promote national minority rights together with the importance of family and Christianity. The French elections were also referenced several times.

Identity-related discourses were very often a communication of politicians, public intellectuals, professionals, especially in the television, and the pro-government media (MN, ORIGO), whereas journalists' articles were more common in the independent media. Independent media also referenced more international or European experts. However, identity-related discourses in pro-government media were often present in independent media as well publishing very similar content that often remained unreflected.

Reasoning based on economic kind of rational cost-benefit analysis, gathering pros and cons or references to specific policy questions stands for a pragmatic or utilitarian logic. On the other hand, discourses based on culture, history, an ideological or an emotional approach of the subject is understood as a symbolic way to relate to it. Direct discourses about national or European identity are also symbolic ones. Nevertheless, different understandings of the nation and Europe or what values they stand for can also be grasped through discourses that use more subtle ways of communication such as placing the subject in a European context or the selection of the subject (decision of the ECJ, what topics are presented from a public opinion survey for example). Such indirect mentions of European values were rather present in the independent media sources (NSZ, HVG) just as a pragmatic approach of the subject in the pro-government ORIGO.

Defence of national sovereignty and identity

The main characteristic of the government's discourse about national sovereignty is that it puts forward elements of cultural identity, and with its primordial character can be considered as a "thick" identity. The main elements are the importance of religion and more particularly Christianity, while family and traditional gender roles are key and recurring components of this discourse. The triangle of "God, homeland, family" are referred often. It is a government discourse about national identity, where Europe remains an important point of reference. While the essence of the national identity remains similar, three sub-discourses exist depending on the perceived nature

of Hungary's relation to Europe. Conferences on the subject, book launches, national holidays are all opportunities to activate this discourse. This discourse, and sub-discourses appear in the propaganda media *MN* was the main media outlet that communicated this dominant, mainly symbolic national sovereignty discourse with varying intensity of anti-EU sentiments from mutual respect and co-existence through Hungary saving the idea of Europe and Europe itself to direct opposition and self-defence. It has also integrated more technical, pragmatic, policy-related elements into this symbolic dominant discourse to form a coherent one. Indirect or pragmatic aspects of this discourse, such as the successful economic performance of the country were rather present in *ORIGO*. In the analysed period, identity-related discourses seldom appeared in television (*M1* and *HÍR TV*): these discourses appeared related to presentation of what has been said in conferences (about questions of national identity) that included several speakers or new elements in the EU's migration strategy – all of which gave possibility to reinforce the main content of the dominant government discourse about national sovereignty.

The EU as equal: "A strong Europe can only be built based on strong nations" (Defence of national sovereignty and identity sub-discourse)

This sub-discourse has a neutral stance towards Europe and the EU and is based on an intergovernmental approach rejecting a European "superstate" or a federalist idea of the EU. Hungary and the EU are seen as equals, their relation based on mutual respect where they can both learn from each other. Hungary, with its different kind of national identity, based on traditional values is seen as an "alternative" that the EU should accept. This is a discourse often held for a foreign public or at an EU event.

[...] it is not a superstate that there is a need for, but a strong Europe of strong nations – declared the minister of justice [...] we can see that those are the natural communities that constitute a nation, that are at the roots of national identity, such as the family, the nation, and regional cooperation like the V4. These strong communities carry the sovereignty of a nation and form the basis of strong member states, while a strong European Union is based on the mutual cooperation of the latter (HÍR TV 2021.07.22.)

Hungary as the saviour of a mistaken EU/ Europe: "We will restart Europe" (Defence of national sovereignty and identity sub-discourse)

Hungary, with its values (Christianity, the family, importance of the nation and traditions) stands as the holder of the “real” values. The general idea of EU or Europe is not rejected, only “false” Europeanness is rejected. Europe is going through an identity-crisis in the sense that it abandoned its Christian roots and traditional values. In this sub-discourse, the EU and Europe needs to be saved – and Hungary appears as saviour, has a mission, in this sense Hungary is seen as superior.

In another version of this discourse, the EU is said to lack a common European demos and a common language, thus needing reinforcement in its cultural dimensions.

To get stronger, Europe needs to return to the traditional values...– declared Péter Szijjártó, minister of foreign affairs and trade in Strasbourg on Tuesday. At the interfaith conference organised by the Hungarian presidency of the Council of Europe the minister emphasized that Hungary leads the way in protecting traditional European values. He highlighted that the international liberal mainstream leads serious attacks against families, freedom of religion and rights of ethnic minorities resulting in an opinion dictatorship and opinion hegemony. If someone dares to defend these values defining Europe they face exclusion, criticism, being considered a joke or someone who lives in the past. Péter Szijjártó declared: there is a need to take actions against this, because Europe is weakened, is losing its population and its weight in world economy. If action is not taken, Europe will be in great trouble, as it will lose everything that connects it with its identity and heritage – he stated. ... – We protect families, just like Pope Francis, we are clear about that a family consists of a father, a mother, and children [...] we dare to defend Christian communities [...] due to our historical heritage we are sensitive to protection of the rights of ethnic minorities – he said. – Traditional European values seem to hold more importance in the East of the Iron Curtain [...] (MN 2021 09 29)

National identity under attack: “Who gets mixed up with bran is eaten by pigs”² (Defence of national sovereignty and identity sub-discourse)

In this sub-discourse, the EU (or other enemies) is intentionally working on cultural alienation, spreading individualism and the deconstruction of strong communities such as the family or Christianity. Hungary is in constant battle

2 „Aki korpa közé keveredik, felfalják a disznók”

to preserve its identity, the “attacks” are diverse (see the section on out-groups). This discourse is intended for pro-government local audience. This discourse is very much in line with the idea of symbolic threat and the fear of loss of Hungarian cultural identity. This sub-discourse is rather present in MN and much less in ORIGO.

Who are “We”? (the in-group within the defence of national sovereignty and identity discourse)

Several understandings of the in-group exist within the dominant government discourse about national sovereignty, which are all some kind of “extensions” of the nation. These diverse forms of in-group definitions can be found throughout the different sub-discourses. Often not made explicit who the “we” stands for, it is implicitly assumed that the “we” are the “Hungarians”. Nevertheless, sometimes Central Europe appears as the regional community where Hungary belongs as opposed to a wider Europe. Central Europe is seen as a region distinct from both the East and the West in terms of their worldviews, their similar history and their national identity based on shared values which lead to similar responses towards the migrant crisis for example. With their pragmatic cooperation based on similar needs and interests these countries became an unavoidable political factor within the EU. When using a pragmatic argumentation, they are rather referred to as V4 countries. Mentions of Central Europe and V4 countries were rather present in ORIGO.

During the analysed period, however, out of the V4 it was rather Poland and Hungary that were in the focus, especially with regards to questions related to Christianity and the rule of law where these countries felt and were challenged by the EU with similar sanctions. Discourses related to Central Europe or the V4 contain both pragmatic and symbolic elements, sometimes these countries are considered as the driving force of the EU, but they can also be perceived as threatening to the EU due to their superiority.

Similarly, the boundaries of the Hungarian nation in certain sub-discourses include Hungarian minorities outside the country. Hungarian ethnic minorities are important part of the nation where the EU’s role is to preserve this. Often referred to as Hungarians from the Carpathian Basin.

When with Russia’s war in Ukraine discourses about Eastern opening and closer relations with Russia became difficult one of the incoherence to deal with was the suffering of the Hungarian minority living in Ukraine. To resolve this incoherence holders of this discourse pointed to the fact that Hungarian minorities already suffered before the war because of the Ukrainian government and its restrictive measures as well.

Furthermore, the importance of ethnic minorities is extended to other nations as well, protection of German minorities in Hungary is also considered important, should be considered as part of human rights.

Who are “Them” (the out-group within the defence of national sovereignty and identity discourse)?

Various out-groups or sources of threats exists within the national sovereignty discourse. Similarly, to the various in-group definitions, these are also to be found across all of the mentioned national sovereignty sub-discourses. Brussels stands for the institutions of the EU that are threatening Hungarian sovereignty when concrete pragmatic, policy measures are taking place. Less often threats are coming from international and national NGOs such as Amnesty International, Helsinki Bizottság, TASZ, Transparency International. When overall values are scrutinized the out-group takes the form of “western leaders”, the “decadent West”, globalization, the European/ globalized left or even atheists undermining national identity and its constituting elements (Christianity, family). George Soros is a general threat. Sometimes ideologies are blamed when identity conflicts presented as “war of ideologies” where Hungarians are under the attack of Marxist or liberal ideas. Migrants, illegal migrants are also a very important threat that can destroy Europe’s cultural identity, in some cases population replacement is an intended phenomenon. Sometimes migrants also specifically refers to Muslims (undermining Christian universalism). With regards to migration Europe is sometimes compared to the decline of the West-Roman Empire.

These outgroups are always threatening Hungarian national identity and try to undermine its elements (Christianity, traditional values, family). Families, traditional gender roles and children more specifically are threatened by the homosexual propaganda/ LGBTQ and gender ideology that falsely declare themselves as European values. Beyond the cultural threat, the West is also threatening the Hungarian way of life with its decadent materialism. Western materialism, a very pragmatic threat, is, however, denounced with a very symbolic reference to a Hungarian poem where the West is called a “Pig-headed Lord”³ with an intention of “killing us”.

The EU is often compared to the Habsburg Monarchy (supranational and globalized), as opposed to national values (note the incoherence: Muslims are reproached to challenge Christian universalism the very same universalism that is criticized in another context). Beyond historical comparisons, present-time comparisons include the case of Canada as far as critique of the liberal system is

3 Ady Endre: Harc a Nagyúrral

concerned, with Justin Trudeau who is said to admire Eastern, not democratic, political systems, and France an example of “Muslim invasion”. France was a recurring point of reference over the period: the case of the French right’s critique with the display of the EU flag supposedly replacing the French flag at the country’s taking up of the EU Council presidency. References to France is even more interesting with presidential elections in France in the spring of 2022 where Marine Le Pen, leader of France’s far-right with similar sovereigntist message, is supported by the Hungarian government.

Pragmatic elements

National sovereignty discourses have pragmatic or pseudo-pragmatic elements as well, both present in MN and ORIGO. Legal questions having an important level of technicality seem pragmatic. As a response to the EU critiques of the rule-of-law in Hungary, the concept of “*constitutional identity*” has been created. In its name it shares similarities with Habermas’s concept of “constitutional patriotism” (Habermas 1992) (referring to a “thin” identity based on a civic kind of attachment to a political entity that enables the formation of identity at the supranational level, such as the EU, beyond the ethnicity and shared cultural or historical traditions), however, in Hungary’s case it stands for quite the opposite, the right of Hungarians to preserve traditional elements and reference to Christianity (a “thick” understanding of identity) in their constitution despite the EU, as an affirmation of their national identity.

Discourses related to Hungary’s economic performance and economic interests can also be considered as more pragmatic approaches, the “opening to the East” discourse about Eastern countries economic superiority is a discourse with a global orientation, EU is sometimes not even mentioned, or it is considered as weightless. Within this discourse Hungary’s superiority is confirmed as the country is seen to be performing well, better than other EU countries with regards to economic indicators (growth, employment), the health system and vaccination (in the context of the covid crisis). National sovereignty is threatened within this discourse when the achievements of “utilities reduction” or Hungary’s energy-dependence from Russia come into play. Hungary’s economic performance is especially mentioned in ORIGO.

A (pseudo-)pragmatic discourse is the demographic sub-discourse when Hungarian sovereignty is dealt with through population dynamics, migration, birth rates, etc. Conferences are being organised about this topic in reaffirmation of national identity as it entails family and traditional gender roles as well as protection of children. It is another opportunity to talk about

migration questions and the identity-crisis of Europe (in Europe there is a lower birth rate because women chose career over their role as mother). Hungary outperforms other EU countries in terms of population dynamics and their handling of immigrants as well.

Counter-discourse: discreditation of the dominant government discourse

The discourse that appears in the independent media (NSZ, HVG) is often a reactive one: the aim being to discredit, to criticize or to provide counter-examples to the governmental one, but always remaining in the frame set by the latter.

Discreditation happens by taking an important element of the governmental discourse and providing another interpretation. NSZ, for example, argues that discourse based on Christianity is a “post-Christian” one: they draw the attention to the fact that the right is not using Christian symbols but ancient Hungarian ones instead, the discourse in reality uses elements of new paganism. In an identity-building, constructivist logic it uses history to create a national narrative and spread these through previously reliable sources such as the National Museum, or at event such as the 2018 inauguration of the National Riding Hall (with horses being key elements in discourses promoting the ancient Hungarian way of life). According to a social psychologist

[...] it is obvious that the prime minister tries to create a conservative tradition, but, as he lacks creativity, he uses past clichés and references to traditions that have nothing to do with socialism or democracy. He builds on that faith is important to Hungarians, that we think ourselves and our history to be special. He appeals to this with a communication strengthening self-confidence through historical references. [...] Just as János Kádár was the father of the people, he also tries to fill this role. The message of the expensive decor is that we, Hungarians, are better than anyone else, that the whole West learns from us and praises us (NSZ 2021.09.19.)

Another example for discreditation is when NSZ takes the “Eastern opening” discourse, that is seemingly a pragmatic one putting forward Hungary’s economic interests and shows how it is instead a value-based discourse. Similarly, they argue that despite the government declared objective to preserve national sovereignty in the name of (anti-liberal) democracy, it leads to less democracy, and they are presenting identity as a constant war.

European superiority, European values discourse

The independent media did not present a real alternative to the dominant primordial-cultural governmental discourse on national sovereignty. In fact, mentions of national sovereignty or national identity were very seldom in HVG. In much less prominent, rather indirect discourses present in the independent media (NSZ, HVG) Europe appears as an example, the guardian of certain values that are threatened or have disappeared in Hungary, although Hungary accepted these values when joining the EU (for example that no negative discrimination will occur towards the LGBTQ community).

We can see what they consider as such values through the presentation of the results of public opinion polls, through what aspects are presented. The elements put forward are what people think of the preservation of democracy, the protection of human rights, but also what they think about migration, and the importance of national identity, gender equality. In these articles Hungarian public opinion appears in a European comparative context, and it is not that much the actual share of supporters of these values that count, but dimensions of opinion that are presented or not, as there is no mentions of opinions about Christianity, family or national minorities. It must be noted though that it is not clear whether the lack of these subjects comes from the survey itself or these are topics omitted by the article, in this sense, public opinion surveys also have the capacity of framing discourses.

Another indirect manifestation of the belief in existence of European values is when, to discredit the governmental discourse about the identity crisis of Europe, NSZ admits that Europe is indeed in crisis although for different reasons. It is not the decreasing importance of the family or Christianity that show the identity crisis of the European nations or Europe, but the crisis in the rule of law, the increasing appearance of illiberal systems, and the spread of populism all over Europe. If the EU, that stands for and should preserve values of democracy and the rule of law let all this happen without an answer that leads to a loss of authority.

Perceived European values are also to be grasped through concrete examples in an indirect way. As concrete examples are cited, this approach is a rather pragmatic one.

The lack of corruption is presented as a European value when describing the case of the city of Kaunas, Lithuania, Cultural Capital of Europe is evoked as a counter-example of Hungary where Pécs, when it was Cultural Capital in 2010 was associated with several cases of corruption. It is furthermore an occasion to cite the Lithuanian organizers when stating that European Cultural Capitals also stands for the reinforcement of European identity and let the focus on the cultural field beyond the economic cooperation.

This discourse in government-critical media (NSZ and HVG) often compares and links Orbán to Putin. Especially in terms of their anti-liberal struggles for national self-determination that serve only to take away the opportunity to the same self-determination from the people.

THE FUTURE OF EUROPE

In the following we briefly present the key elements of discursive strategies concerning alternative visions of the EU. Two main discourses can be identified, which contradict each other: the sovereigntist and the integrationist discourse. These are alternative visions of the ways of relating the nation to the supranational entity and third parties, which have a number of pragmatic problems and may also involve important symbolic content. They are complemented by fragments of discourse, one type of which deals with the intensity of integration and another type which questions the necessity of integration and membership in general.

The description touches upon the intersections with the representation of the West, and with other dominant discursive topics (like pandemic, migration, security). Where necessary, references to political statements and social media sources are provided.

What is needed is not a super-state, not the United States of Europe, but a strong Europe of strong nations, said Judit Varga, the Minister of Justice. By representing this position, Hungarian politics can also set an example for voters in other countries, she added. (HÍR TV 2021.07.22). While there is a need for a constructive dialogue on the future of Europe, it is the EU institutions whose conflicts make the future of the EU unpredictable today – she referred to the conflict between the EP and the Commission (ORIGO 2021.07.24).

The sovereigntist position – emphasizing the nation-state perspective – appears in the pro-government press often, in a uniform and simple way of expression, with positive content. The integrationist position does not receive a similarly structured explanation in any observed forum. It appears as a counter-discourse in the pro-government media.

In this interpretation, integrationism appears as an imperial threat, intertwined with the positive expression of a sovereigntist position. Its representatives are mostly politicians, whose speeches and social media entries are taken over by the

media analysed here. The representation of the EU as an empire – although it has several variants – is often a characteristic part of Eurosceptic critical discourse. The other type of the commentators are public intellectuals who fit critiques of the integrationist concept into the discursive topics of the disintegration of the EU and the declining West. The multi-speed Europe discourse appears as the opposite of federalism, as an intermediate pragmatic solution based on the intergovernmental cooperation of sovereign nation-states.

The Prime Minister called it “legal hooliganism” that the EU had initiated infringement proceedings against the Hungarian government over the so-called Child Protection Act, which banned NGOs dealing with sexual education from appearing in schools. The argument says that education and family law are national competences, the EU has no right to have a say in them, and the sexuality of a child is the sole responsibility of the parent. The case was reported without comment by the independent RTL Klub tv station and with critical commentary by the opposition ATV in a political talk show. In the latter, the critical context has drawn attention to the government’s desire to arm Brussels as an enemy image due the approaching elections. Furthermore, with this debate, the PM wanted to divert attention from the government’s failure to respond to EU-initiated corruption investigations according to this critical interpretation (ATV 2021 0716). The topic will be further discussed in the chapter dealing with disinformation.

Radio and TV statements, social media notes often become a source of news in the pro-government media outlets. Intergovernmental cooperation as the model to be followed was explained in a radio show by analysts of a pro-government think tank. The EU is very popular among Hungarians, they added, but the central institutions of the EU are not. That is why coordination between national institutions with strong legitimacy is needed, the argument said (MN 2021.07.14).

One of the arguments of the political analyst outlining the vision of a crumbling EU was that the politicians elected to lead the countries struggling with the crisis were experts with international economic experience seconded by the EU and the IMF. The Greek and Italian examples were mentioned here, as opposed to the Hungarian case, in which the Hungarian government took unorthodox steps to deal with the economic crisis and reduce the influence of international organizations (MN 2021.07.26).

The integrationist position appears in the independent press as well, but less frequently, with less weight and listing pros and cons. Such are the news describing the results of public opinion polls, which report that the vast majority of the Hungarian population considers EU membership to be a good thing and feels that national and supranational ties are compatible.

On the other hand, one of the basic arguments for the Huxit coincides with government rhetoric accusing EU decision-makers that the European Union since the Maastricht Treaty continued to be marked by stealthy federal aspirations, during which efforts were made to elevate various areas and policies to the supranational level.

In this perspective, Huxit is a marginal topos of the sovereigntist discourse. Although its original wording (“*there is life outside the EU*”) came from the PM’s statement before the EU-accession (<https://uj szo.com/velemen y/orban-van-clet-az-eu-n-kivul-is>), nowadays, if it is mentioned at all, it is discussed by public intellectuals referring mainly to pragmatic aspects.

– *[The Huxit] should be discussed because this union is far from the union, which we have entered, and they are currently preparing for... to punish us...*

– *[S]eeing the British experience, seeing the struggle of the average citizen, what Brexit has caused, we cannot with common sense say that we have to leave...*

– *The Hungarian government’s position is precisely that those countries that want to deepen integration should be able to do so, go ahead calmly, leave the door open for latecomers, such as Hungary. And if it is good, serves the national interest, and is supported by the majority of people, then obviously the Hungarian government will also join. Such is the European army...*

– *The acceptance of the European Union is high, but it has been very, very eroded, and in many, many ways, people are unsure of what kind of Europe they want. And I would raise another thing... I think that it is a lie that the Hungarian government wants to take action against capital and multinationals, and that it represents a uniquely Hungarian position. If we look at the past ten years, there has never been a Hungarian government that served capitalist interests so much. Let’s look at the case of the global minimum tax, Hungary and the Orbán regime insist tooth and nail on being a tax haven. (ATV 2021 08 16)*

It is instructive to observe how Huxit – which is rejected by both the conservative, pro-government, and critical left-wing journalists – fits into the frameworks of multi-speed Europe and globalization respectively and how it sinks into them. The claim about eroding EU-acceptance doesn’t match the facts

but fits both narratives well. The symbolic argument referring to a community of values appears only sporadically, referring to the necessity and difficulties of reconciling Christian-conservative and anti-globalist values.

It is raised in pro-government speeches that EU decision-makers (“Brussels bureaucrats”) discriminate on an ideological basis and apply a double standard. On the other hand, the EU representatives are talking about the lack of functioning of the rule of law standards, freedom of the media and transparency conditions that reduce the possibility of corruption against the Hungarian government.

At a conference bringing together NGOs supporting large families, the Deputy Secretary of State for Justice argued that the values of children determine the values of the future. This should not be based on “abstract and dangerous” ideologies, and demographic challenges should not be addressed through immigration. The solution is a strong Europe based on strong nations that respects traditional communities, the family and the nation. (MN 2021 11 04)

Another feature of the set of information is that it contained, to a large extent, statements by politicians, directly or indirectly. This phenomenon can be explained by several factors. One is that the polarization of the press is strongly intertwined with the polarization of party politics (Hallin-Mancini 2004). The second factor is that questions about the future of Europe, by their very nature, involve less pragmatic and more symbolic aspects. Add to all this the fact as mentioned above that the period examined here fell into the pre-election period, which may have increased the proportion of politicized statements.

The news on EU issues in the non-governmental RTL Klub television outlet was relatively rare. In the campaign period of the Hungarian elections, two MEPs spoke on the proposal on EU-level actions against oligarchic influence. The main argument was that they could buy an important part of the media and thus influence democratic elections. Government sources have responded to the proposal by “*hoping to start the tightening with George Soros, the world’s number one oligarch, and his network*” (RTL, 2022.02.10).

On the same EU-related issue, the opposition NSZ notes that the report of the EP Committee on Budgets mentions Viktor Orbán and Hungary by name. Hungary received the most recommendations from the EU Anti-Fraud Office for the period 2015-2019. There are systemic weaknesses in public procurement and the proportion of public tenders awarded to a single tenderer was exceptionally high. This problem has been exposed before, and the Prime Minister himself mentioned in a press conference, ahead of criticism, that the proportion of single-bid public procurement has been declining recently. Here we encounter the co-emergence of several research problems. One is the phenomenon of sinking and re-emerging topics. It illustrates that sinking and reappearance can occur in the

policy toolbox, not only in longer historical periods but within relatively short period of time as well.

The other phenomenon is the problem of the triple division of media framing, rational-legal discourse of bureaucracy and that of political will. The distinction essentially is due to the difference between the language of policies and politics. Media framing here refers to bureaucratic discourse, and it is less mobilizing than framing that directly targets perceived or real political will — familiar to populist rhetoric. It is so although pragmatic way of speaking may involve strong statements in their own way. They state, among other things, that the Hungarian Prime Minister has centralized and redistributed wealth to a clientele using EU agricultural subsidies.

The opposition press relied on NGOs to link corruption and oppression of personal freedom. The leader of a Hungarian non-governmental organization (TASZ), as a guest of the European People's Party faction meeting, stated that the permission of secret service surveillance in Hungary was illegal. The question arises, he said, if there are such differences in the application of the law by EU Member States, whether the EU can guarantee freedom, security, and justice for its citizens at all.

An alternative way of interpreting relations between the EU and the member states appears in a post of the PM, where he praised the decision of the Hungarian Constitutional Court to consider the right to human dignity not only for migrants but also for those living here. Furthermore, if the EU is unable to enforce the law, national authorities must do so. *"Europeans today have no right to their homeland, language, culture, family and God"* he wrote before Christmas (<https://miniszterelnok.hu/szamizdat-15>) and the blog – in positive or critical framing – was widely quoted by both the pro-government and opposition media.

Another problem is related to how the EU is thematised at the intersections of specific discourses. It is clear that the EU is seldom praised. Rather, it is the subject of criticism, but there are several ways and directions of criticism. There is a pragmatic, glaring criticism that the EU's otherwise desirable effects are not being felt enough, the procedures are inefficient or misled. The other kind of criticisms is the one, that questions the EU's *raison d'être* based on ideological values, stating that national and supranational sentiments are incompatible.

There are also differences in terms of discursive strategies and the tone of communication. On the one hand, there are those who assume that a solution that guarantees mutual benefits for the participants is possible. On the other hand, there are those who believe in the rhetoric of the struggle and assume that one must be careful and cunning, because others want to cheat them. Those who, because of their convictions, interests, or simply because of their habitus, think so, try to apply the rhetoric of struggle in bargaining as well, and this

finds mixed reception. Such behaviour is very unpopular with negotiators for understandable reasons. In part, it questions the sincerity of the partners' intent to negotiate, and it often seems simple blackmail.

Among voters, however, this kind of discursive performance can be framed as the case of a leader who stands up for the interests of the country to the extreme. And for the international viewer of the political scene, he may appear to be pursuing a value-based and effective policy despite his rough style. However, this style is not equally rough in all areas of international politics. It is remarkably militant where the language of compromises is spoken and ready to compromise where the language of brute force dominates.

Evaluating the Madrid meeting of right-wing parties, a think tank close to the Hungarian government discussed the formation of a Euro-realist conservative alliance. It has been argued that the Brussels elite is unfit to deal with crises, as demonstrated by the economic crisis of 2008, the migration crisis, and the pandemic. It is also losing its relevance in world politics and represents the interests of the elite, not the citizens. According to this view there is a need for a new conservative alliance in which Christianity, the family and national sovereignty are paramount. They therefore oppose any attempt that would call into question the primacy of national legislation. At the same time, they argue that a strong Europe is needed, which they believe is guaranteed by strong nation states. This approach reflects the views of the Hungarian Prime Minister, who, relying on a kind of duty ethic, envisioned the foundations of a strong Europe based on strong nation-states representing a wide range of perspectives.

This long-held view of the Hungarian governing elite leaves it open what can guarantee a strong Europe if its decision-making is limited by the bargain of strong national elites. What is emphasized, however, is the need to restore a culture of mutual *respect* between the EU and the nation states. Fight and respect are recurring keywords in the rhetoric of the Hungarian PM.

At the same time, the “*there is life outside the EU*” anti-EU rhetoric of previous years was replaced by a sovereigntist internal criticism around the last quarter of 2021. This could be related to the fact that the vast majority of Hungarian voters are attached to the EU. It should be added that – as revealed above – this proportion has increased despite the EU-critical rhetoric of the governing elites. The replacement of the floating exit option with a sovereigntist critical discourse was summed up by the PM's following statement:

The functioning of the European Union has taken the wrong direction in recent years. We Hungarians see it as a creaking and creaky union structure. But we will stand there until the last moment and hold the last beam. Our Western European friends must also understand that

the Central European countries did not come to the union with open hands, but rather represent with all their might the policy for which the electorate authorized their administrations. Whether Brussels likes it, or not. National independence, protection of our identity, support for families and protection of children are basic principles that we will not compromise for anyone's sake. The analysis also discussed in the Polish parliament clearly shows that we do not receive support from the West, but that Western European countries look to us and take the profits out of our countries. And in the meantime, they want to educate us in European values. Stop the march!... We consider pragmatic, mutually beneficial economic cooperation that respects each other's sovereignty to be desirable. Instead, today neo-Marxist ideology has captured the institutions of Brussels, and crises follow one another. In the meantime, the conservative forces of the old member states withered away. Our task is to restore the balance: return to the original European ideal, focus on well-functioning and rational areas of cooperation, such as economic and military cooperation. We should cut back the Brussels bureaucracy, returning authority to the member states from institutions that politicize and create senseless tensions. (<https://miniszterelnok.hu/orban-viktor-interjuja-az-info-cz-csehorszagi-hirportalnak/> 2021 11 04).

The pro-government media voiced the fact that the Hungarian government's (from that perspective: the country's) foreign image is distorted. The foreign press claims that the Hungarian political system is a dictatorship, which is a false image – argued the pro-government media. This is partly because the foreign press is influenced by George Soros' network and NGOs professing liberal principles according to this view. Partly because the majority of foreign journalists do not speak Hungarian, they receive information only from secondary sources, and these sources are narrow and distorted. In the interpretation of pro-government media international NGOs like Freedom House do not do independent analyst work, but rather propaganda, applying a double standard and discriminating against those on the same ideological platform as them. NGOs influence journalists by bringing them to the right interviewees.

Social media is directly related to traditional journalism in many respects. The pro-government press regularly and immediately broadcasts Facebook posts of Justice Minister Judit Varga, who has a fan base around ten thousand. On February 10, 2022, she noted that the number of EU infringement proceedings against Hungary was 60, which is low by international standards, and the figures for Ireland and Luxembourg, among others, exceed this. The procedure for non-

transposition of directives is particularly low, with only German and Danish data being more favourable. It is therefore unfair that the left-liberal opposition is portraying Hungary in the wrong colours.

The more than a thousand comments, which reflect the real-time reactions of the internet public, have some distinctive features. Most of the comments represent condensed, emotionally saturated and polarized opinions. A significant portion of the entries are expressions of sympathy and antipathy. A smaller part of them contains opinions, only a fraction of the opinions refers to arguments. *“It is a shame that the European representatives of our own country are spreading lies about their homeland”* – argued a pro-government comment. The answer suggested a distinction: *“Here’s the basic misconception! The left-liberal side is not attacking our country, but criticizing the government.”* Or in a harsh version: *“The union has no problem with our country, but with its thieving leaders”* (<https://www.facebook.com/VargaJuditMinisterofJustice>).

CONCLUDING REMARKS

Using media articles covering issues of national identity and the European Union, and a series of deliberative events about the future of Europe, the current paper aims to analyze media discourses about national identity, different understandings of Europe, and different conceptions about the European Union and its institutional construct.

As opposing media discourses on national identity and varying interpretations of the European Union were identified depending on the media outlet, our results do indeed reflect the polarized nature of the Hungarian media landscape in general. There were two main discourses that were identified: one, much less prominent, that was present in the independent media about superior European values and a rather integrationist stance; the other, the government’s discourse about national sovereignty with elements of a cultural/primordial identity based on Christianity, the importance of the nation and family, and placing member-states at the heart of the European construct with varying degrees of rejection of the EU.

Despite negative governmental campaigns targeting the EU since 2010 building on very symbolic messages, positive public perceptions of the EU still managed to increase. Results of our analysis suggest that despite their critical stance, outright rejection of Hungary’s EU-membership appears rarely in the national sovereigntist media discourse and critics are mainly formulated in a European frame against the current European institutions and their performance, based on

“real” European values, and without rejecting the idea of European integration. These ideas are rather in line with the concept of “soft Euroscepticism” (Taggart and Szcerbiak, 2002) or represent a “diffuse support” (Kopecky and Mudde, 2002) instead of a “hard” form of Euroscepticism.

Furthermore, our results shed light on a specific characteristic of current media that also shapes the nature of the content that appear in the media. Comparative analyses show that audio-visual media consumption (vs. newspaper reading) increases receptivity to personalized (vs. program-based) politics. The proliferation of social media may have similar effect, and it is associated with the hybridization of media consumption (Mancini 2015). We are witnessing a related phenomenon in the analysed Hungarian media. The content of social media infiltrates the traditional media, and the adoption is selective and asymmetric. Public media also selectively and asymmetrically take over articles from online journalism. Politicians’ websites and Facebook posts contribute to the personalization of political life. The politician’s personal qualities, appearance, and gestures amplify affective reactions, leaving less room for the content of the programs and rational reasoning. Being on social media usually causes simplistic and divisive reactions. All this contributes to polarization and the spread of populist politics. Politicians’ social media posts are asymmetrically transferred to newspaper websites. They do not include the comments of fans and critics but transfer the communication style of the personalized political milieu for which they were created. In principle, social media is supposed to provide a real-time, balanced relationship between the sender and receiver of the message. However, according to the experiences it does not meet this possibility in its current form. Neither the genre nor the style of online political communication contributes to the spread of rational political communication, but instead reinforces the phenomena of personalization, polarization and populism.

The distinction between the EU and the “Brussels bureaucratic elites” overlaps with a core issue of the future of Europe discussion: the perception of integration. Those who believe that the integration has already gone too far may think within the framework of the EU or reject the EU. The analysed corpus largely represents criticism within the framework of the EU. However, the set of arguments are mixed with the conceptual apparatus of views that completely reject the EU, like the arguments about the declining, powerless West.

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THE CONSOLIDATION OF POLARIZATION. HUNGARIAN DISCOURSES ON MIGRATION

ATTILA MELEGH¹

ABSTRACT: *What discursive structures, interactions, and related material conditions have helped in the consolidation of polarization and the rise of an extreme nationalist counter-hegemony related to migration discourses? Utilizing Karl Polanyi's conceptual framework, we advance a strong hypothesis that general marketization and market utopias have led to opposition among pro-market utilitarian, pro-EU, and nationalist anti-migrant and anti-liberal EU discourses. It seems that, in this, the change in migration processes themselves could be an important factor as they have embodied many of the tensions and contradictions of the neoliberal era.*

However, we need to focus on how to locate the exact historically evolving mechanisms linking marketization with polarization and the rise of the counter-hegemony of anti-migrant nationalism. In this complex realm, we also need to focus on the discursive mechanisms whose own autonomous and immanent role played out in interaction with material processes and conditions. In this paper, we focus on Hungary, which has become an exemplar in terms of the establishment of counter-hegemonic anti-migrant nationalist discourses as opposed to the pro-European managed migration discourses of the 2010s.

The analysis is based on 91 systematically selected articles from the overall pool in the period between July 2021 and March 2022. At the end of the paper, we briefly discuss, based on a few preliminary results, how public opinion approves of, follows, or has an alternative view concerning the discursive functioning of the media.

KEYWORDS: *migration, rules of silence, counter-hegemony, liberal managed Europe, civilizational slope*

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INTRODUCTION

Hungary has become a key country in the intensifying debate over migration. This is clear not only in everyday politics, where the Hungarian government loudly and openly takes one side in international and local debates but also in the fact that since 2002, according to the European Social Survey, the Hungarian public, together with many East European countries, has been extremely negative with regard to taking immigrants from non-European countries (Melegh 2023, 262; Messing-Ságvári 2017, 2019). Concerning media discourses, we have repeated evidence that Hungarian media discourses have overwhelmingly framed the immigration of asylum seekers as a danger in terms of cultural and security concerns (Bernáth-Messing, 2016; Sík 2016). We also have evidence that the Hungarian media is more polarized and compares its views via “positioning” *vis-à-vis* other nations (Maneri, 2023; Melegh et al. 2019).

When we try to identify how discourses evolve, we need to have a complex strategy, including integrating material structures and processes into our analysis (Fairclough 2001). Very often, authors argue that such developments are simply the results of the instrumentalization and normalization of certain discourses to achieve certain goals, mainly associated with populist nationalism transgressing previously upheld norms (Wodak 2015). Some other authors speak about moral panic buttons, thus about the instrumental use of such types of reactions (Sík 2016; Lázár-Sík 2019). Several scholars also claim this is part of the authoritarian turn, managed from above based on political rationality.

These lines of argumentation, of course, capture certain elements, but here, we not only miss the role of non-right-wing discourses (i.e., those generally termed “liberal discourses”) and the interactions with them but an analysis of the complex process of historical development is lacking, without which we cannot see how various hegemonic and counter-hegemonic discursive blocks emerge and develop. This is a complex task, and we can solve only some elements of it here, although we will make reference to some factors that are not elaborated here. Thus, when we analyze Hungarian discourses, we need to look at various historically evolving structures and discursive frames about migration, the idea of Europe, and Europeanization. We also need to link cognitive patterns to overall economic and social change. Thus, this paper has three theoretical perspectives from which we analyze developments.

First is the postcolonial theory of the cultural hegemony of Europe as applied to Eastern Europe, as developed by various authors (for an overview, see Kołodziejczyk and Huigen 2023). The key element of this perspective is the analysis of a longer-term hierarchical imagination according to which, from the 19th century onward, different colonized or previously colonized parts and

people of the world have been portrayed as necessarily subjugated to European rule and guidance due to their cognitive and social inferiority (Said 1978; Spivak and Mignonolo 2001). This hierarchical imagination within Europe could also be detected from the 19th century onward, although in this case, Eastern Europe and the Balkans have been seen as being ordered as an in-between area between Europe and non-Europe (Wolf 1994; Todorova 1997). This idea can be termed the “civilizational slope,” and it appears directly in various Eurocentric population discourses (Melegh 2006). In this theorizing, Böröcz focused on the monopolization of “goodness” on behalf of Western Europe and specifically the EU, including the humanitarianism of receiving immigrants, which needs to be followed by that of “inferior” East Europeans (Böröcz 2000, 2005).

This constructed cultural dominance leads to specific reactions by East European actors and speakers, who may accept but can also challenge this dominance. These patterns have also descended into the popular imagination, and imagining development hierarchically may be identified from public opinion surveys in Hungary, Romania, and Bulgaria just before the so-called refugee crisis (Kiss 2017; Melegh et al. 2016). This phenomenon may also be demonstrated, especially with regard to migration, and the material below gives ample evidence of anti-dominance protests against Brussels and Europe. Within the context of joining and maneuvering within the EU, East European nationalisms have led actors to resist being seen as second-class European nations to be governed by other parts of the world. The questioning of European dominance has become a key tenet of rising nationalism in the form of authoritarian tendencies in some East European countries (Krstev, 2022; Melegh, 2006, 2023). This hierarchical rule is associated with various other rules (for instance, that of pro-Europeanness), structures a complex set of sayable and not-sayable topics, and fosters a set of maneuvering techniques on behalf of the interacting elites.

It has also been demonstrated that migration has been a divisive issue in population discourses as it has been able to create two competing, in some sense, Eurocentric blocks with clear lines stretching back into history (Melegh 2023). One is a pro-market and pro-migration block promoted by major institutions of global capitalism like the World Bank in the name of market rationality, and the other is the so-called anti-migrant nationalist block, which disputes the scale and the selection possibilities associated with the migration process that promote both the dominance and the interests of Europe and the West (Melegh 2023).

The second perspective is to find linkages that explain why such discursive mechanisms, especially the ones that challenge it, prevail or become dominant. In this respect, we utilize the insights of Karl Polanyi, who argued that periods of

market utopias are followed by certain double movements, including nationalism (Polanyi 2001, 1945/2018). The more exact historical material background of this rise of nationalism and the decline of pro-European liberalism has been developed in several publications (Kalb 2011; Hann 2019; Fábry 2019; Mihályi-Szelényi 2019; Messing-Ságvári 2017, 2019, Andor 2017; Böröcz-Sarkar 2017). Also related to migration, and as an explanation, authors have repeatedly pointed at unequal economic and social exchanges between different parts of Europe, the revolt of the nation-state against the opening up of markets and the marketization of societies, a lack of trust in state authority and political institutions, income and welfare gaps. In addition, concerning migration, extremely negative public opinion has been measured on a regional level, especially in Hungary, the Czech Republic, and Estonia, where demographic decline and relatively strong fears of competition from immigrants have all contributed to a rising panic and blaming of Western Europe for “increasing and forcing” immigration onto fragile East European nations (Melegh 2023).

The third perspective is polarization and the development of discourses. Here, we operate with two insights. The first is closely related to the emergence of an abstract concept of migration, which is related to an abstract evaluation of the utility and the overall value of migrants, mainly related to the perceived market-related “demand and supply” problem with the labor force (Melegh 2023). This marketization (reification) of migration is important as its abstraction as a socially constructed concept allows it to be easily misused in polarized debates (through selecting and vilifying elements to represent the whole) and can lead to the radicalization of those forces that would make use, either negatively or positively, of these wider processes and related fears for political purposes (Wodak 2015). This process has been especially successful in transgressing norms and values institutionalized in asylum and migratory regulations.

The second insight is related to the polarization of political systems and media. In this respect, Hallin and Mancini introduced very important arguments in their classic book on comparing media systems (Hallin and Mancini 2004). In this, they claim that in systems of polarized pluralism, there is a lot of political parallelism, and the media becomes highly politicized and a key instrument of the political struggle itself. Hungary clearly fits this pattern, and this development has become very important in the steps toward an authoritarian turn (Polyák-Urbán 2024).

Together with this complex set of analytical angles and perspectives, this paper intends to clarify what discursive structures, interactions, and related material conditions have helped consolidate the polarization of discursive blocks and explain the rise of an extreme nationalist counter-hegemony as related to the discursive linkages between Europe, Europeanization, and migration. The

paper argues that the consolidation of polarization is the result of materially conditioned specific linkages between the symbolic use of imagined hierarchies and the manipulative use of the term “migration,” which combination was linked to various anxieties and fears within the population. This we will test via analyzing the co-occurrence of discursive forms in the analyzed media outlets and through checking whether significant associations can be found in the answers to certain survey questions.

DATA AND METHODOLOGY

The media outlets covered public and private, online and print, pro-government, and opposition media. First, we selected two television channels, one public and one private (M1 and RTL), for their evening news programs. Then, two dailies, *Magyar Nemzet* (MN) and *Népszava* (NSZ), were added, the first pro-government and the second government-critical. Both online and print versions of these dailies were taken into account. In addition, two popular online outlets (HVG and ORIGO) were also incorporated, the first government-critical and the second pro-government. Finally, after realizing that these media outlets do not adequately represent the total spectrum of the political discussion – even if we take into account the problems of the vagaries of live speech – these were supplemented by HÍR TV and ATV, in which political discussions strongly feature. The former is pro-government, and the second used to represent the liberal-critical stance, although recently, this characterization has been questioned by media analysts due to a change in ownership and, in parallel, in tone.

On a weekly basis, overall, between 50 and 100 articles could be identified in the specific pro-government and anti-government media outlets with relevant keywords like “migration,” “migrants,” “asylum seeker,” “immigrant,” “emigrant,” and “migrant quota.” The Ukrainian crisis blew these figures up (sometimes above the level of 400 articles), and the previously rarely used term “refugee” became common. This was supplemented with the keyword “Ukraine” in order to help follow war-related events. Each week, 3-4 articles were chosen to systematically cover key themes, key media outlets, and possible discursive formations based on previous and newly found patterns (for these previously identified patterns, see Bernáth-Messing, 2016; Melegh et al. 2019; Melegh, 2006; Melegh et al. 2016). Ninety-one articles were analyzed and coded altogether.

The Hungarian population survey was conducted within the framework of the Mediatized EU project. The aim of the nationally representative survey of 1,022

respondents was to describe the main features of the Hungarian adult population's views and attitudes towards European integration, elites, and the media. Research fieldwork was conducted from 21.07.2023 to 02.08.2023 using the CAPI method. The sample was formed using a three-step probability sampling method. The work was conducted within the omnibus survey of TÁRKI, an experienced polling company. Quality control was applied in the form of a 10% callback. The raw data were weighted by gender, age, and type of municipality.

The key discussions were dominated by the Hungarian election, the changes in Afghanistan, the Belarus border crisis, and, from February onward, the Russo-Ukrainian war. This latter event proved to be important in the history of the discursive developments in Hungary, as explained below.

We regard our approach as valid and fruitful if we are able to show the following results: Based on closely related discursive formations, we can identify discursive blocks in terms of co-occurrence (cross-relations) of discursive themes and formations within articles. This we will treat as evidence of polarization; also, especially if the formations are formed via opposing and, importantly, degrading discursive formations in the other blocks. In this analysis, we will check if material conditions are mentioned or reflected upon in the discourses and how they are incorporated. Omission is also an important result in this respect.

In the discursive analysis, we will specifically check if the above-described East/West discourses (postcolonial perspectives) link (i.e., appear and organize) both blocks. Then, we will see how this historically inherited hierarchical Eurocentric imagination is related to the identified blocks; otherwise, we need to refute this perspective. We can expect discursive strategies of refuting hierarchies (we are not “second class”) or perceptions that we need to “civilize ourselves” according to “European” standards.

We will also need to check if this hierarchical maneuvering can be demonstrated in the population surveys via a question on developmental hierarchies asking about the subjective ranking of 12 different countries, including Hungary, in terms of developmental level (“Using a scale of development from one to seven where would you put ... individual countries?”). On the basis of answers to this question, an average value can be computed for the various countries, and we can check whether the approval of items related to certain blocks is associated with an “overrating” or “underrating” of the development of Hungary. In a nationalist block, overrating is relevant, while in the case of pro-European liberal blocks, underrating is possible (see Meleg 2006). We will use the Kendall tau-b association and test its significance. If there is no significant association, we will refute that East/West hierarchies appear in public opinion or that they organize blocks of opinion.

Concerning the existence of blocks, we will explore how migration-related questions and answers to them are related to the following certain items, including the above-mentioned hierarchy question.

Within this survey, agreement with the following questions was asked concerning migration:

- The EU is helping to manage immigration from non-EU countries
- Migration solves the EU's labor market problems
- It would only make things worse if many foreigners were allowed to enter the country

Responses to these questions were then checked to see whether items related to blocks were significantly associated with answers related to migration and whether internal cohesion was observable. The blocks, as explained below, were first constructed on a discursive level in the media and then checked in the public opinion surveys. In our analysis, after having discursively identified the liberal-*managed Europe block*, this was translated to the following public opinion items:

- Using a scale of development (1-7 where would you put Hungary ('downrating' compared to average score)
- The EU has an important role in protecting human rights and democracy
- EU-positive: Better management of migration
- Some Member States' deviation from the European course endangers the EU
- The Hungarian government has not used EU funds in a sufficiently transparent way
- The EU has a positive role in Hungary's economic development
- The EU's central institutions must be strengthened
- The EU increases Hungarian security in the context of the ongoing war in Ukraine (this statement is not linked to hierarchies; it is cross-cutting)

In the media, the discursively constructed *nationalist block* (see below) was operationalized for public opinion via the following items.

- Using a scale of development (1-7 where would you put Hungary ('uprated' compared to the average score)
- The EU's so-called LGBTQ propaganda is harmful to children
- The EU threatens Hungary's national identity and related traditional values
- The EU intrudes into Hungary's internal affairs and endangers its sovereignty
- The West is chaotic, ineffective, and in decline.
- Hungary is the depository of true European values, Christianity, and the family

- The countries of Central Europe share common values and traditions that the EU should respect (only the last migration item)
How important do you think it is for a true European to be Christian

KEY DISCURSIVE FORMATIONS: ‘NATIONALIST’ AND ‘LIBERAL-MANAGED EUROPE’ DISCURSIVE BLOCKS AND EAST/WEST DISCOURSES AS ORGANIZING DISCOURSES

After analyzing each article and observing co-occurrence, the lists below identify the key discursive formations and their linkages. We have also paid special attention to identity and pragmatic elements and, very importantly, to linkages across discursive blocks. By discursive formations, we mean basic interrelated discursive elements, patterns, and perspectives, as understood by Foucault.

“Whenever one can describe between several statements such a system of dispersion, whenever, between objects, types of statements, concepts, or thematic choices, one can define a regularity (an order, correlation, positions, and functionings, transformations) we will say, for the sake of convenience, that we are dealing with a discursive formation.” (Michel Foucault 1972, 38).

The complex linkages of discursive formations can be understood as discursive blocks or larger-scale discourses. The linkages are identified via the co-occurrence of discursive formations in the same article. We have described these elements in the list below.

As can be seen, there are very strong interlinkages and major discursive blocks can be constructed, also with some cross-linkages:

The nationalist block contains mainly those formations that legitimize national state-level control and cultural-historical opposition to market-oriented and EU-managed migration. This block is Eurocentric concerning Europe and its historical achievements, but it claims that liberal and non-discriminatory liberal values are either mistaken and/or lead to decline and refers to an earlier version of colonial and nation and religion-based Europe. This Eurocentrism also involves distancing and moral panic related to immigrants, most importantly non-European (in particular, Muslim) asylum-seekers. Such supported formations include:

- Biopolitical control and direct intervention into population processes to defend the “local” and the “normal.”
- Defense of national identity and sovereignty (Westphalian logic) against “globalist.” elites imposing their will on nation-states regarding migration-related issues.
- The decline and chaos of the West and the EU, and this civilizational decline hindering the emergence of real answers to migration based on strength and “fundamental” values.
- “Deep” Europe or Central Europe as the last bastion of Europe as opposed to the declining West.
- Security mechanisms are to be strengthened against immanent terrorist and criminal dangers arising from migration.
- Migration pressure (Malthusian type) from non-European countries due to grave economic and ecological problems and related overpopulation.
- Defence of endangered white Christianity (the latter a historically important force) from liberal identity politics.

The liberal and ,anaged Europe block mainly contains those formations that involve Eurocentric perceptions of a common market based on ideas of a non-nationalist, federal Europe. In these formations, the core countries represent development/civilization and promote the joint European management of migration. This type of management has to satisfy liberal humanitarian utopias (liberal values guide political action and change) and human rights and, at the same time, involves certain utilitarian gains from marketization (Mannheim 1936; Melegh 2006). Namely,

- The EU represents the normal management and control of migration associated with various versions of liberal humanitarian discourses, like the West represents civilized manners.
- Market and labor needs are to be satisfied through migration.
- Fundamental values of liberty, human rights, solidarity, and civilizational values are to be protected even if it is difficult to maintain them in relation to migration.
- Strong Europe. Europe stands up to defend its borders, interests, and values, even in the case of migration.
- The nationalist threat is a critical formation that focuses on the rise of radical nationalism; this formation is dangerous and appears most significantly in Eastern Europe.
- Humanism is a discursive formation that is organized around the need to defend the vulnerable.

- The inequality and unequal exchange (developmentalist) formation is built on the idea that migrants, most notably East European emigrants, are exploited in terms of wages and working conditions.

Linking and organizing formations involve the following formations

- Critical reflection on migration and European discourses, focusing on how to distance the speaker from various “offered” discourses and narratives seen as misleading or “abnormal”
- East/West discursive formations are general organizing structures for evaluating the social development of countries and regions together with migrants in a hierarchical manner within Europe and globally. They are often linked to racialized hierarchies of migrants that determine inclusion and exclusion. They may also be a guide to claiming more dignity for those (nations, migrants) positioned at lower levels.

Beyond the linking and organizing discursive formations (like critical reflection and East/West discursive formations), there are some further important connections between the above discursive blocks, meaning that different blocks can use similar discursive formations in somewhat modified forms. So, the polarization is not complete. Very importantly, the following discursive formations may show up in different blocks in parallel (i.e., both can appear in the same article): the decline and chaos of the West (in the managed Europe block, decline linked to liberal values), securitization, migration pressure, strong Europe, humanism (in the Nationalist block, only associated with Christians, etc.), fundamental values (both liberal and so-called illiberal values), inequality and unequal change. Co-occurrences and possible overlaps show that a new European ideal may be in the making (where the blocks can meet), which common terrain involves a stronger and more combative Europe in relation to the outside world, which at the same time maintains a certain humanism not in general, but toward certain selected groups (whites, Europeans and Christian) and which fights against intra-European inequality.

The opposition among these blocks of formations concerns mainly the modes of intervention in migration processes, the actors of control, and, very importantly, identity-related questions, while the critique of marketization is either related to cultural consequences only or focuses on the “second class,” exploited position of Hungary and Eastern Europe. This identity focus and the lack of systematic contextualization of the migration process can explain the polarization.

In this discursive process, **East/West and immanent racialized hierarchies** structure ideas about the struggle and inclusion and exclusion of social,

political, and migrant groups within and among the discursive blocks. The first targets the liberal and “diluted” West and its East European clients colonizing or ruling other parts, while the latter may see East Europeans and those within the Hungarian pro-government forces as nationalists – i.e., as obstacles to handling challenges on a “European” and collective level and dysfunctional in relation to achieving “civilizational” upgrading.

The debate also refers to the economic necessity and realities of the free market and the related opening-up, as well as the need to restrict and regulate related processes on national or regional levels. In this process, the added values and contributions of the labor of different migrant and non-migrant groups (e.g., immigrants replacing emigrants or compensating for population loss) are seen as comparable from a biopolitical and labor market point of view, thus establishing their formal equality and involving an abstract concept of migrants that includes various, often widely different forms. It is thus a process that can trigger complex counterdiscourses.

SOCIAL AND DISCURSIVE CONDITIONS AND KEY DISCURSIVE MECHANISMS: MARKETIZATION AND THE ABSTRACT CONCEPT OF MIGRATION

In critical discourse analysis, it is very important to clarify the material and some discursive conditions of the various semiotic orders during the period of analysis. There are general and specific conditions, both of which evolve historically (Fairclough 2001; Foucault 1972).

Different forms of migration can be understood as an incredibly rich phenomenon. Geographic mobility involves a large number of complex relations between and among wanderers and sending groups, families, hosts, agents, authorities, and social organizations. This could lead to incredibly rich and diverse forms of representation, while these discursive images and patterns can also be very simplistic and abstract. This depends on how migrants are integrated into power structures based on material conditions and relations.

As a general condition underlying the discursive processes associated with recent decades of globalization, marketization and the opening-up to global markets have increased migration due to the further fragmentation of economic and labor processes, the increased “flexibilization” of labor, and the domination of cross-border value chains (Antunes 2021; Melegh 2023). Moreover, this has increased demand for transnational migrant labor, which is now globally reified and integrated into massive fictitious exchanges. Thus, a migration turn

has been completed, creating a global migratory market around the world in which Europe has been a key player since the 1980s. Naturally, these combined transformations have radically challenged cultural patterns, discursive patterns, and communal mechanisms, thus affecting the identities and interactions of various groups as well as nations. These transformations have been particularly important in certain regions, including the European Union and Eastern Europe, via creating a single unified, unhindered market. The marketization in Eastern Europe has been even more shocking, where socialist mixed economies (regardless of the manifold differences among them) collapsed and where the globalization cycle associated with capitalism was only one of the many difficulties societies had to face. In addition, the decline in fertility, the stagnation in economic redistribution, and thus emerging social security and public service tensions paved the way for conflicts centered around the issue of migration and welfare competition in the context of wider demographic anxieties. Therefore, the emergence of pro and anti-migration blocs utilizing East/West discourses was not a surprise. In fact, Due to the combination of discursive and socio-material processes, the rise of such historical-political blocs has been fueled by actual historical driving forces within the system and thus should be seen as an outstanding historical event in conjunction with globalization.

MARKETIZATION: PRO-MARKET AND THE LIBERAL MANAGED EUROPE BLOCK VERSUS THE NATIONALIST, PRO-SELECTION OR NO MIGRATION BLOCK

The liberal-managed Europe block is represented well by the economic weekly HVG, which, in its discourses, unites all the categories of migrants (refugees, those who purchase settlement bonds, guest workers, etc.). It also makes comparisons among the Visegrád countries, Hungary, and the EU, argues how minor immigration is compared to emigration, and shows the increasing demand for immigrants. Furthermore, it contextualizes their contribution within an East/West framework. As we can see below, the East/West divide also appears in relation to the social positions of the immigrants.

With regard to the labor market, the role of foreign employees was the most significant in 2018 (in Hungary), when they represented 2% of the total number of employees. According to the Economic Research Institute, Ukrainian, Serbian, and Romanian guest workers typically

did manual labor, while those coming from Western Europe filled top manager positions and those requiring special professional knowledge. ERI claims that Hungary is not a popular destination among guest workers. The labor force coming from the East often continues toward the West, toward Austria and Germany, due to higher wages there. The number of guest workers is determined by the expansion of Western firms, as the former are mainly employed by multinational and German companies. In some time, we can expect a rise in the number of Asian employees due to the construction of South Korean and Japanese battery and chemical factories. (HVG, 2021.07.29)

https://hvg.hu/itthon/20210729_GKI_Ot_ev_alatt_20_ezer_kinai_es_18_ezer_nemet_kapott_magyar_allampolgarsagot

This perspective of market-based capital-labor exchanges can be termed an underlying discursive framework of market normalcy, which is directly linked to the above marketization condition and the discursive units referring to “normal” cross-EU market management and East/West hierarchies. The nationalist, pro-selection, or no migration counter-discourse is based on the rejection of marketization, but not on a systemic basis (it visualizes no alternative models and system critique), but due to its perceived or claimed cultural and social consequences (cultural identity, crime rates, great replacement, etc.) In this formation, racialized and hierarchical differences are used to delegitimize the normalcy of the (Western) European management of migration. This is all done using a migration category *in abstracto*, and the statements legitimize the need for direct national and state control with full and unhindered sovereignty not governed by any universal legal norms. Only the will of the “Magyar people” matters in this respect, which makes the discourse a populist one (Joppke 2021; Berezin 2009; Kalb 2011; Sík, 2016; Lázár-Sík 2019)

This is a counter-discourse, and its mechanisms are clearly illustrated by the published Facebook post of Zoltán Kovács (state secretary responsible for governmental communication) in which he argues that there is no need for migrants; migration as such should be stopped and national control enhanced. In this discourse, border fences should be financed by the EU as opposed to establishing “legal migration routes leading toward Europe.”

Migration has to be stopped, and the Brussels-led management of migration has to be finished – writes Zoltán Kovács, state secretary, on his social media page. The state secretary responsible for international communication and relations wrote on Facebook that on October 12,

twelve EU member states, including the ministers of interior affairs within the Visegrad group, wrote a letter to Margaritis Schinas, vice president of the European Commission and Ylva Johansson, commissioner of interior affairs. He added that the ministers of interior affairs drew the attention of the two commissioners that physical obstacles (like the Hungarian border fence) are efficient tools of border defense that serve the interest of the whole European Union and not only the countries with outer borders. He underlined that following this situation, they demanded from the European Commission that this “legitimate measure” shall be financed from the budget of the Union. In contrast, at the 6th European Migration Forum focusing on the integration of migrants, Ylva Johansson argued that we can better “manage” migration and that our society and economy need migrants. According to the international spokesperson, in the meantime, the LIBE Committee asked the European Commission to establish legal migration routes toward Europe. He [Kovács] continued that migration shall be stopped, and the Brussels-led management of migration shall be ended! (2021 11 28)

<https://www.origo.hu/itthon/20211028-kovacs-zoltan-a-migracio-menedzselesenek-veget-kell-vetni.html>

Thus, within this frame (concerning abstract market-based migration category), we see polarization in the context of “migration” as being either beneficial or detrimental overall to local societies, which leads to the rather irrational, hasty deploring of “opposing” arguments in the Hungarian media. At the same time, we see no overall critique of the market mechanisms themselves, so in this sense, the arguments are rather similar, which can increase the need to differentiate.

POLARIZATION RULES AND DISCURSIVE BLOCKS

If we wish to identify why polarization occurs or even why it is necessary, then we have to look deeper into some discursive mechanisms. International migration has been reformulated as an abstract market category, and this shift has increased the tension and antagonistic blocs associated with the debate in the given socio-material and historical context. Such polarization may be an important consequence of constructing general and abstract categories, which,

precisely because it separates migratory processes from social relations, could support “slippery,” overgeneralized debates. These discursive developments avoid addressing the social and motivational contextualization of migration and avoid framing this as a historical and social process, and thus, perceive it as a broader category to be judged as useful or harmful. This calculus leads to polarization,

This we could see above, but general undifferentiated discursive support for immigration (as a market category) can also be found in other cases. Publishing the view of Bloomberg, the Hungarian opposition newspaper *Népszava* takes a pro-market and pro-EU management stand when commenting on the Hungarian Demographic Summit, which frames migration as a threat (this is a regular, larger-scale neoconservative political and intellectual pro-family rally in Budapest) with the aim of showing that anti-migrant rhetoric is just nationalist fear-mongering:

It confronts a larger number of studies demonstrating that immigration helps the economy and leads to wage increases. According to the IMF, if the number of employees increases by 1 percent within five years, it leads to a 1 percent increase in GDP. (2021 09 24)

https://nepszava.hu/3133156_szabad-szemmel-a-nagy-lakossagcsere-elmelet-korul-forog-orban-demografiai-tanacskozasa

In the nationalist counter-discourse, mythical, overgeneralized perspectives can be very clearly seen in relation to the criminalization of migrants. Here, we present a case of a report by the pro-government public media talking about the proportion of foreigners living in European countries. Citing the total number of foreigners, the TV report argues that non-European migrants may be disciplined according to this framework as it leads to demographic change and an increase in insecurity. This maneuver is completed by first “going general” and then switching to addressing very specific cases.

In Austria, the proportion of foreigners reached an all-time high level in 2015, that is to say, after the peak of the migration crisis. According to official data, in this country of 8.9 million people, there were living 1.8 million foreigners. This adds up to one-fifth of the population. Half of the foreigners have an immigration background, that is to say, came from outside the European Union, and thus every tenth has an immigration background. And this does not include those born in Austria with an immigration background. According to studies, as

the number of migrants increases, criminality also goes up. There was an increase in knife attacks and atrocities against women. In Italy, the number of schools with a majority of students of migrant background as opposed to Italians is close to 1,000. Despite critiques about increasing migration pressure and increasing criminality, the EU does nothing and campaigns for diversity. However, according to experts, a more efficient policy against migrants should target compliance with European norms, which would help their integration. (2021.11.18)

<https://mediamonitor-observer.hu/company-common-web/#/view-article/rtvArticle/6196226ff40f1941838df24e/5c57fa781e5ff-d006727ae3b/618bbabf08698c2e14f427da>

This position is hardly conclusive, not only because it involves overgeneralization and the clear mixing of analytical levels but also because the universalist utilitarian perspectives and vicious claims of generalized criminality cannot be harmonized. Such exchanges (without looking at the deeper structural links) lead to polarization because each position necessarily remains isolated. There is no talk about why and how various contextualized forms of migration are linked to social change and social structures within Europe. In this format, the positions cannot be linked to each other rationally, and only mythical solutions can come out, like impersonal and calculated market utility versus evil Soros-type conspiracies that dominate the EU terrain. We may assume that this polarization may even be a conscious discursive strategy on behalf of actors trying to mobilize various segments of the population.

RULES OF SILENCE: WHICH MIGRANTS CAN BE HEARD AND SEEN IN POLARIZED DISCUSSIONS?

In the context of overall marketization and its cultural-nationalist critique, Hungarian media discourses clearly follow social (East/West) hierarchies in selectively representing the voice of refugees or migrants (Melegh 2006; Böröcz-Sarkar 2017). This silence is most conspicuous with regard to asylum seekers appearing at the Hungarian borders. In the period concerned, no article contained an interview with asylum seekers at the Southern border (i.e., non-European migrants). Refugees from Ukraine were treated differently. There was even an occasion when the press reported a conversation between the

prime minister and a family at the Hungarian border (<https://magyarnemzet.hu/belfold/2022/03/orban-viktor-ukrajnai-menekulteket-latogatott-meg-video>).

This is in massive contrast with the representation of asylum seekers from the South, who mainly appear as inhumane, depersonalized images on night cameras and who are mainly spoken about as targets to be caught. If they speak, especially on the government-serving public and private media (M1, HírTv), then they are always outside Hungary, and they briefly speak only about their plans to cross Hungary and to go on toward Germany or Sweden and in the context of locals talking about being robbed by them (<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=nnr4Ua30Pcg>). This does not represent the real voice of such individuals as it only serves fearmongering purposes and for setting the elite agenda. Even the opposition media avoided giving them a voice, and in the surveyed media outlets, there was not a single case when people being turned away or detained at the fence could speak freely and in a complex manner, at least in the articles we reviewed (Bernáth-Messing 2016).

Ukrainian refugees are treated differently, and opposition and even governmental media provide space and longer interviews with people fleeing Ukraine. A good example of this is an article in *Népszava*, in which journalists interview a woman who says, “My husband has been taken to the front, and we are fleeing with our children.” This fact in itself shows that in the current period, involving the Russo-Ukrainian war, humanitarian discourses are revitalized as opposed to previous periods when they were isolated and marginalized (Melegh et al. 2019; Bernáth-Messing 2016; Nagy 2019). This also shows that the basic rules of East/West hierarchies are not overcome with historical change, and we can even argue that they are actually reinforced. Non-European subalterns cannot speak in the Hungarian media, while “Europeans” can (Spivak 1990).

Furthermore, regardless of the earlier huge debate in the opposition media about the phenomenon of providing settlement permits in return for large fees paid by private investors, there were no reports in which such people buying settlement bonds could talk about their perspectives (Melegh et al. 2019). This suggests that not only do hierarchies matter, but there is a general disinterest in migrant perspectives. Even more, migrants should not be shown at all, as the Hungarian public is so negative about them, especially toward any kind of Easterner.

In addition to the above “rules,” we may also see that legal labor migrants coming in from outside (West or East) are not shown personally and mainly appear as figures in assessments of the impact of migration. For instance, regardless of the tens of thousands of Ukrainians who were staying in Hungary even before the war, in no instance would one have been listened to and their perspectives taken seriously (Meszmann-Fedyuk 2019). If reporting emerges

in this respect, it involves the protests of local workers fighting with such “intruders.” So, we can assume that class perspectives also play a role.

This silence applies very notably to employers whose perspectives and employment policies are not asked about and not explained. This omission is very important proof that the current discourses cannot and do not deal with the systemic context involving migration, and readers/viewers cannot obtain a picture of why certain groups appear in Hungary – beyond “their” wish to earn more, or due to the action of various forces, including the Hungarian government.

HIDING BEHIND THE WEST AND DISCURSIVE UNITY CONCERNING EASTERN BORDERS

The above observations and rules partially related and organized according to East/West hierarchies can be further supplemented by the fact that certain discourses are rarely used by journalists and local political actors. Pro-market and normal EU management or humanitarian frames were rarely used with Hungarian developments, and even the opposition media used them only by hiding behind foreign newspapers or foreign speakers in this respect. This technique may include a review of Western newspapers (we do not find systematic reviews of East European newspapers) or Western, EU, or global speakers. This is a hidden form of East/West framing, as enunciation from the West/Europe/civilized world is a tacit (non-confrontational) technique used to show that the pro-migration attitude is the civilized attitude that is not followed in Hungary.

This happened when the opposition weekly HVG cited the Pope through a BBC report when talking about asylum seekers:

The pope used his East Mediterranean roundtrip to draw attention to the miserable situation of the migrants and refugees. He stressed that the Mediterranean Sea is becoming a cold cemetery without gravestones (...). I beg for stopping the sinking of civilization. https://hvg.hu/vilag/20211205_Ferenc_papa_Politikai_propagandara_hasznaljak_a_menekulteket

A similar choice of speakers and methods could also be identified in the same weekly when it reported on sending humanitarian support to the asylum seekers at the Eastern borders of the EU. HVG Weekly explained that Janez Lenarčič, the

Commissioner for Crisis Management, and Ylva Johansson, the Commissioner for Home Affairs, together with 11 union members, sent tents and other help to Lithuania during the Belarus crisis, during which – the article claims – the Hungarian government stayed idle. This was published in the EU section of the weekly version: https://hvg.hu/eurologus/20210723_Humantiarius_segelyt_kuldott_az_EU_a_litvanoknak

This does not mean that the pro-government press does not use such “Under Western Eyes” techniques by citing politicians, newspapers, and TV programs. They simply swap “Europe as good” for “Europe as bad” (Böröcz 2005). Nonetheless, these cases do not involve the silence of Hungarian speakers. On the contrary, the latter want to show that the “normal” part of Europe and the West actually follows the Hungarian position. An example of this is the following article in the government newspaper *Magyar Nemzet*. Here, the visit of the radical right-wing French essayist-politician Zemmour is used to show the vicious nature of the Hungarian and Western liberal press and the normalcy of Orbán and Zemmour, as opposed to fake anti-racism.

The domestic liberal press, again – as always – is the spokesperson of the Western liberal power. Nothing can show this better than when they write the same about Éric Zemmour after the announcement that he will come to Budapest on Friday, being invited by Viktor Orbán. Immediately, the customary – and by now rather empty – denunciation of him being “far right,” “racist,” and “hate provoking” is repeated as a mantra. After all, this is an excellent opportunity to frighten uninformed people and to connect the prime minister with these denunciations – as the electoral campaign has started.

https://magyarnemzet.hu/velemeney/2021/09/eric-zemmour-avagy-az-iro-aki-megvaltoztatja-a-francia-politikat?utm_source=default&utm_medium=referral&utm_campaign=hiraggregator

THE JOINT FIGHT AGAINST THE HARMFUL EAST

A similar working of East/West discursive links can be seen in the fact that there was rather great unity in evaluating the Belarus crisis, where the two blocks mainly used similar discourses as this was connected more with the East, not Hungary. In this case, in most Eastern countries like Ukraine and Belarus, themes of securitization, strong Europe, and migration pressure were used by all

the media outlets we analyzed. In this, we see how “Western” suspicion against “despotic” “Eastern” governments like Belarus or Russia can be combined with “Western” and “Central European” panic over Muslims, illegal migrants, and non-Europeans. In this way, a new common terrain emerges where the blocks can agree with each other.

This unity is clear in the liberal weekly HVG, which writes in an article at a meeting in Brussels (citing politicians) that the moves of Belarus to export migrants are the acts of a mafia and that we need to have solidarity with countries representing the outer borders of the EU. Then, it ends the text with the following Eurocentric quotation:

At the end of the debate, EU Home Affairs Commissioner Ylva Johansson said that we need unity, determination, and solidarity. We cannot prove ourselves weak in the face of brutal oppression and provocation; we represent democracy and not autocracy. (https://hvg.hu/eurologus/20211005_Nemzetkozi_birosag_ele_allitanak_Lukasenkai)

The joint platform also appears in the pro-government newspaper *Magyar Nemzet*, which supports the Polish acts of defense and approves that illegal migrants have to be blocked at the Polish-Belarus border:

Péter Szijjártó warned – ‘We Central Europeans continue to protect ourselves, Europe, and our borders; we help each other in this regard’ – he said, adding that this year, around 100,000 illegal immigrants have already arrived on the continent from the south. He underlined that Hungary is grateful to the other Visegrád states for their support in the protection of the borders, as well as to Austria for the continuous consultation. (<https://magyarnemzet.hu/kulfold/2021/10/szijjarto-peter-a-lengyeleket-siker-es-politikajuk-miatt-tamadjak>)

Thus, here, we see the functioning of the East/West discourse as creating hierarchies and interlinkages across the blocks.

Rejection of anti-racism and the approved violation of rights

This leads to another rule, which involves a discursive fight over who may shout racism and who may not. The pro-EU management discourse often uses the formation that East European nationalism is dangerous and uses racist

language. The liberal weekly states in the title of an article that Orbán is seen as racist, xenophobic, and shameful in Bosnia. (https://hvg.hu/vilag/20211223_Boszniaban_rasszistanak_tartjak_Orban_szavait). In opposition to these claims, nationalist discourses reject universal, equal rights, potentially legitimizing the rejection of anti-racism and solidarity (Cantat 2016; Cantat-Feischmidt 2019). As shown above, one of the key elements of the nationalist discursive block is that “normal” love of one’s own group outweighs claims of racism, and actually, the competing block uses double standards and basically serves various interests in fighting against racism.

This can take the form of the rejection of the free market itself, which, according to the discursive logic, requires a non-discrimination rule. In an article, the pro-government *Magyar Nemzet* argues like this:

A French migrant protection organization intends to sanction those labor agents who exclude foreign workers. French employers do not want immigrants. A study by the SOS Racisme, a civil rights organization, shows that almost half, 45% of labor agencies help French employers to filter and avoid foreign and “not European looking” workers. (2021.10.08)

https://magyarnemzet.hu/kulfold/2021/10/lapozo-a-francia-migransvedo-szervezet-szankcionalna-a-bevadorlokat-kiszuro-munkakozvetitoket?utm_source=default&utm_medium=referral&utm_campaign=hiraggregator

This aspect of the rejection of anti-racism is strongly connected to the above-analyzed fact concerning the Hungarian media discourses, namely the almost non-existent perspective of the migrants themselves. As explained above, this changed slightly with the Ukrainian refugees, which once again clearly shows that there is an almost unbroken consent around silencing and deploring the rights of the subaltern if he/she is non-European, supposedly Muslim, or African. This decontextualized fear and silencing allows for the legitimization of the infringement of rights regarding asylum and proper treatment, which is a clear novelty in our illiberal era (Melegh et al. 2019)

Need for European and non-European migrant labor and the exploitation of East European labor as separate discourses concerning Europe

Apart from the rule of hiding behind the West, another very interesting development was present in the Hungarian media. The demand for migrant labor within Europe and Eastern Europe is put into the mouth of the EU Commission, or most importantly, into the comments of investors, while the massive outflow of East European migrants and their possible exploitation is separated from the discourse about labor demand. This shows the hegemony of the nationalist bloc and the lack of systematic critique of the market.

For instance, we may read the following:

In Great Britain, employers ask the government to provide 10 thousand temporary labor permits to truck drivers. Otherwise, markets will not be able to function, which has already become a problem after Brexit in certain areas like Northern Ireland.

Finland is seen as the happiest country because it has taken the first prize in this competition, but the population is aging rapidly, and the labor force is declining. After Japan, Finland is in the worst position in this respect. Among the OECD countries, here we find the greatest shortage of skilled labor, but their employment is hindered due to the demand for knowledge of Finnish. Now, they slowly move toward the English language.

[https://hvg.hu/gazdasag/20210827_Szallitas_epitkezes_vendeglatas__egesz_Europat_sujtja_a_munkaerohiany](https://hvg.hu/gazdasag/20210827_Szallitas_epitkezes_vendeglatas_egesz_Europat_sujtja_a_munkaerohiany)

As seen in our description of the key formations above that are connected to the market and labor demand, no exploitation discourses appear. These discursive formations remain separate from the topic of the misuse of migrant labor, which applies to East Europeans. Yet there are separate discursive formations on the “misuse” of East Europeans. For instance, this:

Brussels should stop the exploitation of contracted (East European) guest workers – this is suggested by several MPs in the European Parliament after reading the fact-finding report of the Guardian that [found that], in the meat industry, guest workers employed by labor agents had to work for low wages and among deplorable labor conditions. (2021.10.07)

https://hvg.hu/gazdasag/20211007_Hiaba_mennek_nyugatra_sok_keleteuropai_keleti_bert_kap_ott_is

The friction between the discursive formations of inequalities connected to Europe, and Europe as a civilized/moral agent of fundamental values is even clearer in an interview with the moderate leftist András Jámbor on ATV. In this interview concerning China, there was an open clash between discourses about a moral (fundamentally value-protecting) Europe and the local East European working class, including migrant workers. In this Europeanization paradox, one of the most leftist politicians calls for a moral stand against China among German investors and, at the same time, better protection of East European workers. The clash is played out by the interviewer.

AJ: Well, I think we agree on this basically. These large companies basically buy cheap Hungarian labor, and then, in exchange, Viktor Orbán gets power from them, and they help him in Western and EU political debates. So, the Bavarian leader who asked to illuminate the Munich stadium (with rainbow lights as a protest against the anti-LGBTIQ moves of the Hungarian government) is the leader of the CSU partyand has supported the migration policy of the Orbán government. I think this is the link.

I: I had a different argument When you protest against Chinese universities and credit ... China and Germany are the most important trade partners within the EU sphere... So what can we expect beyond words?

JA: When we talk about political community, a country, the EU with elected representatives ... then it is an important expectation to have a moral minimum to defend human rights....

This shows that in leftist discourses, German companies can be criticized as investors for supporting the Hungarian government as supporters of migration policies while approving the latter's anti-homophobic stand. This confusion is acknowledged, while the politician asks for moral and economic unity against China. This shows how East/West hierarchies, taking different perspectives in relation to this, and the lack of an overall market critique actually blow up the idea of Europe as being moral and show that there are serious schisms within the Liberal-managed Europe block.

Very interestingly, there is no such friction in the nationalist bloc, which, of course, while filtering out non-Europeans and non-Christians, does not consider intra-European inequality and the exploitation of East European migrant labor as a separate discourse but as being linked to the biopolitical loss and demographic fragility of the nation. This is possible as, for instance, in an article, Kövér, the Speaker of Parliament, explained that the “cannibal West” had robbed 25 million people from East European nations and made their national identity fragile. This linkage between a biopolitical and nationalist framing and intra-European hierarchical discourses may illuminate why East European working classes and masses have given much credit to these perspectives (Kalb 2011).

Does the public resonate with these findings? Preliminary results

In 2023, one and half years after the media analysis, a representative survey was launched partially based on the media analysis. When measured according to significant Kendall tau-b association, we could clearly see that both the nationalist and the liberal-managed Europe items had significant links to migration-related questions with the right positive or negative signs. So, according to those who approved the liberal-managed Europe items (protecting human rights, East European countries deviating from EU policies, the misuse of funds, EU helping with economic development, the need to strengthen EU bodies and related security issues, and support European identity), the EU solves labor market problems with migration, and Europe manages migration from non-EU countries well. The only migration-related item that did not correlate well with the discursive statements was that respondents agreed that there is no need to allow many foreigners into the country. This shows that this fear is shared to some extent, even among the respondents associated with the liberal-managed Europe bloc.

The nationalist bloc is more cohesive, and there was only a little hesitation around the question of whether the EU is helping manage migration from non-European countries. It can be assumed that this statement could also be read negatively, namely that, according to the respondents, the EU unfortunately helps immigrants from non-European countries. Nonetheless, we can conclude, based on these results, that the identified discursive blocks in the media resonate rather well with the public, so polarized communication is also related to public division. Very importantly, when we check the predictive strength of various items, then our assumption that the East/West discourses organize most of the various blocks proves to be right. Underrating or overrating the country's

development is an outstanding predictor of whether someone opposes the entrance of more immigrants (Melegh et al. 2016). In this way, the interaction of media and public opinion becomes a key issue, and further studies are needed to better examine this relationship and causality.

CONCLUSION

In the above analysis, we have shown the emergence of two relatively well-organized basic discursive blocs in the Hungarian media concerning Europe and Europeanization and the question of migration. So, we not only observe singular discursive formations but also firmly established actual blocks. In some ways, the latter can be understood as historical-political blocks (Gramsci, 2000). These are in a continuous struggle with each other, while neither provides any systematic critique of social factors and marketization as the key engines behind the rise of migration. Material conditions are mentioned, but no critique is formulated. These blocks interpret and frame many issues differently, but most importantly, they differ in the areas of migration as related to various identity-related questions, the level of sovereignty, the need to protect local culture, and EU actions and policies. They portray each other in an inflammatory mode and present each other as being dangerous to Hungary. This vilifying is a key mechanism in the polarization process.

We have also demonstrated that media polarization can be observed in public opinion a year and a half later after our media analysis, which shows that these blocks may be stable and well formulated, and thus, they directly influence power structures at a societal level. This also shows that these attitudes and public opinions have developed over a long period of time, and they are not the immediate result of governmental or media campaigns (Messing-Ságvári 2017, 2019; Melegh 2023). Further, this indicates that we need to maintain a complex approach as opposed to just focusing on the rise of nationalism and seeing the changes in discourses as transgressions (Wodak 2015).

We have also demonstrated how various discursive mechanisms, like polarization, silencing, positioning in East/West hierarchies, and the rejection of anti-racism, help to consolidate the blocks in their interaction with each other, and they can be seen as important societal mechanisms in Hungarian political development. We also showed that the creation of a general migration category and related material and ideational marketization could be one of the key material factors behind the observed discursive mechanisms that have fueled the polarization among the discursive blocks.

Regardless of polarization, we have shown that there are linking discourses like East and West hierarchies intimately linked to inequalities within and outside the EU. These historically inherited discourses create the ground for how various themes and topics are formulated and what dangers and fears can be named. The nationalist block makes special use of the discursive position that they are fighting for normalcy and against the claimed superiority of the West, which has declined and lost its common sense. It also seems clear that the public resonates with these discursive mechanisms, as we could see on the basis of the survey.

In other ways, common themes like strong Europe versus the decline and chaos of the West and Europe also appear in both blocks. These commonalities and linkages deserve significant attention if we would like to understand the dynamics of the discursive developments – we can envisage the emergence of a new Europe that is more concerned about securitization, fundamental values, and a supposedly stronger Europe. Actually, we could also see that the war in Ukraine led to the emergence of topics associated with a more selective and hierarchical humanism without any real, systematic attempt to reflect on material conditions and the phenomenon of marketization.

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APPENDIX 1. KEY TOPICS IN CHRONOLOGICAL ORDER

July	National consultation on LGBTQ and migration is organized by the government, Fudan Chinese University is challenged by the opposition and the crisis in Belarus start over refugees.
August	Crisis in Afghanistan, Orbán interview with Tucker at Fox News on issues like migration, asylum crisis at the border of Belarus
September	Crisis in Afghanistan, US leaves and future migration crisis is feared, and Belarus crisis continues, rule of law investigation by the EU against Hungary, German election is held, migration policy is reviewed, Demographic Summit is organized by the government with neo-conservative forces,
October	Crisis in Afghanistan, and Belarus, the rule of law investigation by the EU continues, visit of the Egyptian president and Marie Le Pen, where migration is discussed, The Opposition pre-election campaign starts with migration issues discussed marginally.
November	Opposition program launch and countering government policies including migration, Crisis in Belarus continues, the ruling of the EU court against the Hungarian law Stop Soros counters government policies on NGOs and migration, the campaign of the Hungarian opposition figure showing that Orbán takes migrants not Soros.
December	The visit of Macron leads to further discussion on migration, the ruling of the Hungarian Constitutional Court supporting the taking over of EU authority in the case of border control and not granting asylum in case it is EU rulings are not efficient.
January	Ukrainian tension evolves, election campaign continues in which migration issues are promoted by governmental politicians and journalists.
February	War in Ukraine broke out and there was a need to rethink migration discourses according to migratory relations.
March	War in Ukraine continues, refugee waves evolve, and humanitarian help is offered widely. Government help is offered if Ukrainians are employed. Who wants to stay out of the war debate goes on between opposition and government. Government rally is held with migration issues also, and hierarchies are established. Frontex deal with Moldova, EU activity on refugees,

THE REPRESENTATION OF DISINFORMATION, HYBRID WAR AND THE COVID EPIDEMIC IN THE HUNGARIAN MEDIA – A DISCOURSE ANALYSIS¹

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ABSTRACT: *The discursive construction of the populist divide between us – the ingroup of “normal,” “patriotic” people – and them – the outgroup of “suspicious others,” the current enemy – is closely linked to the dissemination of disinformation. The spontaneous spread and interest-motivated dissemination of disinformation is occurring with unprecedented speed and efficiency as a result of info-communication technology. This undermines public trust in public institutions, including the media itself, and threatens democratic values and the political processes. This paper identifies and examines the EU-related populist media discourses of disinformation, hybrid warfare, and the COVID-19 epidemic in Hungary between July 2021 and February 2022. It will be shown to what extent the discourses accompanying the above events and phenomena were used by the individual media sources and the actors presented in them to challenge European institutions and their legitimacy, as well as the European integration project as a whole.*

KEYWORDS: *COVID-19; disinformation; hybrid war; media discourses; EU; political polarization.*

INTRODUCTION

There is a significant overlap in the media representation of disinformation, the COVID epidemic, and the hybrid war issue in relation to the EU. It is well

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known that the harmful effects of disinformation include threats to democratic political processes and democratic values in general, undermining trust in institutions and in digital and traditional media. Disinformation also harms democracies by hindering informed decision-making by citizens. Being uncultured and highly efficient, disinformation has been deployed by state and non-state actors as a key tool for exerting influence (European Commission 2018b). Disinformation on the one hand intervenes with the democratic order by dominating and distorting public discourses and corrupting the process of democratic decision-making concerning central issues of public interest. On the other hand, when a political force wins the elections, it might deconstruct the constitutional order of the state (Bayer et al. 2019). Disinformation also increases polarization in society and decreases trust in mainstream media and institutions (Vériter, Bjola, and Koops 2020). The other indirect effect of disinformation is the temptation of governments to infringe upon civil liberties. As Vilmer et al. (2018) argue, this could be the true end goal of the foreign powers behind disinformation campaigns – that is, to lead governments to take measures that are contrary to their democratic and liberal values. The narratives promoted by disinformation campaigns exploit preexisting tensions in society associated with contentious issues such as migration, crime, the rights of sexual minorities, and reproductive rights. What is important is that the messages are designed to distract the audience from certain issues (Bayer et al. 2019). Government-owned or government-sponsored media outlets may also constitute an important vehicle for the dissemination of disinformation (Vilmer et al., 2018). As for ideological and partisan media outlets, they also promote misperceptions aligned with their ideology. A study by Garrett, Weeks, and Neo (2016) suggests that partisan media promotes misconceptions about reality in at least two different ways. First, by questioning the credibility of experts whose conclusions challenge their ideology. Second, on some occasions, they promote misunderstandings of evidence. Likewise, mainstream media outlets can unwittingly propagate disinformation: “[a] conspiracy theory could now go from fringe speculation to the headlines of network news within weeks. And even if the mainstream news was reporting on it in shock or disgust, it still led millions of viewers and readers to be exposed to these ideas” (Marwick and Lewis (2017: 22).

In the EU, Russian-origin disinformation is a major threat, especially since the annexation of Crimea in 2014. The EU has already taken steps to mitigate the damage by raising awareness (EUvsDisinfo 2015), and since the start of the Russian war against Ukraine, overtly propagandistic Russian state media (Russia Today and Sputnik News) have been banned from the EU with limited success (Euronews 2022). Newly mediatized important events provide an opportunity

for foreign disinformation sources to weaken the EU. This happened with the COVID-19 epidemic and the war in Ukraine.

Disinformation has a serious impact on public opinion, partly due to the uncontrolled social media activity of many “useful idiots” and partly due to state-run so-called “public service” media, which itself spreads disinformation.

The issue of hybrid warfare began to gain prominence in parallel with the war in Ukraine. Presumably, the practice of hybrid warfare (involving a significant amount of disinformation) has become more common than the talk about it.

The aim of the study described here was to analyze the media discourses that were published in selected media – M1, RTL, HÍRTV, ATV, ORIGO, HVG.HU, Népszava.hu, Magyar Nemzet.hu – between July 2021 and March 2022.

The three themes, disinformation, hybrid warfare, and the COVID epidemic, were included in the study partly because of the division of labor between the members of the research team and partly because disinformation is a tool of hybrid warfare and has been frequently used in anti-EU discourse on the COVID epidemic.

In the following, we present the results of an exploratory analysis of media discourses dealing with the EU and Europe that also touched on one of our three main themes (disinformation, hybrid war, and the COVID-19 epidemic). Accordingly, we identified and analyzed the following contents: a) EU or European Union, or Brussels or Europe, and disinformation, lie, fake news or fake news (61 items found) b) EU or European Union, or Brussels or Europe, and hybrid war, (63 items) c) EU or European Union, or Brussels or Europe, and COVID, COVID epidemic, Coronavirus, Coronavirus epidemic or pandemic (459 items).

As expected, the epidemic was an event and a topic of extreme importance, and the number of media discourses about it, therefore, exceeded the number of discourses about the other two topics many times over. The COVID outbreak dominated the media and the political space and provided an opportunity for individuals and media sources to shape the discourse and present themselves and their rivals according to their interests. Each media source covered these issues according to its original affiliation. The pro-government media echoed pro-government views and anti-EU sentiment on COVID-19, while the independent media tried to present an accurate picture of reality.

Media discourses on the COVID epidemic may be diverse depending on the mentioned aspect of the epidemic (economic, health, crisis management), the actors (opposition, government, EU, health professionals, or the public), and the behavior of the public. As the epidemic in Hungary was covered very intensively in a very polarized media space, this is the most important of the three topics and will be presented in more detail and at greater length.

The following three chapters present the media discourses related to the EU. In the first chapter, we present the discourse on the EU and disinformation; in the second chapter, the EU and hybrid war; and in the third chapter, discourses identified as addressing the intersection of the EU and the COVID epidemic.

DISINFORMATION

Disinformation is defined as “false, inaccurate or misleading information designed, presented and promoted to intentionally cause public harm or for profit” (European Commission, 2018a: 10).

In the EU, according to the consensual agreement on use, “disinformation” is the preferred term for fake news (European Parliament, 2015). “The term fake news fails to capture the complex problem of disinformation, which includes content that is not entirely ‘fake,’ such as fabricated information mixed with facts, as well as practices broader than the concept of ‘news,’ such as the creation of automated accounts used for astroturfing³, fake follower networks, fabricated videos, organized trolling, and visual memes. In addition, the term ‘fake news’ is used by some politicians and their supporters as a tool to dismiss reports that they find objectionable” (European Commission, 2018a).

In addition to disinformation and fake news, the term “misinformation” should also be mentioned. In contrast to disinformation, misinformation is distorted or falsified information that is not intentionally manipulated (for some purpose or profit). The disseminator of misinformation believes that he or she is disseminating correct, factual information. The EU’s specialized linguistic database (IATE) also stresses that the terms disinformation and misinformation should not be confused. According to IATE, misinformation is “information that is incorrect or misleading but not intentionally so.”

Since time-series data on exposure to disinformation and trust in the media are not available, we can rely on some surveys from recent years to characterize Hungarian media consumers.

In 2016 (Eurobarometer 452), the majority of EU citizens (53%) trusted the national media, compared to 44% in Hungary.

In 2019 (Table 1), data on disinformation awareness (not directly on the actual spread of disinformation) showed that the latter was around or slightly above the

³ “Astroturfing” is the deceptive practice of masking the supporters of an organized message to make it appear as if the latter is a spontaneous, grassroots message.

EU average in Hungary. A larger proportion of Hungarians than the EU average found it easy to identify disinformation.

Table 1 Attitudes and experiences with disinformation

% who agree with the following statements	In the EU	In Hungary
The existence of misleading or even false information is a problem for democracy in general.	79	78
The existence of misleading or even false news and information is a problem in Hungary.	74	76
You often come across news or information that you believe to be misleading or even false.	69	75
You can easily identify news or information that you think misrepresents the truth or may be false.	58	63

Source: Standard Eurobarometer 92 – 2019 https://europa.eu/eurobarometer/surveys/detail/2255eb92_fact_hu_en.pdf

When respondents were asked *in 2022* about the extent to which they trust different sources of information about the war in Ukraine (Flash Eurobarometer 2022), the data showed that Hungarians trust EU authorities more than national authorities and trust journalists less than the EU average.

Figure 1 Trust in information sources (In general, how much do you trust the following sources of information about the war in Ukraine?)

Source: Eurobarometer (2022) EU response to the war in Ukraine, edited by the author <https://europa.eu/eurobarometer/surveys/detail/2772>

Another survey from 2022 (Ipsos, 2022, p. 67) found that people in Hungary had the least trust in the media of the 29 countries surveyed, with 9% of people believing the media to be reliable and 64% considering it unreliable, compared to a global average of 19% and 43% respectively.

According to a Eurobarometer survey from 2023, nearly half of respondents in the EU (48%) said that public TV and radio (including their online editions) were the most trusted source of news, followed by print media and their online editions, with 38% of respondents trusting them more, compared to 29% for private TV and radio. The credibility of public media in Hungary is by far one of the lowest in the EU-27, with only 25 percent of respondents citing it as their most trusted source of news. In terms of trust, social media (28%) and online platforms (28%) are also ahead of public media.

Figure 2. Use of disinformation-related terms in different media sources, July 2021 – March 2022

Source: author's data collection

The overall picture shows that over the last decade, trust in the media, and in Hungary, in particular in public media, has gradually declined, and it is now half the EU average. Trust in journalists in general is also low (there is no separate data about what respondents think about journalists associated with independent media and public or pro-government media). Trust in EU institutions is higher than trust in domestic institutions, and trust in social media is higher than trust in public media. Awareness of disinformation is similar to the EU average, and Hungarians are even more confident about their ability to stop disinformation than the EU average.

As there is a difference between everyday and official language, we used keywords that better reflect today's Hungarian media vocabulary. To identify news at the intersection of EU and disinformation, we used the following keywords: disinformation, lie, fake news, false report, and propaganda.

Propaganda, a specific form of distorted reality, was also used as a keyword, but surprisingly, there was not a single EU-related article in the selected media outlets that contained this term during the period under review. However, in the few independent media outlets (which are not part of our current sample), discourses related to propaganda did appear – particularly in relation to the war in Ukraine and EU sanctions against Russia.

The chart shows that the terms “lying,” “fake news,” and “false reports” are more frequently used than “disinformation,” and the media that most frequently use these terms are the so-called “public service media,” which in current Hungary serves as a mouthpiece for the state. One explanation for this may be the emotional charge of the words; “disinformation” is neutral and descriptive, with less emotion, while “lying” or “fake news” is better suited to attracting attention and provoking a quick emotional reaction – which seems important in a very polarized society during general election time. In general, the news items that were studied contain discourses that are not related to the issue of disinformation (or its more common equivalent, such as fake news or lies) but only use these terms to disqualify political opponents or ideological rivals or the content of the communication.

In the period under study (July 2021 to March 2022), 61 news items were found in the selected media that related to the intersection of EU and disinformation. In these texts, the following discourses could be identified.

The fight against disinformation and measures taken against it are just other tools for the enemy to censor content it does not like, violate Hungary's sovereignty, and strengthen the rule of Brussels.

These discourses were presented exclusively in pro-government media (Magyar Nemzet and Origo.hu). It is in this context that *Lakmus*,⁴ the first Hungarian fact-checking announcement in the “public service media” was presented. In these discourses, Hungary is being persecuted by George Soros,⁵

4 <https://www.lakmusz.hu/rolunk/>

5 George Soros is a Hungarian-born American businessman and philanthropist. In Hungary, he is considered one of the main enemies of the Orbán government.

Brussels, liberals, the West, etc., and the fight against disinformation, such as fact-checking, is just another liberal ploy to silence opinions they do not like. Facebook moderators are also accused in these discourses of being hypocrites for betraying fundamental liberal values such as freedom of speech and expression. Nowadays, identifying disinformation without any context or attribution can simply involve referring to “Brussels” – a mere item on the list of enemies:

“...And no one can take that away from them, despite globalist pressure, Brussels blackmail, disinformation about the rule of law and the mantra of fake news.” (Topolánszky 2021)

In order to mitigate the epidemic-related situation, cooperation at the EU level is needed in a number of areas, particularly to address the issue of disinformation about the causes and treatment of the disease.

In the independent media (hvg.hu, RTL, and Népszava.hu), when worsening trends emerged during the COVID outbreak, this discourse was usually followed. According to this, raising awareness and tackling disinformation must always be on the EU's to-do list.

China and Russia are spreading disinformation to weaken the EU, and Hungary is helping them.

This discourse was presented in the independent media (hvg.hu and népszava.hu). A specific case occurred in January 2022, when the Hungarian government was condemned for the illegal use of Pegasus spy software and the decision to establish a campus in Budapest for China's Fudan University. A draft European Parliament report on foreign interference in the EU's democratic processes and misinformation (European Parliament 2022) expressed concern that Hungary (and Serbia) are helping China and Russia to achieve their geopolitical goals and contributing to the spread of disinformation in the region. It also condemned the close links between Fidesz and Jobbik (a Hungarian government party and another right-wing party) and the Kremlin. The report accuses “malign and authoritarian foreign states and non-state actors such as Russia and China” of interventionist tactics aimed at subverting democracy.

Quasi-disinformation

This information about the disinformation practice of the government is presented in the independent media (hvg.hu).

These discourses critically depict so-called “peacock-dance communication,”⁶ – where there is a huge gap between the regime’s official international position and the narratives being disseminated domestically, leading to different content for different audiences, e.g., in Brussels and Hungary, or different content for the same audience at different times, avoiding communication with independent media, and contacting only the partisan media where only pseudo-questions are asked. This in itself is not necessarily disinformation, but in terms of effect – creating confusion and maintaining voter engagement and loyalty – it is almost the same thing.

In February 2022, the EU-Africa summit in Brussels concluded with the adoption of an eight-point joint declaration. The document advocates the creation of legal migration routes, which Viktor Orbán agreed with. Even at the end of the summit, it was not clear why Viktor Orbán posted on his social networking site before leaving for Brussels that “We stand as David against the Goliaths of Brussels.”

Disinformation is the stuff that political rivals spread, and it is a major danger – especially when they spread unpleasant things about us.

This type of discourse is mainly prevalent in the so-called “public media” (M1) and pro-government media (Magyar Nemzet and Origo.hu) and is often used as a tool to dismiss the opinions of political rivals. The whole independent media is classified as a “fake news factory” by the Prime Minister (Szili -Fábián 2018) and by many members of the governing party.

HYBRID WAR

Hybrid war refers to a military strategy that uses political warfare and mixes conventional warfare, irregular warfare, and cyber warfare with other methods

⁶ The current Prime Minister of Hungary, Viktor Orbán, once called this good practice when he was negotiating in Brussels.

of influence, such as disinformation campaigns, fake news (*kompromatka*, ‘hahaganda’), diplomacy, law enforcement, and foreign electoral interference.

Much of the discourse on hybrid warfare has been intertwined with the discourse on migration, giving the speaker the opportunity to denounce EU migration policy. On the Polish-Belarusian border, the migrant crisis triggered by Lukashenko created an opportunity to update the Hungarian populists’ enemy list: Brussels attacking Hungarians, the EU’s ineptitude at managing migration, and the migrant threat are discussed alongside the success of Hungarians and Viktor Orbán in managing migration. More than 40 percent of the 63 items were published within one month during the period under review (November 2021), 60 percent of them in the government media (m1, origo.hu, magyarnemzet.hu).

The hybrid war between normal people and the liberal lobby is not what it seems.

In populist conservative, pro-government media (M1, Magyar Nemzet, and Origo.hu), journalistic ideologues often redefine and reinterpret concepts such as hybrid war. Normal people, the majority, are described as oppressed by a perverse, aggressive minority in a hopeless world.

“This is not a conflict of nations, nor are the advocates of globalism trying to subjugate the ‘localists.’ The real conflict is between the mass of normality and a rather narrow minority. The battlefield advantage does not necessarily lie in numbers. Those of us who want to maintain normality are in the majority, but the more effective weapons are concentrated in the hands of a few. And the era of hybrid warfare was introduced by the few to ensure that the existing imbalance would not only develop but become almost irreversible – an irreversible process – in the interests and favor of the minority.” (Földi 2021)

“Hybrid warfare” between quotation marks – so-called hybrid wars

These discourses question the use of the term itself. The use of quotation marks is meant to suggest that either there is no hybrid war at all or what is happening on the Polish-Belarusian border is not a hybrid war.

“The authorities have recently witnessed a significant increase in migratory pressure across the Polish-Belarusian border and from the Middle East via Belarus towards the eastern border of the European Union. The increase in immigration is an ‘organized action’ which, according to the Poles, is a ‘hybrid war’ waged by Belarus. Since the beginning of August alone, more than two thousand people have tried to cross the Polish-Belarusian border illegally.” (Origo 2021)

Fragmented, incomplete discourses

These discourses, presented in pro-governmental media, are characterized by omission. In these, one can only learn what is happening, typically at a concrete, illustrative level (e.g., thousands of migrants are freezing on the Polish-Belarusian border), but the level of abstraction does not rise any further; one cannot know why it is happening, what is happening, who the actors are, what they are doing, or what motivates them. In general, the parts of the discourse related to Lukashenko and the Kremlin are amputated by the speakers and often linked to the discourse that “the EU is incompetent on migration” and “Hungary is wise, farsighted, and consistent about migration issues.”

The tactic of silencing is a feature of propagandistic communication. During the campaign leading up to the Hungarian parliamentary elections in April 2022, Prime Minister Viktor Orbán never named the opposition’s candidate for prime minister. Further, when Ukraine was attacked by Russia, Hungarian government politicians carefully avoided naming the aggressor. The same tactics are used to avoid naming the perpetrators of the ‘migrant crisis’ and to avoid calling what is happening on the Polish-Belarusian border a hybrid war.

“According to him [Foreign Minister Péter Szijjártó], all those politicians in Brussels who have taken a pro-migration stance over the past six years, who have kept the mandatory resettlement quota on the agenda and refused to give money to countries protecting their borders, should now go to the Polish-Belarusian border, and ‘shame on them.’ So Szijjártó made a statement about the situation on the Belarusian-Polish border without mentioning Belarus’ role in it. This was done earlier by Justice Minister Judit Varga.” (hvg.hu 2021)

Brussels, background power, secret political powers – the hybrid war is fueled by the EU – pure ‘conteo’

These discourses appear in the so-called “public media” and pro-government media (M1, Magyar Nemzet, Origo) – the “experts” from these newspapers envisage a chaotic world in which only two things are certain: inevitable danger and a main enemy in the form of a “background” power. The basic structure of the discourse is simple and involves moving in a few steps from a specific question to the basic problem challenging the world, which is the ultimate explanation for everything. In this approach, the EU is evil, not of its own volition, but because it is in the grip of a “background power.” Sometimes the role of this background power in these narratives is played by George Soros.

While medical disinformation discourses about the COVID outbreak failed to penetrate the Hungarian mainstream media, remaining in social media and the fringe media, conspiracy theories about the power politics of hybrid war have been given free rein – at least in the pro-government “public service” media.

“ – What makes defense impossible for Europe today is that a large part of the European political elite, led by Brussels, is simply in the grip of a backroom power which is not seeking to defend Europe but to achieve the aims of this particular war, whether overtly or covertly. This issue is difficult to resolve because the political forces in decision-making positions are working with the enemy. For this reason, systems that would otherwise be capable of defending themselves, such as armies, NATO soldiers, and border protection organizations, are not given the right orders to defend themselves but instead create an unacceptable living situation for them. The problem is not that there is no protection but that the policy does not allow it.

- There is already talk of hybrid warfare in the EU. Do you think the current migration crisis could be a turning point?

- From the mouth of the Brussels bureaucracy, hybrid warfare implies that Russia is fomenting this tension between Belarus and Poland; in other words, Lukashenka and his team are attacking the EU on behalf of Russia. This is not the case. That is precisely the logic of hybrid warfare [–] that I am diverting attention to someone else, making someone else the scapegoat, while I am the guilty party.

- *Because starting migration with unnecessary wars, not stopping the invasion at Europe's borders, and creating tensions between European governments is not an attack by Russia, but [is due to] the cooperation of Brussels bureaucrats. (Földi 2021, Magyar Nemzet)*

- *There is a hybrid war on the EU's eastern border, we are in solidarity with Poland, but let's ask quietly: 'what has been going on at Hungary's southern border since 2015?' asked Kövér. He stressed: 'the West is waging a hybrid war against the Hungarian and Polish governments.'* (Kövért 2021 Magyar Nemzet)

Lukashenko's migrant crisis on the Polish-Belarusian border is part of a hybrid war.

These pieces in the independent media (hvg.hu, Népszava) rely mainly on Polish and EU sources and quote politicians. They claim that Lukashenko, the Belarusian president who lost the recent elections and, with Russian help, suppressed his political opponents, has retained power, leading the EU to impose sanctions against him and a number of Belarusian officials. The artificially created migrant crisis at the border is partly Lukashenko's revenge on the EU and partly the implementation of Russian orders. The method avoids the use of arms but weakens EU unity by creating chaos and making it impossible to apply the EU's core values consistently because of the self-contradictory nature of the situation.

COVID-19 PANDEMIC

To examine the discourses related to COVID-19, we followed the usual procedure: a) we identified all the news published by selected media related to the EU, the European Union, and Brussels, and b) we filtered these articles to those that mentioned the pandemic (coronavirus, epidemic, COVID).

As a result of this process, 459 items remained which contained some kind of relevant discourse.

Table 2 shows the course of the epidemic in Hungary. The most severe wave in Hungary started after the start of vaccination. Modern vaccines were used, but traditional Chinese and Russian vaccines were also widely used in Hungary,

especially at the start of vaccination. The data for Hungary are quite negative, both in terms of mortality and vaccination rates.

Table 2 *The COVID-19 epidemic in Hungary*

Waves of the pandemic so far	5
The most severe wave	the third (peak 17 April 2021)
Deaths per 100,000 inhabitants	504.76 (3rd worst in the world after Peru and Bulgaria)
First vaccination start date	23 December 2020
Vaccination with at least one dose (%)	64.8
Vaccination with the full vaccine series (%)	62.7
Vaccination with supplementary dose (%)	38.3
Willingness to vaccinate against COVID-19	12% of the Hungarian adult population is determined not to be vaccinated against SARS-CoV-2, and among Hungarians aged 30-39 years old, the proportion of non-vaccinators reaches 23%
Vaccines used	Pfizer – Biontech, Moderna, Sputnik V, Astra Zeneca, Sinopharm, Jansen

Sources: WHO 2022; Johns Hopkins University 2024; IDEA 2021; author's compilation.

The COVID-19 pandemic was accompanied by an unprecedented wave of false and misleading information, the so-called “infodemic” (WHO Infodemic). COVID-19 was also exploited by disinformation campaigns by foreign states, mainly China and Russia, to discredit the EU and democratic governance in general. The disinformation campaigns created misleading narratives, such as identifying the EU’s alleged lack of assistance to partners and third countries, instead highlighting the goodwill of China and Russia (Bayer et al. 2021). This led the European Commission to publicly identify China and Russia as the main perpetrators of online disinformation. The EU recognized that the pandemic had opened the door to disinformation campaigns aimed at undermining the credibility of European democracies and the EU and national or regional authorities. It also accused Russia and China of “seeking to undermine democratic debate, exacerbate social polarization and improve their own image in the context of COVID-19” (European Commission 2020: 3).

EUvsDisinfo is a flagship project of the European External Action Service’s East StratCom Task Force. The project was established in 2015 with the aim of better anticipating and responding to the Russian Federation’s ongoing disinformation campaigns that are affecting the European Union, its Member States and the countries of the Common Neighborhood. EUvsDisinfo uses data

analysis and media monitoring services in 15 languages to identify, collate, and expose disinformation cases from pro-Kremlin media in the EU and Eastern Partnership countries.

At the intersection of the EU and the COVID pandemic in Hungary, the four pro-EU narratives defined by EUvsDisinfo (2020) are clearly discernible in the majority of the media discourses that were analyzed:

1. The EU is not able to handle the pandemic, and it is on the verge of collapse. This narrative has been disseminated by pro-Kremlin sources and a number of domestic networks/sources in and outside the EU.
2. The EU is selfish and betrays its own values. This narrative has also been spread by pro-Kremlin sources and numerous domestic networks/sources inside and outside the EU.
3. Russia and China are responsible powers. The pro-Kremlin media focused on Russian aid to Italy, proclaiming that “Russia helps Italy and the EU does not.” Pro-Kremlin sources portrayed the Chinese “global project” as superior to the EU. The Chinese state-controlled media and social media outlets heavily promoted the idea that the Chinese model was superior in the fight against COVID-19 while highlighting global expressions of gratitude for Chinese aid deliveries, including in Italy.
4. Finally, the EU is using the crisis to advance its own interests.

Results of the analysis of the discourse on COVID

During the period under study (July 2021 to March 2022), there were, on average, 100 items per month related to the research question. We focused on those in which the keywords were not just mentioned but were part of a discourse. Since this was the pre-election period in Hungary, discourses creating or blaming enemies often combined a whole range of enemies; Brussels, liberals, the declining West, and the political opposition were often combined into one item, but the discourse was not about Brussels, but about the opposition. In ironic descriptions of anti-EU propaganda, Brussels is used not only as a noun but also as a verb, such as “to Brusselize” (meaning to condemn, blame or blame Brussels, i.e., the EU).

Using the items (news items from selected media), the following discourses were identified and will be elaborated later: the EU’s failure to tackle the pandemic; the existence of a diabolical or evil plan to destroy Europe; Hungary is doing better than the EU; the EU is selfish and betrays its values; China and Russia are doing better; the EU is exploiting the crisis to advance its own interests.

In Hungary, the public service media is under pro-government influence and, according to critics, a mouthpiece for government propaganda. In independent media, anti-EU propaganda discourses are also quoted or ironically presented. The pro-government *origo.hu*, *magyarnemzet.hu*, and M1 TV presented the same discourses using the same wording and repeated them exhaustively. After it was semi-officially revealed that Sinopharm is ineffective in a quarter of people over sixty, and the Prime Minister offered people a third booster vaccine, the “China is good” discourse disappeared.

After the final climax of the pandemic, discussions about the EU began to focus on the allocation of the recovery fund to Hungary rather than on how to deal with the pandemic. In the protracted negotiations, the EU Commission called for anti-corruption measures and greater transparency from the Hungarian government, while the government’s discourse accused the EU of making political rather than professional decisions about the so-called Child Protection Act (which conflates protecting children from pedophiles with homophobia).

From 24 February 2022 onward, the pandemic issue disappeared completely, giving way to the war-related crisis in Ukraine. The upcoming elections on 3 April filled the media space with the communication turbulence of the Hungarian government (the previous pro-Putin stance had to be explained under the circumstances).

Despite the failure of the “opening to the East” strategy (a major element of government rhetoric in recent years) and the exposure of the government’s overheated pro-Russian policies, the dominant narrative has portrayed the opposition as the enemy of the state and the nation.

Discourse on the failure of the EU

This discourse appeared in the pro-government media M1, *Origo.hu*, and *Magyar Nemzet* (which overlap with the public media in contemporary Hungary) and are often intertwined with the discourses “Hungary is doing better against it” and “Russia and China are good.” In these cases, the EU is portrayed as a slow, disorganized, underperforming entity accused of not providing enough vaccines, masks, or respirators. The EU is to blame in this context not only for the delayed initial response at the start of the pandemic but also for the failure to recover quickly and the lack of Community resources for recovery.

The reports of a rebellious and brave Hungary deciding to buy vaccines from elsewhere (China and Russia) are intended to reinforce the image of an efficient, well-organized, and generous China and Russia and to point out that the EU is descending into chaos.

The real situation and chances of Chinese and Russian citizens were never discussed. There were reports of aggressive demonstrations in European cities against the epidemic-related measures, highlighting police brutality. For the same reason, the Hungarian “national consultation” became part of the discourse on COVID-19. It was used to show that Hungary is doing better because instead of suppressing people and their opinions (as in other countries), the Hungarian government is asking for people’s opinions and acting accordingly. The post-epidemic national consultation was about post-crisis recovery. The media, the national poster campaign, and the questions in the consultation questionnaire⁷ show that pandemic-related issues were a good way (at least for the government) to keep alive the old discourses on migration: the old enemies – Brussels and Soros – and highlight the “savior”: the (better performing) Hungarian government that is protecting Europe’s borders.

In the summer of 2021, Budapest hosted some mass events: the World Hunting Exhibition, the European Football Championship, and the Eucharistic Congress. In the “EU is a failure, Hungary is doing better” discourse, it was often said that this summer would have been a summer of restrictions for Hungarians, with events canceled due to the slow pace of vaccine procurement in Brussels, but with the help of China and Russia, Hungary was able to organize these events, while other EU countries were unable to lift restrictions. Critics who argued that the government should not have taken a health risk with these events were accused of being anti-Christian or of depriving “normal people” of their pleasures (football and hunting).

The “diabolical plan and danger” narratives

In these discourses, the future of the EU is apocalyptic – involving the failure of the EU in the future tense – and the consequence of an evil plan (as presented in M1, Origo.hu and Magyar Nemzet). This is sometimes only superficially linked to the pandemic. The pandemic serves only as a gloomy background to a long

⁷ For example, questions 12 and 13:

12. The European Court of Justice has ruled that the detention of immigrants at the Hungarian border in transit zones is illegal. The ruling states that migrants must be allowed to enter Hungary during the epidemic. This decision coincides with George Soros’ old migration plan to let in a million migrants a year at any cost. Do you agree that the government should continue to stand up against immigration and maintain a tight protection of Hungary’s borders? Yes No
13. Brussels is preparing an offensive against the immigration-related provisions of the Hungarian Constitution. They want to force us to amend the articles of the Fundamental Law that prevent migration. Do you agree that the Hungarian government should stick to its anti-immigration rules, even at the cost of open conflict with Brussels? Yes No

jeremiad about the future of Europe and the world. The discourse often begins by claiming that the European Union is facing dangerous times: pandemics and migration flows will determine the most important developments in world politics and economics. In this way, pandemics and migration are linked, and this provides a solid basis for the other ingredients to be strung together.

“The EU’s role in the global economy, in industrial and technological innovation, is diminishing. The continent has been hit by a financial crisis, a migration crisis and then a coronavirus epidemic, while the foundations of the eurozone are cracking, the budgetary and public finance situation in the southern member states is deplorable, not to mention the demographic decline that is a major cause of all the problems. Firstly, the validity of creation, of the Christian parable, has been called into question, on the basis of rationality and the assumption that what the human mind cannot understand, measure or experience does not exist. Doubts about ancient truths have become the source of modern knowledge. Following the trend of doubting God, scepticism about the importance of nations, about the ‘love of place,’ has spread: that our natural environment, our ancestors, their customs, our linguistic-cultural tradition derived from them, is a recent construction, a romantic fantasy, [that it is] now time to leave behind in the face of the global goals of an increasingly unified Humanity. And now – for several decades – we are witnessing ... the questioning of the female-male creation and the consequent denial of the child’s right to adequate physical, mental and moral protection.” (Szánthó 2021, Magyar Nemzet)

Sometimes, the EU itself poses a threat, for example, when the number of incoming migrants increases and, according to the discourse, the need for mandatory resettlement quotas is repeatedly raised by NGOs and the Brussels bureaucracy. But even in these difficult times, the Hungarian government is resisting and continues to disagree with the plan for mandatory distribution.

Childless Western couples who have given up on having children of their own are also part of the general danger because their world is no longer biologically self-sustaining, so they are forced to import people from outside – and this brings us to the issue of dangerous migration, rephrased as the problem of “replacement.”

And in the extended discourse, migrants are a health risk because they spread the coronavirus. In these discourses, political forces, Brussels bureaucrats, left-wing liberal groups, NGO networks, and the media are also fomenting ideological conflicts that threaten to bring down the EU.

“Hungary is doing better”

In these flattering discourses (presented in M1, Origo.hu and Magyar Nemzet), Hungary is months ahead of Europe in terms of vaccination or reopening. The success of the vaccination program is also largely due to the government’s timely realization, before the failed vaccine purchase in Brussels, that it should not rely only on the European Union but also open up to the East. The Hungarian economy is projected to recover to above its pre-plague level by autumn 2021, while most EU countries have not yet managed to do this. Selected statistics were cited on how happy Hungarians are compared to their less happy EU counterparts.

Whenever possible, this economic success was mentioned. In such reports, the relevant indicators were carefully chosen: the number of deaths from COVID and the excess deaths per 100,000 people were mentioned only in periods when the EU average, the Central European average, or the Visegrad average was worse.

The “wise decision” of the Hungarian government to place hospitals under military administration was praised, and the “*calm governance*” of the government was praised, which contributed significantly to the smooth implementation of the restrictions and the restart of the economy in Hungary. The Hungarian state “*went to war*” and saved the country; thanks to this, we did not see images like those in Bergamo, Portugal, or Romania – the discourses claim.

Finance Minister Mihály Varga, often quoted by government media, said that before the epidemic, the Hungarian economy was the second fastest-growing economy in Europe and that after the global crisis, Hungary was still one of the fastest-recovering economies in Europe. The recovery would not have been so rapid, he said, if the pandemic had not hit a strong, fast-growing and resilient Hungary.

One factor behind Hungary’s supposed success is a strong leader who is the saviour of the country. The prime minister has been preoccupied with the leader topos for more than a decade. He has argued that in difficult situations in the EU a strong leader is the salutary solution. “*...when we are in trouble institutions are not able to help. So, you need personal leadership. And personal leadership is not respected at all in the European Union...*” (Orbán 2015)

“The EU is selfish and betrays its own values” discourse

In Hungarian public service media (M1) and pro-government media (Origo.hu, Magyar Nemzet), coverage of the protests against the EU’s pandemic measures often concluded that despite the alleged brutal dispersal of protests,

there were no international repercussions, which is an example of the application of double standards and thus a betrayal of fundamental liberal values. The case of the Recovery and Resilience Plan not being adopted by Hungary is the most striking example of the alleged betrayal of fundamental EU values linked to the pandemic.

Hungary submitted its recovery plan on 12 May 2021 (European Commission 2021). As a general rule, if there had been no obstacles, Hungary would have received the related funds by now. However, due to the outstanding issues with the plan, which was intended to strengthen the anti-corruption framework, including improving prosecutorial efforts and access to public information, negotiations have been delayed and have not been concluded to date. The Commission says EU funds for Hungary are being withheld because of the need to strengthen the anti-corruption framework. At the same time, the Hungarian government and Fidesz, the governing party, claim that the EU Commission is acting according to its political biases. They accuse the Commission of making political judgments because, after the Hungarian parliament passed an amendment to the child protection law in June 2021 that EU institutions say discriminates against LGBTQ people, negotiations on Hungary's economic recovery plan stalled.

The two events (the condemnation of the so-called Child Protection Act in the European Parliament because of its homophobic nature and because it conflates homosexuality with pedophilia, and the rejection of the Recovery Plan) have been linked in the discourse of Hungarian government political actors according to their interests. Since June 2021, the EU-critical discourse, although still starting from the COVID crisis (as the recovery fund is meant to mitigate the damage the latter caused), has grown into a discourse in its own right, with EU criticism at its core.

According to this discourse, the EU is biased (it has already given the funds to other countries), persecuting and punishing Hungary (for not participating in the LGBTQ canon), interfering in its internal affairs, and violating Hungary's sovereignty. This discourse allows the public and the media to silence the fundamental objection raised by the lack of guarantees against corruption in the Hungarian Recovery Plan.

“Russia and China do better; they are the good ones” discourse

This discourse is very often intertwined with the “Hungary is doing better” discourse (presented in M1. Origo.hu and Magyar Nemzet). Without the Eastern vaccines and timely government decisions, Hungary could not have performed

better and saved people. Thanks to the Russian and Chinese vaccines imported into the country, Hungarians were among the first to have access to life-saving vaccines.

China was described as a world of the East, with new state and digital giants rising and economic and military centers gradually shifting eastwards. This image was contrasted with a so-called neo-Marxist, bloated liberalism waging a (self-)murderous war against its own country: Western civilization.

As mentioned in the introduction, there were problems with the effectiveness of the Chinese vaccine among the elderly. Since then, these discourses have faded.

Discourse of “the EU exploiting the crisis to promote its own interests”

This form of discourse was very rare (presented in *Magyar Nemzet*) and involved references to business considerations embedded in a wider power context whereby centralization of the procurement of protective and other equipment, which is otherwise rational, strengthens the former’s mandate. As a result, the narrative suggests that Member States are devalued, and some have been badly served in the distribution of vaccines. Brussels thus seeks to increase its power through disease management under the guise of a Health Union. However, the issue of disease management, along with other health issues in the EU, has been left to the Member States.

CONCLUSIONS

The European integration project is at the heart of political polarization in Hungary. Viktor Orbán’s government in Hungary has been characterized by defiance and criticism of the EU, its institutions, and values (Bayer 2020). The confrontation with the EU is often built around identity-based arguments, which tend to question the values of the EU. The questioning of liberal democratic governance promoted by the EU is exemplified in an article published by Viktor Orbán himself in the conservative pro-government Hungarian newspaper *Magyar Nemzet*, where he wrote that

“The doctrine that ‘democracy can only be liberal’ – this golden calf, this monumental fetish – has been debunked.” (Orbán, 2022).

This controversy culminated in Viktor Orbán's public campaigns against the EU institutions. These included the 2018 "Let's Protect Hungary" campaign against a European Parliament resolution that raised concerns about systemic problems with the rule of law in Hungary (Bayer- de La Baume, 2018) and a 2019 poster campaign funded by Hungarian taxpayers that accused Jean-Claude Juncker, then president of the European Commission, and Hungarian-American businessman George Soros, of advocating migration plans that threatened Hungary's national security (Bayer 2020).

While political polarization over the EU is present in other EU countries, it is exceptionally visible in the Hungarian media. This can be explained by the government's control of the media. The Hungarian government-controlled media are themselves directly involved in the dissemination and production of disinformation against the EU. There is no need for organized Russian disinformation campaigns since the pro-government media, especially the public service media, perform this task. Such media spread pro-Kremlin narratives. According to the Oxford Internet Institute, "pro-government disinformation is the equivalent of Kremlin narratives without direct influence from Russia" (Bradshaw – Howard 2018). This is not limited to pro-Russian messages but also includes attempts to portray the EU as weak and unviable, thus undermining trust in EU institutions in general (Chatterjee – Krékó 2020). It is not surprising, therefore, that the narratives revealed by EUvDisinfo have been embraced by the pro-government Hungarian media. It should be stressed that domestic disinformation can be much more effective as local governments have more information about the preferences and needs of their own populations (Szicherle – Krekó 2021).

After Fidesz came to power in Hungary with a two-thirds majority in 2010, Viktor Orbán's explicit goal was to establish an illiberal regime, and he announced a policy of opening up to the East. Central to this ideology was the fight against threatening external forces, multinational companies, migrants, and the EU. The party changed the constitution, the electoral law, and the media law, obtaining significant media dominance. Brussels became a target of blame, and this was strongly reflected in the discourse on COVID-19. In it, the Hungarian prime minister criticized not so much selfishness as EU inertia, embedded in a narrative of a declining West, contrasting this with Russian and Chinese performance and effectiveness.

However, the vast majority of the Hungarian population is pro-EU, so there are clearly limits to the domestic elite's criticism of the EU. This was especially true before the elections, so the strong EU criticism of the Hungarian government turned into a pragmatic sovereigntist stance in the second half of the period under review.

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EUROPEAN UNION, GEOPOLITICS, AND THE WAR IN UKRAINE: AN ANALYSIS OF GEOPOLITICAL DISCOURSES IN HUNGARIAN MEDIA IN 2021-2022

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ABSTRACT: *The paper analyzes Hungarian media discourse related to the geopolitics of the European Union between July 2021 and March 2022. The qualitative analysis draws on a sample (n=100) of the geopolitics-related media corpus of the MEDEU project. Before the start of the Russian invasion of Ukraine on February 24, 2022, the questions of migration and border control, the enlargement of the European Union in the Western Balkans, discourses about the future of Europe, and the assumed divide between the “Eastern” and “Western” Member States dominated the geopolitics-related media content. Following the Russian attack, the Russo-Ukrainian war became the most salient topic, while older themes were also reframed in light of this event. Governmental narratives and terminology dominated the analyzed media contents, which were reinforced through (so-called) experts presented in pro-governmental media. At the same time, the political opposition and government-critical media were rarely able to present and/or disseminate their own narratives.*

KEYWORDS: *EU enlargement, geopolitics, media analysis, migration, Russo-Ukrainian war*

INTRODUCTION

The paper presents Hungarian media discourses related to the geopolitics of the European Union between July 1, 2021, and March 31, 2022. The analysis draws

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on the media contents of the Hungarian media corpus of the “*MEDIATIZED EU – Mediatized Discourses on Europeanization and Their Representations in Public Perceptions*” Horizon 2020 project. Although the term “geopolitics” is widely known and used by politicians, journalists, security experts, and members of several scholarly fields, its definitions and applications are far from consistent (Dodds, 2019). In most cases, it is understood as the division of the world into geographical units (including metaphors such as the “Iron Curtain”), the “geographical understanding” of the world based on these divisions, and the foreign and security policies deriving from this understanding (Dodds, 2019). An important part of the scholarly study of geopolitics is critical reflection on these practices: how these divisions and “geographical understandings” are constructed, how they function, and what goals these geopolitical constructs (geographical units and metaphors) serve, as well as the related interpretations and identities (Dodds, 2019).

In line with these considerations, the paper investigates how the geopolitical challenges of the European Union (such as its enlargement in the Western Balkans, the Russo-Ukrainian war, and irregular migration from outside of Europe) are represented in Hungarian media, what discursive frames are used for their interpretation, and what the outlined potential/desired actions are in these media contents. This also includes the media framing of the geopolitical perspectives of the Hungarian Government and (when it is present) the perspective of the political opposition. Additionally, we cover regional geopolitical constructs such as the “Visegrad Four” (V4), which has become a salient collaborative unit within the European Union.

CONTEXT

The European Union faced several important geopolitical challenges at the beginning of the 2020s, including migration crises, the difficulties of the Western Balkans and “Eastern” enlargements, and the relationship with the major global geopolitical actors such as the United States, China, and Russia. The Russian invasion of Ukraine, starting on February 24, 2022, created several further salient challenges, including the issue of energy security and the ability of European states to defend themselves against external aggression. The war came with serious sacrifice: at the time of writing (2024 November), the number of injured and casualties, according to secret service intelligence, may have surpassed a million people (The Wall Street Journal, 2024), while the GDP of Ukraine shrank by 30 percent in 2022 (European Parliament, 2024a).

Currently, 20 percent of the internationally recognized territory of Ukraine is under Russian occupation, but the near-daily air strikes (which regularly result in civilian casualties) involve the majority of the territory of the country, causing serious infrastructural damage. Another consequence of the war is that several million Ukrainians have had to leave their place of residence, many of whom applied for asylum in EU Member States. According to UNHCR, by November 2024, 6,225,700 Ukrainians had applied for asylum in a European state and 560,200 outside of Europe (UNHCR, n.d.). The war caused the largest European wave of migration since the end of the Second World War (Dodds et al., 2023).

The war also put the question of EU enlargement into a new perspective. Following the “big bang” enlargements of 2004 and 2007 and the accession of Croatia in 2012, the enlargement process practically became stranded: accession talks with countries of the Western Balkans progressed slowly (Serbia, Montenegro) or had not even begun before the start of the war (North Macedonia, Bosnia-Herzegovina). At the same time, none of the countries of the “Eastern partnership” (Georgia, the Republic of Moldova, Azerbaijan, Armenia) had even reached candidate status prior to the war. Although the EU has used the issue of accession as a geopolitical strategy since the Balkan Wars of the 1990s (Anghel & Džankić, 2023), several experts have pointed out that, unlike in the case of post-Soviet Eastern Europe, in the case of the Western Balkans and the “Eastern partnership” there was no real intention for enlargement (e.g., Petrovic & Tzifakis, 2021; Verdun & Chira, 2011). According to this interpretation, keeping the issue of enlargement on the political agenda and promising potential future accession have been used by the Union primarily to ensure the stability and security of the area and to limit Chinese and Russian influence in the region (Anghel & Džankić, 2023). The Russian invasion created a new situation in the enlargement process: following the start of the war, Ukraine, Georgia, and the Republic of Moldova applied to join the European Union (in June 2022, Ukraine and Moldova officially became candidate countries). Simultaneously, accession talks with Albania and North Macedonia finally started (Albania officially became a candidate country in 2014 and North Macedonia in 2005).

The Hungarian government took a geopolitical position different from the EU majority on multiple issues, including the question of migration, the enlargement of the EU, and the relationship with China and Russia. Governmental positions were shaped by both domestic and international (primarily EU-related) considerations. Following the landslide victory in 2010, the Fidesz-KDNP coalition returned to power with a two-thirds parliamentary supermajority, and the second Orbán government was formed. The new government quickly began dismantling constitutional checks and balances and building a new, more centralized regime with extensive control over the political system and

the media, which exhibited several autocratic traits (the characteristics of this new regime have been extensively discussed in the literature, see, e.g., Körösnéyi et al., 2020; Krekó & Enyedi, 2018; Lengyel & Ilonszki, 2012). These changes quickly attracted criticism from EU institutions (e.g., European Parliament, 2013, 2022, 2024b) in response to which the Hungarian government launched an intensive anti-EU campaign, which has been going on (with minor interruptions) up to the present day. Some typical examples involve the so-called “peace march” (a mass demonstration organized by a pro-governmental NGO/GONGO) on January 21, 2012, which featured the slogan “We will not be a colony [of the EU],” the governmental communication related to the 2015 European migration crisis (see, e.g., Bocskor, 2018; Bognár et al., 2022), the 2016 “quota” referendum campaign against the refugee resettlement scheme proposed by the European Commission (see European Commission, 2016; about the referendum campaign see e.g., Demeter, 2018; Gessler, 2017), the anti-EU campaign during the COVID-19 pandemic (see e.g., Szabó & Szabó, 2022), and currently the governmental communication related to the Russo-Ukrainian war (in particular, the opposition to the EU sanctions against Russia). One goal of these campaigns was to strengthen support among the electorate and shape issue-related public opinions, which was particularly successful in the case of the governmental anti-immigration position (see, e.g., Bíró-Nagy, 2022). Another goal was to delegitimize, in the eyes of the Hungarian electorate, criticism coming from the EU, as well as to delegitimize EU institutions and, in a broader sense, “Western liberal” values. As an alternative, the prime minister and the governmental communication presented a traditionalist, nativist-nationalist, Christian-conservative value system (see e.g., hvg.hu, 2018; Orbán, 2014).

In order to expand the economic and political room for maneuvering internationally, the Hungarian government initiated the so-called “Eastern opening” policy. This policy strived for closer and more visible cooperation with countries including China, Russia, and several other autocratic systems. Simultaneously, the government intended to strengthen its position within the EU by promoting closer cooperation between the V4 countries (Hungary, Poland, Slovakia, and the Czech Republic) in order to advocate regional interests more effectively as well as to counterbalance “Western liberal values” (Balogh et al., 2022; Scott, 2022). Regarding the enlargement of the EU, the government positioned itself as a strong supporter of the accession of the Western Balkans countries. This support was partly motivated by the desire to increase the number of potential allies within the EU, as most of these countries share some regional interests, show similar autocratic tendencies, and are socially more conservative than the (so-called) Western Member States. It was also motivated by a general desire to strengthen illiberal actors internationally. Following the

Russian aggression against Ukraine in 2014, the Hungarian government also positioned itself as a strong supporter of Ukraine's EU membership (Lamour, 2024). However, this changed after a controversial Ukrainian language law was passed, which limited the usage of the native language for minorities in several areas (such as education, health care, and social services), including the language use of the Hungarian minority in Ukraine (see, e.g., Venice Commission, 2019a, 2019b).

Due to the strengthening economic and political relations with Russia and the deteriorating relations with Ukraine and the EU leadership, the Hungarian government found itself in a precarious situation following the Russian invasion of Ukraine in 2022. Russo-Hungarian and Ukrainian-Hungarian relations that had primarily involved bilateral issues before, such as economic cooperation or disagreement about minority rights, now gained international salience and became increasingly seen as a political choice between the "Western" and "anti-Western" alliances. While Hungary joined the EU declarations condemning the war and supported the sanctions against Russia (e.g., Council of the EU, 2022a, 2022b), the government strongly criticized the same sanctions, which it labeled "the sanctions of Brussels," distancing itself from them. Governmental communication emphasized that the economic interests of Hungary should be prioritized, including interests related to energy security (cf., Lamour, 2024). At the same time, governmental communication avoided publicly condemning the Russian aggression (with the exception of signing the EU declarations) or even naming the aggressor, consistently referring to the war as a "Slavic internal war" (*belháború*) and demanding its prompt ending even at the price of Ukraine giving up parts of its territory. Relatedly, governmental communication strongly criticized Western weapon supplies to Ukraine, arguing that it would extend the war (i.e., by providing the opportunity for Ukraine to defend itself). The perceived pro-Russian position of Hungary also put a strain on the relations between the V4 countries, with the other three countries openly expressing support for Ukraine and condemning Russia.

METHOD

For the analysis, I used the geopolitics-related media contents of the Hungarian media corpus of the MEDEU project. I created this geopolitical sub-corpus by using the following 19 keywords: security council (*biztonsági tanács*), security policy (*biztonságpolitika*), embargo (*embargó*), energy security (*energiabiztonság*), UN Security Council (*ENSZ Biztonsági Tanács*),

geopolitics (*geopolitika*), NATO, national security (*nemzetbiztonság*), Russo-Ukrainian war (*orosz-ukrán háború*), Russo-Ukrainian conflict (*orosz-ukrán konfliktus*), Paks2, sanction (*szankció*), Ukraine (*Ukrajna*), the war in Ukraine (*ukrajnai háború*), Ukrainian conflict (*ukrán konfliktus*), Ukrainian-Russian war (*ukrán-orosz háború*), Ukrainian-Russian conflict (*ukrán-orosz konfliktus*), and V4, Visegrad countries (*visegrádi országok*). These searches resulted in a total of 4149 media items (online articles and transcripts of television programs) in my sub-corpus. Since analyzing such a large corpus with qualitative methods is not feasible, I took a random sample of 100 pieces of media content. Content that turned out to be irrelevant from a geopolitical perspective was again replaced by random sampling.

The MEDEU media corpus contains the contents of four pro-governmental (*origo.hu*, *magyarnemzet.hu*, M1, HírTv) and four government-critical/neutral (*nepszava.hu*, *hvg.hu*, ATV, RTL Klub) news media. Fifty-eight percent of the geopolitical sub-corpus comes from the pro-governmental media and 42 percent from the government-critical/neutral media. The 100 pieces of media content of my sample that I analyzed broadly adhered to these proportions (66 and 34 percent); the difference is primarily caused by filtering out non-relevant content and replacing it with random sampling (i.e., sampling not only from the contents of the news medium that was omitted). However, since the analysis is qualitative in nature and the analyzed sample is relatively large, it seems less likely that important geopolitical themes of the observed period were overlooked. This is supported by the fact that the sample covers all parts of the observed time period, somewhat over-representing the period following the start of the Russian invasion (59 percent of the sample comes from this time period, while its proportion is 42 percent in the geopolitical sub-corpus). Relevant parts of the 100 media items were first identified by thematic coding. During thematic coding, 36 codes and sub-codes were developed. I have used these identified parts in the subsequent analysis.

ANALYSIS

The investigated time period was divided into two parts according to the start of Russia's military invasion of Ukraine (February 24, 2022). In the first, longer period (July 1, 2021 – February 23, 2022), geopolitics-related media content was dominated by the issue of migration, the enlargement of the European Union, and the (assumed) divide between the “Eastern” and “Western” Member States. The second, shorter period (February 24 – March 31, 2022) was naturally

dominated by topics related to the Russian invasion, while topics of the previous period were also framed (or reframed) in light of this event. Simultaneously, the salience of geopolitics-related issues also increased: 42 percent of the media contents of the corpus come from this shorter period. Discourses were largely influenced in both (but in particular in the second) period by the election campaign preceding the April 3, 2022, general election in Hungary.

Main discourses before the start of the Russian invasion

From July 2021 until the start of the Russian invasion, the observed media content contained a wide range of geopolitics-related topics, including the enlargement of the EU (in particular in the Western Balkans), Europe's energy security, the question of migration and border security, the future of Europe (politically, geopolitically, culturally), cooperation among the V4 countries, the EU's Eastern Partnership, Hungary's "Eastern opening" policy, and the (assumed) division between the "Eastern" and "Western" EU Member States over the rule of law procedure and cultural differences. Most of the observed media contents were dominated by the Hungarian government's frames and narratives.

With regard to *migration and border security*, the dominant themes were the debate between Hungary and the European Union concerning refugee and migration policies and the Belarus-European Union border crisis. Since discourses related to migration have been widely discussed in the literature, we will only highlight a few points related to geopolitics here. The most important point is probably that governmental narratives framed migration from outside of Europe (in particular from the Middle East and North Africa) as a physical threat to Europe against which it had to defend itself.

The minister [Péter Szijjártó, the Hungarian minister of foreign affairs] argued that in order to keep Europe safe, we must stop the waves of migration. He warned that the withdrawal of NATO troops from Afghanistan posed a security challenge, which could make the country the source of new waves of mass migration. (...) He emphasized that in order to avoid new migration pressure, all open issues had to be solved with Turkey in relation to migration. The EU's "lines of defense" need to be strengthened – he added.² (origo.hu 2021.07.12)

2 The quotations presented in the paper were translated into English by the author.

These security concerns, together with the well-known older topoi of terrorism and cultural threat, became re-contextualized after the American withdrawal from Afghanistan had actually taken place:

Replying to a question, Viktor Orbán talked about the problem of migration. He emphasized that Europe should not risk its own culture because of migration and that terrorism interlinked with migration was a real threat, which he had been talking about for years. This is the situation with Afghanistan as well – he added. There should not be a situation when migration undermines the European project. About the relationship between demography and migration, he argued that the large masses of migrants put Europe’s cultural identity in danger. (origo.hu 2021.09.01)

In addition to these themes, the events in Afghanistan led to the re-emergence/intensification of the anti-Brussels narratives, which framed Brussels as incompetent, extremist, and dangerous to the future of Europe.

The [border] fence does not need to be strengthened, the fence is good and strong. It is possible that we will need more men, but we will ask for them then, and we will send them here. The weak point is Brussels. They say there that those who want to leave Afghanistan should be allowed to enter Europe. This is betrayal. Look, there are thousands of men working here [at the border]. There are thousands of men working here so that there, in the center of Europe, everyone can live in security, welfare, and comfort. And when these men here work so that migrants cannot come in, then to say from Brussels that they will bring in people from Afghanistan is a betrayal. (...) Those who want to bypass this fence to take in migrants to Europe betray the European men. Brussels is planning to do this, and we need to stop it. (M1, 2021.09.22, V4 news)

This excerpt demonstrates well that the limited number of alternative discourses (e.g., from the European Union or the domestic opposition) are mainly presented as part of the dominant governmental narrative and are framed accordingly.

With regard to the Belarus-European Union border crisis, the governmental position and the position of prominent EU politicians seem to be more in line (at least regarding the geopolitical aspect). The central argument here is that Europe is under a hybrid threat as, in addition to the migration pressure, the Belarusian government is strategically using irregular migrant flows against Europe.

Margaritis Schinas [the Greek EU Commissioner for Promoting the European Way of Life] told the Brussels portal [Politico] that “a new type of threat emerged at the borders of the European Union. This is a hybrid threat. Human suffering is used as a weapon against the European Union. We have to make the attackers understand that we will defend our borders. This has been successful so far. We have the resources and we can finance the efforts of member states to protect the borders, but this does not mean that we will finance the cement and stones which would be built into such a wall”- said the EU commissioner. (hvg.hu 2021.10.29)

Another key geopolitical theme in the observed time period was *the enlargement of the European Union*. The Hungarian Government presented itself as a strong supporter of the accession of the Western Balkans countries. The central argument was that the integration of the region was necessary to guarantee the security of Europe, while the lack of prompt action to integrate on the EU's part would lead to other geopolitical actors integrating the region. The government even argued for the immediate accession of Montenegro and Serbia. According to the governmental narrative, those Member States that do not support the region's accession (by trying to slow down the accession process) are making a serious strategic mistake. The government also envisioned the Western Balkans region as the next potential driver of economic growth in the EU. I did not find any alternative discourse or challenge to the governmental position regarding the Western Balkans in the media corpus.

According to Viktor Orbán, the Balkans should not be made a buffer zone but should be integrated into the EU. (...) “Until they [the prime ministers and presidents of the member states] decide that we need to integrate the Balkans, we will be part of a continuously postponed process that gets lost in the details, focuses on regulation issues instead of strategic questions, and are called negotiations but in fact are delaying tactics” – he warned (...) “If the peoples of the Balkans get a chance, they will catch up in a few years, just like the Visegrád countries did, they will strengthen their economies and the real great economic growth will arrive from the Balkans to the European Union.” (hvg.hu 2021.09.24)

In addition to the Western Balkans, the accession of Ukraine also occasionally came up in the observed corpus. The Hungarian government expressed support for the process but argued that the Western Balkans needed to be prioritized and

that Ukraine needed to respect the rights of national minorities (in particular, the rights of the ethnic Hungarian minority).

Another key geopolitical issue in the observed period was *the cooperation between the V4 countries*. The V4 group was present in the observed contents in at least four different ways: 1- as a form of economic and political cooperation; 2- as the “engine” of the EU economy; 3- in relation to the (assumed) differences from the Western Member States in terms of cultural identity, norms, and values; 4- in relation to differing approaches to energy policies (in particular, the opposition to the European “Green Deal” and against green policies in general). The last two points will be revisited as part of the other themes below.

The politician [Viktor Orbán] held a speech in Katowice, where he met his three Central-European colleagues as Hungary holds the presidency of the V4. He emphasized that low taxes help boost investment and the development of infrastructure, and this is one of the main goals of the Hungarian government for the next half a year as the head of the group. However, he still does not want to hear about the compulsory settlement of migrants. In his view, immigration is a security issue. He added that he expected respect and not public lecturing from the other member states as the four [the Visegrád group] represented significant economic power. He also argued that no one could tell Hungarians how they should raise their children. (nepszava.hu 2021.07.01)

The issues of *energy security* and *energy policy* were also present in the corpus, particularly related to Russian natural gas exports, renewable energy sources, and nuclear energy. The governmental narrative disseminated by pro-governmental media personnel (journalists and so-called experts) argued that Brussels and some Member States followed irrational anti-Russian positions, while Russia was, in fact, a respectable and reliable partner and energy provider and Russian gas combined with nuclear energy provided the key to the energy security of Hungary. The government contended that renewable energy sources did not provide (yet) a viable alternative, and the EU’s green policies were framed as irresponsible and as contributing to both energy insecurity and the drastic increase in prices. Related to the issue of renewables versus nuclear energy, there also seemed to be unity among members of the Visegrad group, while the attitude toward Russian natural gas was more divided, although this division was carefully avoided in the pro-governmental media.

Brussels still denies that it has responsibility for the surge in energy prices. (...) In the meanwhile, Brussels wants to introduce a so-called climate protection tax. The Vice-President of the European Commission, Frans Timmermans, would impose it on motorists, apartments, and family houses. This would cost 32,000 HUF [approx. 90 EUR] a month for the Hungarian people [per capita]. The Director of Communications of Fidesz argues that this is not only unacceptable but also hypocritical. Because the climate protection goal is just a charade. István Hollik said that the left supports Brussels' plan in vain as the government will not let it happen. "We will protect utility cost reductions and together with the V4 countries we will veto the plan of an EU-wide climate tax. Because we believe that the price of climate protection should not be paid by the European and the Hungarian people, but the large multinational companies destroying the climate." (M1 news 2021.10.17)

Commerce with Russia and, in particular, the procurement of Russian natural gas and the contract with *Rosatom* to build a second nuclear plant ("Paks2") have been challenged both by the domestic opposition and some international actors, arguing that this makes Hungary dependent on Russia.

The discourses related to the *future of Europe* involve a wide range of topics, including: 1- the struggle between competing visions of a federal Europe and a "union of nations" (i.e., primarily economic cooperation); 2- the struggle between competing cultural values ("traditional" versus "progressive" values); 3- relationships with other regions of the world, and 4- ultimately, the survival of the EU and "Europe." This last topic is mostly framed in cultural and racial/ethnic terms and in relation to migration.

Charles Michels talked about the creation of a geopolitical union. In his opinion, this was not a dream anymore but could become a reality soon since competition with the rest of the world could only be kept up this way, and this way, we could give effective answers to the challenges facing us. (...) Viktor Orbán, in reaction to this [another comment about the collapse of the Roman Empire], argued that historical parallels are important in general, but migrants are coming now, and currently, it is less relevant what happened to the Roman Empire, not to mention that the migrants are Muslims and they change the cultural character of Europe. Europe primarily needs economic success and not so much common policies – added the Hungarian prime minister. (origo.hu 2021.09.01)

Main discourses during the Russian invasion

From the start of the Russian invasion on February 24 until the end of the observed time period (March 31), the war dominated the geopolitics-related media discourses. The main topics related to European geopolitics were the (physical) security of Europe and the Eastern Member States; the energy and food security of Europe; the belongingness of Ukraine (and the Western Balkans) to Europe; questions concerning EU and NATO enlargement; and sanctions against Russia and their impact on Europe. Importantly, Hungary held a general election on April 3. Thus, the observed time period also overlapped with the most intensive part of the election campaign. The war itself soon became a central theme of the campaign.

The central message of the governmental communication was that Hungary needed to be kept out of the war to ensure the security of the Hungarian people and the energy security of the country. On the domestic level, they argued that the “left” (i.e., the united opposition) was acting irresponsibly by being “on the side of the war” (e.g., by wanting to send weapons or, assumedly, even troops to Ukraine). They also argued that such hasty politics would endanger the energy security (price levels and sufficient supply) of Hungarian households. The long-established tropes of the opposition being incompetent, dangerous, and serving the interest of Western leftist-liberal interest groups re-emerged and became reframed in the context of the war. Simultaneously, the long-established tropes of the dangerousness and incompetence of Brussels were also built upon.

In spite of intensively criticizing Brussels and the idea of Western sanctions against Russia, in the first days of the war (and even one or two days before it), Hungarian governmental politicians emphasized European unity and argued that Hungary would join with its allies (EU, NATO) in all decisions. For instance, Minister of Foreign Affairs Péter Szijjártó argued that:

The position of Hungary is clear: We support the sovereignty and territorial integrity of Ukraine, as we have always done, and we will not break up European unity related to the response, just as we have never done so. (hvg.hu 2022.02.23)

An interesting aspect of the pro-governmental media is that, in the first days of the war, they also presented pro-Russian positions and narratives, while later, they tried to balance Western narratives with more pragmatic techniques. For instance, in line with governmental communication, they referred to the events with the general and more neutral term “war in the neighborhood” without mentioning the Russian president or the fact that Russia had attacked Ukraine.

At the same time, they put significant emphasis on the assumed incompetence of Brussels and the Western powers in general (failure of Eastern policies, lack of power in preventing the war) and on the ineffective and dangerous nature of the sanctions. Pragmatism, criticism of the West, and even cynicism were characteristic of pro-governmental publicists and so-called media experts. For instance, the publicist of the pro-governmental *Magyar Nemzet* extensively mocked the German Green Party for agreeing to remove the full “blockade” of the Russian energy sector from the list of sanctions, a significant turn in the party’s energy policies.

They could decrease their cursed Putin- and Russophobia when it came to the question of how to heat or how to supply energy to their factories. Practice triumphed here over obscure ideologies which were built on the following: we are the good democrats who tell you how you should lead the country we cannot even position on a map. No doubt the United States has the best record at this so far, but the Germans believe in this as well. (magyarnemzet.hu 2022.03.22)

However, within a few weeks, Hungarian leaders clarified their position related to the sanctions and argued that no sanctions should involve a ban on the import of Russian fossil fuels. They emphasized that Hungary would not support any decision that endangered the energy security of the country.

She [Judit Varga, the Hungarian Minister of Justice] said that there was a war in the neighborhood of Hungary, and the position of the Hungarian government was clear, firm, and consistent: “We will not let anyone embroil Hungary into this armed conflict.” Judit Varga also mentioned that, according to the position of the government, sanctions against Russia cannot be extended to the area of energy policy “since we would endanger not only the energy security of Hungarian households but also the energy security and supply of the households of several other European countries.” Hungary will always be part of the united international action so long as it is about making peace. (origo.hu 2022.03.22)

The governmental narratives and discursive frames were widely disseminated by the pro-governmental media, publicists, and think tanks, while so-called experts in these media reinforced them by applying the exact same arguments and terminology as governmental communication. For example, in the excerpt below, the director of analysis of the pro-governmental think tank

Nézőpont Institute repeated the narrative and terminology of the governmental communication, while in the last sentence, it even seems as if he were talking in the name of the government.

It is obvious that those who ask for the extension of the sanctions are, in fact, suggesting that the price of the war in the neighborhood should be paid by the Hungarian people and Hungary. The left and Péter Márki-Zay [PM candidate of the united opposition in 2022] are even demanding sanctions that are weakening the Hungarian currency – said the director of analysis of Nézőpont Institute on M1. Those oppositional formations and Péter Márki-Zay and the united opposition, those who demand the introduction of different sanctions and, for instance, their extension to the energy sector, they create insecurity, just as do their ideas about weapon supply. Making the sanctions more brutal and extending them creates such an insecure climate that can obviously weaken the forint. The government, just as they have made it clear multiple times on Monday, will not support any measures that would endanger the energy supply of Hungary. (M1 news 2022.03.07)

The domestic political opposition could not create and/or successfully disseminate an alternative narrative with regard to security and energy policies, except for repeating multiple times that they would not send soldiers to Ukraine or otherwise get Hungary involved in the war (which was one of the most widely disseminated accusations in the election campaign). They also emphasized that they would not endanger the country's energy security, although they did not provide many details on how they would replace Russian energy sources. However, they did manage to construct an alternative narrative related to geopolitical relations and the place of Hungary within them. They framed the war and the related questions as a choice between the "East" and the "West" and emphasized that Hungary needed to belong to the latter. They argued that the events showed the failure of Orbán's "double game" and that Hungary needed to act together with its Western allies (EU, NATO), support every sanction, and even send weapons to Ukraine if needed. They also strongly criticized the "Eastern opening" policy of the Hungarian government. For instance, Anna Donáth, who was chair of the oppositional party Momentum at the time, said:

I believe that Europe took it seriously that we had to prepare for this [event], even if the Hungarian government was not always a partner in this. Even now we don't see anything else from the Hungarian government but that they are playing this double game. They would

like to remain good partners with Putin, and, of course, they have to be partners with Europe as well. (...) I can imagine that they blocked the process as long as they could. (...) I will only believe it if I see that Hungary supports the common European sanctions or calls Russia to account just as the Germans or the others do. Let's see when the Russian spy bank will be expelled, which was allowed in the country by the government itself, and when sanctions will be implemented against oligarchs and businessmen. (ATV 2022.02.22, Egyenes Beszéd [a daily political talk show])

Similarly, Ágnes Kunhalmi, who was co-chair of the Hungarian Socialist Party at the time, argued the following way:

According to her, the hypocrisy of Prime Minister Viktor Orbán is demonstrated well by the fact that in the first days of the war by Russia against Ukraine, the pro-Fidesz media, including MTVA [the official state media conglomerate] predicted "great Russian success," and now, when it turned out that even Orbán cannot make himself independent of NATO [positions], they are explaining his complete turnaround. (...) She emphasized that the state media, instead of fairly presenting opposition politicians, propagates lies. She recalled that they claimed about Péter Márki-Zay that he would send soldiers and weapons to Ukraine, which was a blatant lie. (nepszava.hu 2022.03.02)

Although the war dominated the media discourses during this time period, some other important themes were also present, mostly linked to the events of the war. First, a split among the V4 countries over Hungary's Russia policies was occasionally mentioned in the non-governmental media (although this discourse became more prevalent *after* the observed time period). Second, the discourses related to EU enlargement were extended with the issues of Ukraine and Georgia's EU membership, simultaneously with the possible enlargement of NATO with Ukraine, Finland, Sweden, and Georgia (Finland and Sweden since joined NATO in 2023 and 2024, respectively). These discourses were attached to the changed security situation of these countries as well as to the issues of the security of the Eastern EU Member States.

Finally, an election-related theme also came up occasionally: the assumption of governmental politicians and pro-governmental publicists that the Organization for Security and Co-operation in Europe (OSCE) would intervene in the Hungarian elections in favor of the united opposition and would present a politically motivated assessment of the elections. The following excerpt from an

essay written by the pro-governmental think tank *Századvég* is a good example of this.

The [current OSCE] report relies on the argumentative scheme of the Hungarian left and involves false claims regarding our election system. Consequently, we can assume that the final report of OSCE following the election will be biased and politically motivated and will be manifested in a preconceived judgment, which we are not willing to accept. The biased conclusions and unjustified accusations thus will not serve [the goal of] observation, which would be the official goal of the mission, but [will serve the goal of] interference in the democratic elections. (origo.hu 2022.03.29)

CONCLUSION

The paper has analyzed the geopolitics-related media content of the Hungarian media between July 2021 and March 2022 in the media corpus of the MEDEU project. We have shown that the observed time period may be divided into two parts: the longer period preceding the start of the Russian invasion of Ukraine on February 24, 2022, and a shorter period following this. In the first, nearly eight-month-long period, a wide range of geopolitical topics were observed, including EU enlargement in the Western Balkans, the questions of migration and border security, discourses related to the future of Europe, the cooperation between the V4 countries, the “Eastern opening” policy of Hungary, and the (assumed) divide between the “Eastern” and “Western” EU Member States due to the rule of law procedure and cultural differences. The second time period, lasting just a bit more than one month, was naturally dominated by the Russo-Ukrainian war, and older topics were reframed and reinterpreted in light of this event. Geopolitical perspectives also became more salient; nearly half of the contents of the geopolitical corpus were associated with this shorter period.

The analyzed media contents were dominated by the topoi, terminology, and frames of governmental communication: the pro-governmental media widely cited and reinforced them, including in opinion columns and via carefully selected (so-called) experts who used the exact same arguments and terminology as the government. The political opposition and the government-critical media could rarely create and/or disseminate their own narratives; they predominantly positioned themselves in relation to the governmental narratives (mostly opposing them) without being able to provide their own framing. One

notable exception was the reframing of the “Eastern opening” policy and the Russo-Ukrainian war as a choice between the “East” and the “West.” According to this framing, the government had chosen the “East,” while the opposition emphasized Hungary’s belongingness to the “West” and the importance of making political decisions accordingly.

Several governmental positions remained consistent over the observed time period and beyond, including the governmental perspective on migration and the Western Balkans enlargement of the EU. At the same time, cooperation between the V4 countries and the political and economic relations with Russia were severely impacted by the Russian invasion of Ukraine. Governmental communication and the pro-government media tried to downplay the rift within the V4 by mostly remaining silent about it, while the ambivalent relationship with Russia was evaded by redirecting the focus toward the assumed inability of the European Union to deal with the consequences of the war and emphasizing the negative impacts of the sanctions. This criticism largely drew on the terminology and discursive frames of the permanent anti-EU campaign that has been going on since 2010 and which is expected to be a defining feature of future Hungarian-EU relations in the short term. On the other hand, if relations with other V4 countries remain strained, governmental communication will need to reflect on this and present new alliances to remain consistent with its own image of showing initiative in representing Hungarian and regional interests within the EU.

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THE DISCURSIVE CONSTRUCTION OF THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN HUNGARY AND THE EUROPEAN UNION IN LIGHT OF ANTI-LGBTQ LEGISLATION

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ABSTRACT: *This paper investigates how the relationship between Hungary and the European Union, particularly regarding the diffusion of social norms and values, has been discursively constructed in the Hungarian media in relation to the adoption of Act LXXIX of 2021, frequently referred to as the “child protection Act” or “homophobic Act” in the Hungarian political and media discourse. The Act introduced stricter regulations aimed at protecting children from sexual exploitation and abuse while also restricting the dissemination of media content portraying sexual minorities, asserting that it is harmful to children. The adoption of the law intensified tensions between Hungary and the European Union, sparking discussion in the Hungarian media about the EU’s role in promoting LGBTQ rights among its Member States, as well as the specific relationship between the EU and Hungary. Therefore, this study focused on media content discussing the European Union and the new Hungarian anti-LGBTQ law. The analysis identified nine dominant discourses and found that anti-EU discourses connected to the Hungarian government called for weaker enforcement of the social norms and values enshrined in various EU documents, labeling the diffusion of such norms as external oppression and as the violation of national sovereignty. In contrast, only a few discourses advocated for the European Union to monitor, disseminate, and enforce the norms enshrined in its own founding documents more rigorously.*

KEYWORDS: *Hungary; European Union; Europeanization; LGBTQ; discourse analysis; media discourse*

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INTRODUCTION

This study explores how the relationship between Hungary and the European Union, especially the Europeanization process, was discursively constructed in the Hungarian media regarding the adoption of the so-called “child protection law” in 2021 and the related public referendum in 2022.

In the summer of 2021, the Hungarian Government introduced a bill initially aimed at imposing stricter penalties for pedophilia, to which amendments soon emerged on behalf of government politicians restricting the dissemination of media content portraying lesbian, gay, bisexual, transgender, and queer (henceforth LGBTQ) people. The adoption of Act LXXIX of 2021 was not the first measure taken recently by the Hungarian government that targeted LGBTQ individuals. However, it significantly intensified tensions between Hungary and the European Union since the EU contended that Hungary had violated several of its legal and social norms with this legislation, ultimately prompting the European Commission (henceforth EC) to initiate an infringement procedure against Hungary (EC, 2021).

At the same time, discussions about the European Union’s role in the diffusion of values and social norms, as well as its relationship with Hungary, have intensified in Hungarian media. The study relies on Europeanization theory and anti-gender discourse studies to understand how the Hungarian media and, through that, Hungarian political elites have conceptualized the role of the EU in the protection and promotion of LGBTQ rights in its Member States and the relationship between Hungary and the EU. To answer these questions, discourse analysis was conducted on 48 pieces of media content (news articles and television programs alike) from eight Hungarian media outlets published between July 1, 2021, and March 31, 2022; this period encompassed both the period after the adoption of the new Act and the campaign leading up to the Hungarian referendum held in relation to it. The media outlets thus selected represent both pro-government (*MI*, *Hír TV*, *Origo*, and *Magyar Nemzet*) and government-independent media (*RTL Klub*, *ATV*, *HVG*, and *Népszava*) and are also diverse in their formats.

In the following sections, the Hungarian context will be presented first, followed by the study’s conceptual framework. Then, after the description of the methodological approach, the discourses identified from the analyzed media content will be presented in detail. Finally, in the concluding remarks, the findings will be examined in the light of the conceptual framework thus presented and the Hungarian context.

THE HUNGARIAN CONTEXT

Since 2010, the Fidesz party (Fidesz - Hungarian Civic Alliance), along with the Christian Democratic People's Party (henceforth KDNP), has dominated the Hungarian Parliament, consistently securing supermajorities that allow for significant legislative influence. Scholars believe that Fidesz-KDNP's right-wing paternalist populism is fundamentally opposed to the meaningful representation of minority interests, including those of sexual minorities (Enyedi, 2016), and the right-wing populist party alliance has continuously argued that the equality of LGBTQ people is incompatible with Hungarian cultural and religious traditions. Among other activities, KDNP released a statement in 2008 claiming that the legislation introducing registered partnerships for same-sex couples was "an attack on families."² Viktor Orbán, leader of Fidesz and Prime Minister of Hungary since 2010, emphasized in one of his European Parliament speeches that he perceives the legal equality of LGBTQ people as incompatible with Hungary's religious roots (Orbán, 2013); in 2015, Orbán, in response to a journalist's question about his opinion on homophobia, thanked Hungarian homosexuals for "not acting provocatively, unlike LGBTQ people in Western countries," adding that although he considers Hungary a tolerant country, this only means that the majority population has patience towards LGBTQ people and not that the sexual minority should have equal rights (Fábián & Szilli, 2015). A few years later, in 2019, László Kövér, a member of Fidesz and Speaker of the Hungarian National Assembly, caused public outrage with a speech made at a European election campaign event where he compared child-rearing by same-sex parents to pedophilia and claimed that "A normal homosexual [...] does not necessarily consider themselves equal [to others]" (Dull, 2019). On top of these, the government-friendly public media has consistently provided space for anti-LGBTQ opinions and organizations (Tamássy, 2019).

The ruling parties' anti-LGBTQ stance showed up in legislation as well, as in 2011, the Hungarian parliament adopted a new constitution, the Fundamental Law of Hungary, with the almost exclusive support of Fidesz-KDNP, that defines marriage as a union between a man and a woman. With the Fundamental Law, the ruling parties de facto prohibited same-sex marriage, which was not legal before 2010 either but was not prohibited at a constitutional level. The curtailment of LGBTQ rights resumed in the spring of 2020 when Parliament prohibited the legal recognition of gender changes with the overwhelming support of Fidesz-KDNP politicians, ending legal acknowledgment for transgender and intersex

2 See <https://kdnf.hu/news/a-bejegyzett-elettarsi-kapcsolat-tamadas-a-csalad-ellen>. Retrieved: 2024.10.29.

individuals. In December 2020, Parliament amended the definition of family in the Fundamental Law to explicitly exclude same-sex couples from the concept. This amendment also asserted that “Hungary defends the right of children to identify with their birth gender and ensures their upbringing based on our nation’s constitutional identity and values rooted in our Christian culture” (Hungarian Fundamental Law, art. XVI, cl. 1). Additionally, Act CLXV of 2020 was enacted, reserving child adoption exclusively for married couples. This effectively banned child adoption for same-sex couples, who were not previously allowed to adopt as a couple, though individual members of such couples could adopt separately.

This wave of anti-LGBTQ legislation culminated in the latest anti-LGBTQ law to date, Act LXXIX of 2021, “on taking more severe action against pedophile offenders and amending certain Acts for the protection of children,” which was supposed to introduce child protection regulations concerning sexual exploitation and abuse³. Then, members of Fidesz proposed an amendment to the bill to ban or restrict minors’ access to content that “propagates or portrays” so-called “divergence from self-identity corresponding to sex at birth, sex change, or homosexuality.” The new Act, including this anti-LGBTQ amendment, was adopted on 15 June 2021. According to the Act, any media content depicting sexual minorities is classified as unsuitable for those under 18 and is to be distributed accordingly. The Act attracted nationwide and international criticism for suggesting a connection between sexual minorities and pedophilia and suggesting that the mere media representation of LGBTQ people poses a threat to children’s mental and sexual well-being. LGBTQ advocacy groups also criticized the Act for making LGBTQ-inclusive sex education in public education institutions quasi-impossible (Háttér Society, 2021), thereby limiting the access of LGBTQ students to comprehensive sexual health information and increasing their vulnerability to health risks.

The Fidesz-KDNP’s anti-LGBTQ actions have significantly impacted Hungary’s relations with the European Union, leading to explicit criticism from EU bodies toward Hungary, as the EU and its institutions have consistently developed directives and resolutions aimed at strengthening and broadening LGBTQ rights and condemning various forms of discrimination since the 1980s (Tóth, 2013). Following the enactment of Act LXXIX of 2021, many prominent European politicians and EU institutions condemned it, arguing that it discriminates against and stigmatizes LGBTQ people. Moreover, the EC launched an infringement procedure on 15 July 2021 against Hungary for

³ The manuscript of this article was submitted in November 2024, that is, before the 2025 amendment to the Fundamental Law of Hungary, which allows the ban of Budapest Pride.

violating, among other things, the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights concerning the fundamental rights of LGBTQ people – regarding human dignity, freedom of expression and information, the right to the respect of private life, and the right to non-discrimination, – and the free movement of services (EC, 2021). Additionally, at the end of September 2021, the European Parliament Committee on Civil Liberties, Justice and Home Affairs (LIBE) arrived in Hungary for three days to evaluate the rule of law in the country, including human rights and, thus, LGBTQ rights. The Committee then prepared a report in which it, in the name of the majority of the delegation, expressed “serious concerns about democracy, the rule of law and fundamental rights in Hungary” (LIBE, 2021, p. 29).

After the EC launched the infringement procedure, Viktor Orbán announced that the Hungarian government would initiate a so-called “child protection referendum” at the time of the upcoming Hungarian general election on 3 April 2022. Questions for the referendum concerned LGBTQ-inclusive sex education in public education institutions and the distribution of (media) content depicting LGBTQ people and gender-affirming care (for the referendum questions, see Appendix A). Subsequently, several Hungarian LGBTQ organizations and other human rights NGOs published a joint statement in which they emphasized that the referendum questions were formulated in an explicitly hostile tone and misleading manner and encouraged citizens to cast invalid votes.⁴

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

The relationship between developing and broadening LGBTQ rights and EU membership and candidacy in (Central) Eastern European post-communist countries has been researched extensively. Although it is known that the EU aims to promote various minority rights, including LGBTQ rights, in its candidate and member countries, the efficacy and impact of the instruments used to promote the broadening of such rights, as well as their possible shortcomings and negative effects, continue to be the subject of scientific inquiry and contest.

Scholars in the field often use Europeanization theory, which conceptualizes the construction, diffusion, and institutionalization of EU norms (Radaelli, 2003, p. 30) to model the effect of the EU and its institutions on broadening domestic

⁴ See <https://www.amnesty.hu/szavazzunk-ervenytelenul-a-kormany-kikozosito-nepszavazasan/>. Retrieved: 2024. 10.29.

LGBTQ rights in candidate and Member States.⁵ Specifically, they rely on two models of the Europeanization concept to grasp the process of transposing EU norms and regulations into domestic contexts: *external incentives* and *social learning* models (Schimmelfennig & Sedelmeier, 2005). The former basically refers to conditionality mechanisms, i.e., the European Union's practice of linking a state's accession to the Union to the formal transposition of EU legal norms into its domestic context. The conditionality mechanism has been assessed as effective to some extent in relation to adopting better legal frameworks for LGBTQ people in post-communist countries (Krizsan, 2009; O'Dwyer, 2013). However, as conditionality's leverage weakens after accession, the model has been characterized as unable to account for post-accession political and policy changes in the Member States (O'Dwyer, 2012, 2013; Pelz, 2014). Others note that adopting LGBTQ-friendly policies in post-communist member and candidate states might not positively affect social norms concerning LGBTQ persons either in society or among political elites (Krizsan, 2009; Pelz, 2014; Shevtsova, 2020). As such, external pressures might only tackle LGBTQ rights but not societal and political homophobia (O'Dwyer, 2013). Moreover, even in countries where political elites aim to meaningfully adhere to the EU's LGBTQ-related policy requirements, they may lack the resources necessary for enforcement (Krizsan, 2009).

The other frequently discussed model of Europeanization theory, social learning, refers to domestic political elites' internalization of so-called European norms and values through the candidate and Member States' continuing cooperation with each other and EU institutions and domestic non-governmental organizations' (in this case, LGBTQ and other human rights advocacy groups') transnational cooperation supported by EU institutions and mechanisms. In contrast to external incentives, the social learning process has a slow but long-term effect, which supposedly becomes stronger as time passes after a state accedes to the EU (O'Dwyer, 2012; Pelz, 2014; Schimmelfennig & Sedelmeier, 2005). However, social learning is more likely to positively affect LGBTQ-related social and political attitudes in settings where the EU norms in question do not conflict with domestic norms (O'Dwyer, 2012; Schimmelfennig & Sedelmeier, 2005). In Hungary's case, the external pressure stemming from the country's accession negotiations was preceded by "some equality thinking in Hungary since the mid-1990s" (Krizsan, 2009, p. 6) and endogenous LGBTQ-friendly societal developments (Forest, 2018, p. 133). However, the

⁵ See, among others, Krizsan's (2009) study in the Hungarian context, Forest's comparison regarding Croatia, Hungary, Slovenia, and Slovakia (2018); O'Dwyer's (2013) analysis of Poland; Shevtsova's study on Ukraine (2020), and Pelz's (2014) comparison of Estonia, Latvia, Montenegro, and Serbia.

legal framework adopted to adhere to the EU's LGBTQ-related norms did not lead to greater social acceptance of LGBTQ persons (Krizsan, 2009).

According to the models presented here, the EU accession of a country should lead to both a sound legal framework protecting LGBTQ rights (through conditionality) and greater acceptance of LGBTQ persons (through the social learning process). If any political backlash should arise, the social learning process ought to consolidate the legal frameworks protecting minority groups, including LGBTQ persons, and the commitment of political elites to support and promote minority rights in the long run after the accession of a country. O'Dwyer (2012) criticizes Europeanization theory for not only being unable to conceptualize the LGBTQ-related political changes in post-communist countries after their EU accession but also failing to account for political backlash and its implications for minority rights in these countries. The scholar understands the strengthening of Polish LGBTQ organizations and advocacy groups not as the outcome of the social learning process outlined in the Europeanization theory but as the outcome of the domestic political backlash following the adoption of some pieces of LGBTQ-related legislation in Poland to adhere to EU norms. As such, in O'Dwyer's (2012) reading, the EU's external incentives and, through these, the Polish domestic political backlash catalyzed LGBTQ and human rights advocacy groups. Others also conceptualize the rise of political homophobia and transphobia and, where it applies, state-funded homophobia and transphobia as domestic backlashes to the EU's and its institutions' promotion and protection of LGBTQ rights in EU member and candidate states (Forest, 2018; Pelz, 2014; Shevtsova, 2020).

Scholars who have analyzed the anti-gender discourse that emerged in the late 2000s and early 2010s conceptualize homophobic and transphobic discourses as key components of the transnational anti-gender political movement and its related discourse (Félix, 2015; Korolczuk & Graff, 2018; Kováts, 2022; Kováts & Pető, 2017). This movement and the associated discourse have local manifestations throughout the world (Korolczuk & Graff, 2018; Kováts & Pető, 2017), including in Hungary (Balogh, 2014; Félix, 2015; Kováts, 2022). In the context of anti-gender discourse, the terms "gender" and "gender ideology" encompass a wide range of phenomena. These include the promotion of gender mainstreaming, the promotion and expansion of reproductive rights, the (academic) use of the analytic concept of gender, the recognition and prevention of gender-based violence, and the protection and advancement of LGBTQ rights. Those opposing "gender ideology" or "genderism" typically reject or question these aspirations (Balogh, 2014; Korolczuk & Graff, 2018; Kováts, 2022). According to anti-gender rhetoric, "gender ideology" is being imposed on an "oppressed majority" by various international actors, including feminist movements, organizations like the United Nations and the European

Union, and concepts such as “the West,” “the gay lobby,” or “the LGBTQ lobby” (Félix, 2015; Korolczuk & Graff, 2018). This narrative portrays the anti-gender movement as a form of resistance to external forces that threaten national sovereignty (Kováts, 2022), grasped by some as the distorted adoption of colonialism theories into the anti-gender discourse (Korolczuk & Graff, 2018). Perceiving “gender ideology” as external oppression and an attempt to interfere in domestic affairs is a critical tenet of the anti-gender movement, distinguishing it from previous political backlashes against feminist and LGBTQ movements in post-communist countries (Korolczuk & Graff, 2018).

In the Hungarian context, scholars trace the emergence of anti-gender discourse back to 2008-2009, although noting that, at the time, the anti-gender discourse lacked an identifiable movement (Kováts & Pető, 2017). By the mid and late-2010s, the anti-gender discourse had accelerated with the support of Fidesz-KDNP politicians, (radical) right-wing media outlets, and members of the Hungarian clergy (Fodor, 2022; Kováts & Pető, 2017). Researchers perceive the emergence of the anti-gender discourse in Hungary, in line with the above-presented concept, as a domestic manifestation of a broader transnational trend (Félix, 2015; Kováts & Pető, 2017) rather than merely a political backlash against the diffusion of EU norms in the region. Hungarian findings regarding the use of the terms “gender” and “gender ideology” further strengthen international notions in that they conclude that the expressions are most often used to refer to issues relating to transgender people and somewhat to LGBTQ issues as well (Fodor, 2022; Kováts, 2022). Consequently, the recent wave of LGBTQ rights curtailment in Hungary, which began in 2020, can also be interpreted as part of this ongoing trend as the Fidesz-KDNP government initiated and supported the adoption of several pieces of anti-LGBTQ legislation, claiming that “gender ideology” poses a threat to Hungarian culture, national identity, and sovereignty (Kováts, 2022). The anti-EU stance is particularly pronounced in the Hungarian anti-gender discourse, which portrays any aspiration to protect or broaden LGBTQ rights as part of a foreign threat from which only the Hungarian government can provide protection (Fodor, 2022; Kováts, 2022).

The study resorts to discourse analysis to connect the two concepts formerly introduced. Discourse analysis, conceptualized as both a theoretical framework and methodological approach, fundamentally challenges the perception of language as merely a transparent medium or a neutral tool for accumulating knowledge about the so-called “real world” (Wetherell, 2001). Rather, it posits that discourse—comprising of language use and its related practices—is a social practice that plays a crucial role in constructing social reality (Fairclough & Wodak, 1997; Gee, 2010). This perspective implies that texts (in their broadest sense) do not simply describe

a phenomenon; they actively define and reshape it (Phillips & Hardy, 2002; Potter & Wetherell, 1987). Moreover, texts do not exist in isolation; their meanings are inherently contingent upon the contexts of their production and dissemination (Fairclough, 1992; Phillips & Hardy, 2002), as well as the broader socio-political and cultural environments from which they are interpreted (Reisigl, 2017). As such, discourse both constructs and influences social reality and is simultaneously shaped by it (Fairclough & Wodak, 1997). Consequently, a discourse analytic approach to media texts may shed light on how Hungary's relationship with the EU is constructed through the issue of LGBTQ rights.

METHODOLOGY

Considering the systematic changes in the Hungarian media landscape since 2010 (see Bajomi-Lázár, 2019; Mérték Médiaelemző Műhely, 2019; Szeidl & Szűcs, 2021), the study analyzes a diverse range of media outlets. The analysis includes four television channels: the public television channel *M1*, characterized by scholars as broadcasting pro-government views; the independent commercial channel *RTL Klub*,⁶ and *Hír TV* and *ATV*, two commercial news channels, the former often characterized as pro-government, the latter as independent; however, due to its changed ownership and tone, this is increasingly questioned by some (Bajomi-Lázár, 2019; Bátorfy & Urbán, 2020; Mérték Médiaelemző Műhely, 2021). Besides television channels, the corpus also includes articles from two dailies online and print versions, *Magyar Nemzet* (pro-government) and *Népszava* (independent), and two news sites, *hvg.hu* (independent) and *Origo* (pro-government) (Bátorfy & Urbán, 2020; Mérték Médiaelemző Műhely, 2021). As such, the analysis covers a broad spectrum of pro-government and independent media outlets and is diverse in terms of formats.

To analyze the EU-related media discourse touching on LGBTQ rights, we selected a time period for analysis around the Act LXXIX of 2021, which came into force on 8 July 2021, and the campaign leading up to the resulting public referendum held on April 3, 2022, thus collecting data between July 1, 2021, and March 31, 2022. Articles that discuss the EU's and Hungary's relationship in connection with LGBTQ rights were found with the help of keywords.

⁶ To increase comparability, the fact that RTL Klub primarily broadcasts entertainment programs not necessarily containing political opinions or content was taken into account; hence, only these two channels' main evening news programs were included in the corpus.

Namely, first, EU-related content was selected from the previously listed media outlets based on whether they contained at least one of the following Hungarian keywords: *Európai Unió* (“European Union”), *EU*, *Brüsszel* (“Brussels”), *Európai Parlament* (“European Parliament”), *Európai Bizottság* (“European Commission”) and *Európai Tanács* (“European Council”). Second, to find articles that discussed LGBTQ rights, keywords were selected for their central role in the public debate around the anti-LGBTQ law and the referendum; these were *család* (“family”), *családvédelem* (“protection of families”), *gender*, *genderlobbi* (“gender lobby”), *gyermekvédelem* (“child protection”), *homoszexuális* (“homosexual”), *LMBT** (“LGBT*”), *meleglobbi* (“gay lobby”), *pedofil* (“pedophile”), and *pedofiltörvény* (“pedophile Act”). The two selection steps identified 1328 articles. A randomized selection process was used to achieve a more manageable sub-corpus suitable for manual analysis (Krippendorff, 2019), considering the articles’ relevancy to the focus of the study and their distribution across media and publication date. This resulted in 48 articles, six from each selected media outlet.

The study applies discourse analysis that focuses on four main angles of EU and LGBT-related media discourse: 1. what views on Europeanization are represented in the media articles under analysis; 2. what views on the future of the EU and Europeanization appear in this media content; 3. what symbolic factors appear in articles to legitimize or delegitimize Europeanization, and in relation to this, the equality of LGBTQ people, and how are these discursively constructed in the articles; and finally 4. what pragmatic factors are represented in the material that legitimize or delegitimize Europeanization and, in relation to that, the equality of LGBTQ people, and how are these discursively constructed in the media content under analysis.

To analyze these four main angles, the study relies on Foucault’s (1991) framework of discourse analysis, which examines the characteristics of producing and disseminating discourses through five aspects, i.e., the limits and forms of *sayable*, *conservation*, *memory*, *reactivation*, and *appropriation*. These focus on sayable and unsayable things in discourse, prevalent and circled and repressed and disappeared discourses, discourses accepted as valid or invalid, reactivated previous discourses and their transformations, and the individuals or groups competing to dominate and control the discourse(s) in question, respectively (Foucault, 1991, pp. 59–60). The data was approached with an inductive coding strategy, and articles were coded using NVivo, focusing on the Foucauldian aspects of the four previously defined main angles of analysis.

DOMINANT DISCOURSES CONCERNING LGBTQ RIGHTS AND THE EUROPEAN UNION

Pro-EU and neutral discourses

In all identified pro-EU or neutral discourses, there is a clear understanding of the hierarchy between the EU and Hungary: Hungary should not give up its sovereignty but should respect and obey the EU's norms and rulings. Namely, none of these discourses suggests a change in the status quo between Hungary and the EU; indeed, this is portrayed almost as a given, and, apart from very few exceptions, nor do they argue for a federal Europe. Articles engaged in these discourses emphasize that the EU institutions' calls to repeal Act LXXIX of 2021 should be respected and blame Viktor Orbán and his political party for the possibility of retorts.

Human rights discourse

In this discourse, Act LXXIX of 2021, its possible effects on Hungarian LGBTQ people, and the pragmatic issues concerning its enforcement are in the limelight. Articles engaging in this discourse generally explicitly condemn the Act and the ruling parties responsible for it while implicitly or explicitly cherishing the EU's reaction. Nevertheless, the reports mostly focus on domestic affairs instead of the European political context.

The EU and its institutions are portrayed positively, framing the EC's launching of an infringement procedure as a legitimate and even necessary step to protect Hungarian and, thus, European and LGBTQ people and their human rights. According to the discourse, the Commission is "doing its job" when evaluating laws in EU member countries. The discourse incorporates the argument that LGBTQ media content does not "turn" children LGBTQ, nor is it harmful to anyone.

This argumentation and the general pro-EU stance of this discourse are reflected in the wording journalists use. For example, they often refer to the legislation as "the homophobic Act" or as "the so-called child protection Act." Additionally, there is a noticeable journalistic and editorial choice of predominantly quoting EU and Hungarian officials and NGO spokespeople who criticize or condemn the Act. The quoted or interviewed Hungarian and EU representatives, along with Western European political leaders, NGO spokespeople, Hungarian political analysts, and other experts, frequently explicitly criticized the new Act

for discriminating against LGBTQ individuals and violating EU legal norms. Moreover, some even expressed support for the EC's outrage regarding the Act, hoping that the EU's response would lead to its repeal.

The following quote, broadcasted under the lead "Right and left MEPs alike called the so-called anti-pedophile law a disgrace in the European Parliament today" in RTL Klub's main evening news program, exemplifies some of these journalistic approaches.

*"The protection of children from pedophilia is a common goal, but the legitimate public interest cannot be a pretext for introducing provisions that discriminate against groups that are minorities in terms of sexual identity and gender orientation," – said the Commission's vice-president, who said the so-called pedophile law could also have an impact on EU funding. "What kind of society is it where the government wants to determine who you love?" – asked a member of the biggest, the People's Party group, to which Fidesz also belonged months ago.*⁷ (RTL Klub, 2021a)⁸

Furthermore, the rule of law mechanism and the EC's infringement procedure frequently appear together in the discourse. They are portrayed as rightful and necessary steps by the EU against Hungary for violating LGBTQ rights, regardless that many EU officials, such as Vera Jourová, vice president of the EC, stated that the rule of law mechanism assesses the state of democracy in general and not the new Act (Hungary Today, 2021).

The pragmatic factor present in the discourse regarding Europeanization concerns the EU's role and duty in protecting its citizens' rights, in this case, the human rights of LGBTQ persons. Namely, the European Union's duty to enforce the norms and values enshrined in the Lisbon Treaty and the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights in its Member States.

Symbolic arguments in support of the EU and its response revolve around the importance of protecting and promoting human rights and equality. Another, although less frequently appearing, symbolic factor was the linking of

⁷ All translations from Hungarian are the Author's own.

⁸ " » A gyerekek védelme a pedofiliától közös cél, a jogos közérdek azonban nem lehet ürügy olyan rendelkezések bevezetéséhez, amelyek hátrányos megkülönböztetést jelentenek a szexuális identitásukban, nemi orientációjukban kisebbségnek számító csoportoknak « - jelentette ki az Európai Bizottság alelnöke, aki szerint az uniós támogatások kifizetésére is hatása lehet az úgynevezett pedofil törvénynek. »Milyen társadalom az, ahol a kormány akarja meghatározni, hogy az ember kit szeressen? « - tette fel a kérdést a legnagyobb, a néppárti frakció tagja, ahová hónapokkal ezelőtt még a Fidesz is tartozott."

Europeanness and being part of a broader European community to supporting LGBTQ people and their rights. Concerning this aspect, the adoption of an anti-LGBTQ Act drove Hungary away from the European community and European norms.

Therefore, the EU is positioned as both an institution that enforces legal norms and as a broader community that promotes specific social norms and values that Member States, especially their political actors, should internalize and represent.

Economic law discourse

Though less frequently, an economic law discourse also appeared in the articles analyzed. This discourse, allowing space for EU-neutral positions, shifted away from arguments centered on human rights and instead emphasized the consequences of the new Act for the flow of economic goods between EU borders. As such, the discourse both provided a pragmatic context for interpreting the new legislation and contained a direct, pragmatic reason for repealing Act LXXIX of 2021. The discourse emphasized that, according to EU regulations, the free flow of products, including media content, must be guaranteed across EU borders; it also pointed out that as the new Act contradicts this principle, it violates the EU's economic laws.

Quotes from EU institutions and politicians were frequently used to convey this discourse.

The President of the European Commission called the so-called pedophile Act a disgrace this summer. In July, the body launched an infringement procedure because it believes the law violates both content providers and trade directives by restricting the distribution of certain publications while also assessing the law as discriminatory. (RTL Klub, 2021b)⁹

In the discourse, the EU is portrayed merely as an international organization protecting its and each of its Member States' economic interests, and to do so, it has to enforce its economic regulations in each of its Member States. As such,

⁹ "Szégyennek nevezte az úgynevezett pedofil törvényt nyáron az Európai Bizottság elnöke. A testület júliusban kötelezettségzegési eljárást indított, mert álláspontjuk szerint a tartalomszolgáltatókat és a kereskedelmi irányelveket is sérti a törvény azzal, hogy bizonyos kiadványok terjesztését korlátozza, és diszkriminatívna is tartják a törvényt."

the discourse ignores symbolic and moral arguments and focuses only on the legal matters over which the EU has authority.

Distraction

The third pro-EU/neutral discourse interprets the adoption of Act LXXIX of 2021 and the pro-government media's increased attention to the EU, its institutions, and politicians' reactions to the new legislation as only a government strategy intended to distract the public from other political scandals occurring in the same year, such as the so-called Pegasus scandal and the Fudan University scandal. As such, it is more focused on Hungarian domestic affairs. The following quote from the independent daily *Népszava*, which refers to the independent think tank Political Capital in interpreting the government's anti-LGBTQ legislation and the subsequent referendum, exemplifies this discourse.

Political Capital believes that the government is trying to take back the initiative with the LGBTQ issue after several topics that cast a negative light on the government were put on the agenda. First, the Fudan issue made bigger waves than expected; now, the Pegasus scandal has embarrassed the government, while the period ahead was supposed to be about the opposition's primaries. The government is trying to put all of these things behind with the referendum. (Czene, 2021)¹⁰

Regarding how LGBTQ issues affect the relationship between Hungary and the EU, the discourse posits that the EU and its institutions are not particularly invested in promoting LGBTQ rights in Hungary but aim to enforce the rule of law in Hungary. That is, media outlets engaging in this discourse argued that even though the EU condemns the government's anti-LGBTQ legislation and the related homophobic political discourse, the rule of law mechanism is due to the deterioration of democracy, lack of rule of law and adequate anti-corruption measures, not value or moral-based reasons, i.e., the "ideological reasons" of enforcing human rights for LGBTQ people.

Two main pragmatic aspects emerged in the discourse regarding the EU. First, the EU is portrayed as a legitimate and objective institution that can rightly and

10 "A Political Capital is úgy látja, hogy a kormány az LMBTQ-témával próbálja visszavenni a kezdeményezést, miután több, számára kellemetlen téma került napirendre. Először a Fudan-ügy vert a vártnál nagyobb hullámokat, most a Pegasus-botrány hozta kínos helyzetbe a kormányt, az előttünk álló időszak pedig az ellenzéki előválasztásról szólt volna. A népszavazási kezdeményezéssel igyekszik a kormány ezek mindegyikét zárójelbe tenni."

correctly judge the state of democracy and the misuse of EU funds in Hungary. Second, the EU has the right to withhold funds if its Member States, in this case, Hungary, do not fulfill their legal requirements.

Concerning symbolic factors, the human rights angle appears in the discourse only as collateral damage in the government's attempt to cover up its non-rule-of-law-compatible operation. As such, the EU's role in enforcing particular social norms and values in its Member States is secondary to its duty to monitor the rule of law and state of democracy in the Member States.

Janus-faced power demonstration

This discourse focuses on the Hungarian government's, and specifically Viktor Orbán's, relationship with the EU rather than the EU's role in domestic or European politics.

In this discourse, the government's adoption of Act LXXIX of 2021, the subsequent referendum, and the anti-LGBTQ political discourse around these are only political tools in domestic politics. That is, the new Act and the associated state-funded homophobic discourse are conceptualized as Fidesz-KDNP's campaign tools, deployed to gain voter support in the upcoming general elections by whipping up social homophobia in the name of child protection. This discourse reflects the anti-gender discourse formerly presented, so much so that the following quote from Péter Balázs, the late Minister for Foreign Affairs, on a television program on ATV, compares the government's focus on LGBTQ issues to the political discourse in Russia and Poland, thus interpreting the domestic campaign as the local manifestation of a transnational trend.

Péter Balázs: It [the new Act] is about him [Viktor Orbán] searching for and finding another piece of ammunition for next spring's elections. Since Soros has got old and [the] migrant [issue is] out of sight, Brussels somehow had to be cast in a new enemy role. They [Fidesz] now have invented this role for it [Brussels]. As I said, this is the Russian model that the Poles also use. (ATV, 2021)¹¹

¹¹ "Balázs Péter: Arról van szó, hogy ő egy újabb municiót talált, keresett és talált a jövő tavaszi választásokhoz. Ugye Soros megöregedett, a migránsok nem láthatók, és Brüsszelt valahogy egy új ellenszerepbe kellett beállítani. Most ezt a szerepet találták ki neki. Mondom, ez azért orosz minta és a lengyelek is alkalmazzák."

Considering the new Act's impact on the relationship between the EU and the Hungarian government, those employing this discourse argue that the Hungarian government, particularly Viktor Orbán, capitalizes on these arguments with the EU. Namely, such incidents can be framed as a battle in domestic public discourse. The 'Janus-face' of the discourse lies in the notion that while in Hungary Viktor Orbán portrays himself as a freedom fighter who singlehandedly teaches manners to the EU, in the EU and foreign media, he mostly escapes accountability by arguing that the new Act only applies to children and that Hungary still protects the rights of adult LGBTQ people. As such, those engaging in the discourse continuously emphasize this ambiguity of the Hungarian Prime Minister's discourse, portraying himself as a relentless fighter against Brussels' oppression in the Hungarian media and, at the same time, a harmless and misunderstood protector of LGBTQ rights in the EU.

Anti-EU discourses

Although to different degrees, all of the Hungarian pro-government and anti-EU discourses revolve around a David-Goliath theme: a gigantic, strong oppressor, i.e., Brussels or the EU, is trying to control European countries and violate their sovereignty. According to this view, the Hungarian government is protecting so-called "traditional Hungarian values" and even posing as the custodian of "real" European values.

This overarching political narrative questions the concept of the EU as a community with shared values and social norms. It portrays the EU's goals of enforcing minority rights not as a legal or human rights issue but as a purely ideological one. Thus, it delegitimizes the EU's role in the diffusion of European social norms and values, presenting it as purely ideological external oppression. As such, sovereignty is a key concept in these discourses, entangling pragmatic and identity factors. In pragmatic terms, sovereignty is interpreted as questioning and delegitimizing the superiority of EU law over Hungarian law. As a symbolic factor, sovereignty refers to the notion that Brussels, as an abstract political entity, should not have the authority to tell Hungarian people how to live their lives and cannot force them to change their values and norms.

Journalistic methods employed to convey this discourse include quoting government officials and pro-government "experts" without providing any counterpoint to their views and the repetition of the government's narratives and arguments as *facts*.

Denial

The discourse of denial was dominant in pro-government media in the first few weeks when the EC began to criticize the adoption of the new Act.

Two main arguments dominated the discourse. First, Fidesz-KDNP officials, pro-government public figures, and journalists argued that EU politicians and bureaucrats were attacking the Hungarian government, or as frequently put in the discourse, the “Hungarian people,” because they had not actually read the new Act. Some even suggested that EU officials were having difficulty understanding or interpreting the Act. Second, the Act had been misunderstood, and the Hungarian government and the Act were being falsely accused of being homophobic. The latter argument was frequently underpinned by downplaying the discriminatory parts of the Act, for example, claiming that the Act only applies to those under 18 and, therefore, does not affect LGBTQ adults in any way or emphasizing that the Act’s main target is pedophiles and not sexual minorities.

In this discourse, the EU’s proposed retaliatory measures were portrayed as an exaggerated and disproportionate response to what was perceived as a misunderstanding. This narrative implicitly delegitimized the Europeanization process by relying on the pragmatic notion that the EU is not capable of objectively evaluating the laws enacted in its Member States.

Parents’ rights

In this discourse, Fidesz-KDNP politicians and the pro-government media argued that the new Act only strengthens parents’ right to decide what is taught to their children. They also claimed that the EU does not respect parents’ rights when urging the repeal of the legislation. Consequently, the governing parties and the media outlets supporting them portrayed the governing parties, especially Viktor Orbán, as fighting for parent’s rights to decide what is taught to their kids. The following excerpt from the pro-government public television channel MI’s evening news program, quoting Máté Kocsis Fidesz MP, exemplifies this discourse.

Through children’s books, advertisements, and various Internet platforms, minors are bombarded with propaganda that we think they should be kept away from because it is only the parents’ right to decide on their children’s education regarding this matter. It is up to the

parents to decide which direction they want their children to take, but only they can decide. (MI, 2022)¹²

Furthermore, the discourse changed noticeably throughout the period under analysis. What started as the argument that the Act is “ensuring parents’ right to decide,” with the “collateral damage” of LGBTQ rights’ erosion transformed into a pronounced anti-LGBTQ discourse dehumanizing LGBTQ individuals, portraying the EU as wanting to strip parents of their rights, and LGBTQ activists and so-called “LGBTQ propaganda” as posing an explicit threat to children. In this later phase of the discourse, pedophiles are rarely even mentioned; the focus instead shifted to “LGBTQ propaganda” and LGBTQ activists who supposedly pose harm to children’s development.

The phrase “we will not let them into our kindergartens and schools” became the core of the discourse, where “them” referred to both LGBTQ persons and organizations and, figuratively, the EU and Brussels, who are portrayed as aiming to interfere in Hungarian parents’ private decisions.

The discourse does not engage with meaningful pragmatic aspects of the relationship between Hungary and Brussels but portrays the relationship as a battlefield where Brussels sides with “gay propaganda,” which poses a threat to the healthy development of children. Legal aspects, such as the Lisbon Treaty and the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights, are not considered. Instead, symbolic aspects concerning the “ideology-fueled” imposition of “Western values” dominate the discourse.

The people’s will

This discourse appeals to the idea that the Hungarian government represents the opinion of the Hungarian people and is also the protector of the “oppressed majority” around Europe. According to this discourse, people in Hungary and all over Europe are fed up with the values and social norms that “Brussels ideologists” constantly try to force on them, and the Fidesz-KDNP government is the only political force that actually cares about and represents the will of “the people.” As part of the discourse, Fidesz-KDNP politicians often state that by questioning the legitimacy of the adopted Act, the EU is questioning

12 “Mesekönyvek, reklámok, az internet különböző felületein olyan propaganda árad a kiskorúakra, amitől azt gondoljuk, hogy őket távol kell tartani, mert kizárólag a szülőknek a joga, hogy ezirányú neveléséről döntsenek a gyerekeknek. Az, hogy melyik szülő milyen irányba tereli a gyerekeit, az már a szíve joga, de kizárólag ő dönthet.”

the legitimacy of elected Hungarian representatives and intends to override Hungarian voters' decisions regarding their own political representation.

The idea of Fidesz-KDNP having political allies in their crusade strengthened in the discourse after the LIBE Committee's visit when two visiting EU officials called the LIBE visit a witch-hunt, its only goal being to punish Hungary for its conservative views. They also stated that democracy is strong in Hungary and that the Hungarian government should not be punished for the new Act or any other reason. Relying on these two politicians' opinions, pro-government media concluded that even Western politicians and people are fed up with the EU's enforcement of liberal values. Therefore, the Hungarian government is not only fighting for the Hungarian people but is also one of the last bastions of traditional European values.

The following quote from the pro-government daily and online news portal *Magyar Nemzet* represents this discourse, in which "true Germans," i.e., "national sovereigntist conservatives," reject the values implicitly promoted by EU officials who otherwise look down on and threaten everyone who "thinks differently."

Von der Leyen and her Brussels colleagues, hovering in a rainbow bubble and scorning, lecturing, and threatening those who think differently about European values, human rights, migration, racism (such as the far-left BLM's anti-white and anti-Christian racism), the aggressive and destructive LGBTQ network and the ultra-liberal stormtroopers, should think about which side they are on. On the side of the internationalist socialists – including the new German "cultural philosopher" Aydan Özoguz – or on the side of the national sovereigntist conservatives, Christian democrats, and true Germans? Either – or: there is no third way. (Faggyas, 2021)¹³

13 "A szivárványos buborékban lebegő, az európai értékekről, emberi jogokról, migrációról, rasszizmusról (például a szélsőbaloldali BLM fehér- és keresztényellenes rasszizmusáról), az agresszív és destruktív LMBTQ-hálózatról és az ultraliberális rohamosztagokról másként gondolkodókat lenéző, kioktató és fenyegető Von der Leyennek és brüsszeli társainak el kellene gondolkozniuk, melyik oldalon állnak. Az internacionalista szocialisták – köztük az újnómet „kultúrfilozófus” Aydan Özoguz –, vagy pedig a nemzeti szuverenista konzervatívok, kereszténydemokraták és az igazi németek oldalán? Vagy-vagy, nincs harmadik út.”

Moral superiority

This anti-EU discourse is best grasped as incorporating the view that the government is on high moral ground compared to the EU and representing the issue of child protection and LGBTQ rights as a zero-sum game.

The discourse incorporates the argument that the EU favors gay rights instead of children's rights and puts LGBTQ lobbyists before innocent children by trying to make the government repeal the Act, just as with the parents' rights discourse. However, in this discourse, another aspect is emphasized: the EU is "morally corrupt" for supporting so-called LGBTQ propaganda instead of protecting young, innocent children. Since the Hungarian government puts kids first, protecting them and their families, it is morally superior to the EU. It is noteworthy that the argument involves a zero-sum game logic, depicting the promotion and protection of children's rights and LGBTQ rights as inherently conflicting, as shown in the following excerpt from M1.

Judit Varga [then Minister of Justice for Hungary] highlighted that an unprecedented campaign has been launched against Hungary because our country considers the protection of children more important than the LGBTQ lobby. (M1, 2021)¹⁴

Furthermore, with a somewhat twisted logic, the discourse posits that the government had successfully solved the issue posed by the zero-sum logic, as it had put children first but did not sanction adults and their private lives. Consequently, Hungary is performing better at protecting minority groups' rights than the EU as it has managed to resolve the contradiction between children's rights and LGBTQ rights (a "contradiction" that the Hungarian government introduced in this discourse), which makes "us" Hungarians "even more European" than the EU.

This discourse further strengthens the Hungarian government's moral superiority by portraying the legal case of an MEP as characteristic of the EU as a whole. Cyrus Engerer, who proposed the draft resolution in which the European Parliament condemned the new Act, was found guilty by the Maltese Court for distributing pornographic pictures of his former partner as revenge. Media outlets engaging in this discourse frequently mentioned that the MEP in question is gay, implying that his sexual orientation bears a relation to his felony, further strengthening the link between homosexuality, pornography, and

14 "Varga Judit arra hívta fel a figyelmet, hogy eddig soha nem látott hadjárat indult Magyarországon ellen, mert hazánk a gyermekek védelmét fontosabbnak tartja az LMBTQ lobbival."

crimes, which were already present in the discourse. The pro-government media used this case to emphasize that the Hungarian government is morally superior to the EU.

As a pragmatic factor, the discourse involves the government's criticism of Europeanization, arguing that the EU does not satisfyingly protect children's rights and that the Hungarian Act serves children better than other EU laws. However, the symbolic element is much more dominant in explicitly stating that the Hungarian government and, thus, Hungarian people who voted for them, are morally superior to EU bureaucrats and that generally no one, but specifically morally questionable people (who would choose LGBTQ rights "instead" of children's rights, for example) can impede the Hungarian legal system.

Ideology-based punishment

The most prevalent anti-EU discourse initially centered around the claim that Hungarian politicians tried to negotiate with EU bureaucrats and help them understand the Act and the will of the Hungarian people, but the "left-liberal bureaucrats" instead chose to attack Hungary, disguising their ideology-based attack as human rights reservations and an impartial assessment of the rule of law in Hungary. According to this discourse, the circle of those attacking Hungary for ideological reasons, i.e., merely due to the country's right-wing government promoting traditional Christian values, ranges from George Soros, international human rights and LGBTQ organizations, and the "LGBTQ lobby" through the EU to the Hungarian opposition.

The infringement procedure and the rule of law mechanism are continuously mixed up in the discourse, and the argument that the EU is punishing Hungary for the new Act is used for both. Therefore, it is not addressed anywhere in the discourse that the rule of law mechanism was separate from the infringement procedure. The rule of law mechanism is addressed through two strategies in the discourse. First, in claiming that the only reason EU institutions support the rule of law mechanism against Hungary is the adoption of the new Act, which they condemn on ideological bases either because, for Brussels, LGBTQ rights are more important than the protection of kids or because Hungary has a conservative ruling party. Second, through admitting that the rule of law mechanism targets corruption but claiming that opposition politicians are the ones who violate the EU's rules and engage in corruption.

There are no pragmatic reasons present in the discourse concerning why the EU/Brussels would pick on Hungary particularly. Instead, it is emphasized that Brussels tries to push its (LGBTQ) values and norms on the Member States and

attacks Hungary because it does not bow to this so-called “left-liberal ideology” but stays a conservative country, which Brussels, as the external oppressor, cannot stand. The portrayal of the EU is sometimes refined by pushing the responsibility onto LGBTQ advocacy groups and the so-called “gay lobby” and claiming that these organizations are behind the EU’s “attack on Hungary,” suggesting that the EU’s wrongdoing is that it gave in to pressure from these international organizations.

In the following excerpt, which contains a condensed example of this discourse, the Hungarian pro-government public television channel M1 is quoting Balázs Szolomayer, lead analyst of the *Center for Fundamental Rights*, a pro-government think tank.

[Balázs Szolomayer:] They [LGBTQ and other human rights organizations] are deliberately trying to make the Hungarian government look bad, and the reason behind this is that Hungary is now run by a right-wing government, a conservative government, which is contrary to their ideological views. (M1, 2021)¹⁵

Moreover, the discourse also connects the EU’s response to the new Act to the Hungarian domestic political landscape, implying that there is an alliance between Brussels and the Hungarian opposition parties, which aims to prevent the government from protecting children from pedophiles and LGBTQ content. It portrays the Hungarian opposition as aiming to “sell” the country to “the West” and give up any traditional, Christian, Hungarian values. The discourse appeals to the idea that Brussels and the EU aim to use Hungarian opposition parties and politicians to overthrow the legitimate Hungarian government due to its conservative Christian views instead of left-liberal ones.

As part of the discourse, attention is also drawn to the ambiguity of the EU’s interpretation of human rights, claiming that Brussels only cares about human rights and the rule of law when it concerns certain groups, like sexual minorities, but does not care about discrimination when its victims are conservative and catholic groups or are victims of political groups that the EU favors.

In this discourse, the Member States criticizing the Hungarian Act are portrayed as the “declining West,” where the abnormal is the new normal, and traditional values are supposedly penalized. In contrast, Hungary is portrayed as a country protecting its traditional, Christian-conservative values; as an “island

15 “Tudatosan próbálják rossz színben feltüntetni a magyar kormányt, és ennek az áll a háttérében, hogy egy jobboldali kormány vezeti ma Magyarországot, egy konzervatív kormány, amely ellentétes az ő ideológiai nézeteikkel.”

of sanity” in the decaying left-liberal European Union, for which it is punished by Brussels. As such, the interpretation of the Hungarian Act transformed it into a means of self-protection intended to defend the country’s Christian-conservative values from fast-spreading and aggressively propagated “deviances” such as “LGBTQ propaganda.” This is a shift in the sense that initially, the Hungarian government deemed the Act per se necessary, but later, the Act transformed into a reaction to already existing so-called “gay propaganda” or “LGBTQ ideology” that Brussels forces on the Member States.

CONCLUSION

The nine identified discourses are mainly fragmented among the media outlets. Government-related anti-EU discourses appeared in both pro-government and independent media outlets, while neutral and pro-EU discourses appeared only in independent media outlets, demonstrating that they represent more diverse voices in the public discourse. However, EU-critical discourses independent of the government’s political discourse did not emerge in the period under analysis. A possible explanation is that the strong connection of EU criticism to the governing parties, Fidesz and KDNP, and their radical right-wing satellite, the Mi Hazánk party, in the polarized Hungarian public and media discourse led to the exclusion and abandonment of EU-critical political voices independent of the government.

The analysis showed that the pro-government media, in its prevalent and anti-EU discourses, opted for a strong anti-LGBTQ discourse as well, portraying the EU as enforcing its social norms and values on its Member States against the will of European people and traditional and conservative values. Although public media services, such as M1, have distanced themselves from the topics of sexual and gender minorities and their equality (see, for example, Tamássy, 2019) in the last few years, the turn in the government’s and, thus, pro-government media’s communication is striking as the identified discourses construct LGBTQ identities and national identity as mutually exclusive.

Regarding the discourses’ stance on Europeanization, anti-EU discourses connected to the Hungarian government explicitly called for the weaker enforcement of social norms and values enshrined in various EU documents, labeling such attempts to diffuse these norms as “external oppression” and as a “violation of national sovereignty.” In contrast, only a few discourses called for the need for the European Union to monitor, disseminate, and enforce more rigorously the norms enshrined in its own founding documents. In the polarized

Hungarian media discourse around the adoption of Act LXXIX of 2021 and the EU's response to it, pragmatic factors often intertwined with symbolic ones regarding the evaluation of the Europeanization process or even disappeared because mere symbolic aspects heavily dominated the discourses.

The identified discourses support the conceptualization of the governments' recent anti-LGBTQ discourse as part of the transnational anti-gender movement because the anti-EU discourses, even if intertwined, are imbued with the characteristics of the anti-gender discourse as identified by Korolczuk and Graff (2018), and especially the characteristics of the Hungarian local manifestation of the anti-gender discourse identified by, among others, Kováts (2022), Kováts and Pető (2017), Félix (2015) and Balogh (2014). So much so that even some who engaged in pro-EU discourse emphasized that the Hungarian government's homophobic discourse and anti-LGBTQ legislation is part of a greater transnational trend also present in Russia and Poland. These findings further strengthen the crucial role of international bodies, such as the EU, in the anti-gender discourse. They underpin that the way discourses interpreted Hungary's relationship with the European Union and the representation of European values was decisive in its assessment of and attitude toward LGBTQ rights. Whether the 2020-2021 wave of anti-LGBTQ policies has strengthened domestic LGBTQ movements in the long term is for the future to tell.

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APPENDIX

Questions in the so-called ‘child protection’ referendum held on 3 April 2022.

- *Do you support children in public schools participating in classes that demonstrate sexual orientations without parental consent?*
- *Do you support information about gender change treatments being given to children?*
- *Do you support media content of a sexual nature and affecting the development of children being presented to them without any restrictions?*
- *Do you support media content presenting gender change being presented to children?*

Source: <https://abouthungary.hu/news-in-brief/parliament-votes-to-hold-referendum-on-hungarys-child-protection-law>

CLIMATE CRISIS, HUNGARY AND THE EU: IS THERE A UNIQUE CONSERVATIVE APPROACH TO CLIMATE CHANGE? A CASE STUDY ON THE MEDIA DISCOURSE INVOLVING CLIMATE CHANGE AND ENERGY POLICY

ANNA VANC SÓ¹

ABSTRACT: *This study investigates the dominant discourses concerning the climate crisis and climate and energy policy as they are interpreted in the context of the European Union within Hungarian news media from July 1, 2021, to March 31, 2022. Applying content and discourse analysis methodologies, we identified and interpreted key discourses emphasizing Hungary's positioning within both EU and global contexts. Our findings show that climate change is not associated with a distinctive and autonomous discursive framework. Instead, it is predominantly embedded within dominant narratives reflecting the current government's stance, specifically its criticism of the European Union. This critique often alleges the process of diminishing the role of nation-states and favoring a federalistic EU approach within EU decision-making processes. These findings align with prior research indicating that climate change discourses in Hungary exhibit parallels with global narratives but are primarily reframed within pre-existing dominant discourses.*

KEYWORDS: *climate change, climate crisis, energy policy, EU*

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INTRODUCTION

Recently, climate change has become a dominant, overarching problem around the globe, shaping the relationship between numerous actors on various levels. This study examines the dominant discourses surrounding the climate crisis and climate and energy policy related to the European Union within Hungarian news media. The objective is to analyze the various perspectives through which the EU is interpreted in these discourses and contextualize the findings within broader EU-related narratives. The analysis is based on the media contents of the Hungarian media corpus of the Horizon 2020 project MEDIATIZED EU – Mediatized Discourses on Europeanization and Their Representations in Public Perceptions.

The discourse on the climate crisis in connection with the European Union (EU) has a peripheral position in Hungarian news media. It is often loosely attached to wider narratives addressing Hungary's role within the international community or integrated into discourses on migration, family dynamics, or the broader future of Europe. Therefore, through the analysis of the interpretation of climate crisis and energy policy, a deeper and more complex image can be formed about the position of the country on a national, European, and global scale.

To obtain a clear interpretation of this relationship through the discourses of the news media, it is essential to briefly introduce the complex relationship between Hungary and the EU and the main dimensions of conflicts with a special focus on climate change and energy policy.

CONTEXTUAL BACKGROUND

Hungary in the EU

The relationship between Hungary and the European Union since Hungary's accession in 2004 has been complex and shaped by both pragmatic and ideological differences. While Hungary and the EU share some main goals—such as enhancing Europe's economic strength—their visions for achieving these objectives often contradict. These tensions have become more pronounced since 2010, following the electoral victory of the current Hungarian government, led by Prime Minister Viktor Orbán.

A key source of conflict lies in the weakening of democratic institutions within Hungary. Scholars have described the political system in various ways, reflecting on this erosion of democratic characteristics. Terms such as “populist democracy” (Pappas, 2014), “deconsolidation of democracy” (Brusis, 2016, p. 272), “simulated democracy” (Lengyel & Ilonszki, 2012), and how PM Viktor Orbán also defines it, “illiberal democracy” (Rupnik, 2012; Bozóki, 2015, p. 4; Enyedi, 2016, p. 218; Buzogány, 2020), highlight the perceived shift toward hybrid governance. Critical perspectives also describe Hungary’s system as a “hybrid regime, a mix of democratic and autocratic practices” (Ádám & Bozóki, 2016, p. 105). The government’s reaction to this criticism centers on the disagreement associated with several key issues such as migration policy, external relations, and, recently, climate strategy – issues which are all based on allegedly core differences concerning the future of the EU as a federalist structure instead of prioritizing the sovereignty of nation-states. There are, therefore, strong ideological and pragmatic differences. While the EU seeks to enhance the norms of liberal democracy, Hungary highlights an illiberal democracy with conservative Christianity-based values as the foundation of the future of Hungary. The current political system has found various allies inside the EU over the previous twenty years, mainly among the V4 countries. Moreover, strong bilateral relations have also been established around specific political issues, such as the relationship between Hungary and France, which is strengthened through their common understanding of nuclear energy as a clean and climate-friendly energy source.

Energy and Climate Policy in the EU Context

The situation with energy and climate policy further exemplifies the complexities of Hungary-EU relations. As highlighted by Osička et al. (2018), energy policy remains a particularly sensitive issue for many Central and Eastern European (CEE) countries, including Hungary. These states are mostly dependent on fossil fuels and have a complex and dependent energy relationship with Russia, which became more complicated with the Russo-Ukrainian War considering the EU sanctions and the hastening of the energy market liberation policies of the EU (Zuk et al., 2023). However, the energy sector is differently structured in these countries regarding the role of state ownership and the diverse types and mixtures of energy, making them even more vulnerable to these changes (Zapletalová & Komínková, 2020). Therefore, in these countries, the discourse on climate change and energy policy is strongly related to the current discourse about sovereignty represented by populist political parties that

“ally with climate skeptic positions and impede the green transition in the name of a supposed national interest” (Paris, 2020, p. 20; Vanderheiden, 2020, p. 184).

A contemporary approach to the climate crisis in Hungary

Since 2010, when the Fidesz-CDP coalition gained power, the issue of climate change has been pushed back, and the government abolished the independent Ministry of Environment and the Ombudsman for Future Generations. However, by the end of the 2010s, when climate change became a central political topic in the EU, but most importantly, Hungarian society became more conscious, environmental organizations were born, found their voice, and had growing and visible power in the public sphere; climate change became the top concern and fear of Hungarian youth (Bíró-Nagy & Szabó, 2021) and the government could no longer reject this problem. As a result, it became a political issue that shaped a climate and environmental protection action plan for 2020. All this led to a unique, conservative green approach to the environment, which “rests in the belief that only local solutions, not vague, unenforceable global commitments, will lead to effective improvements in environmental protection”² (2020.01.27. Judit Varga, Politico). Previous research distinguishes three approaches to climate change by right-wing populist parties in northern countries: climate denial, climate nationalism, and climate conservatism. According to Mikecz and his colleagues (2023), the governmental approach seems to best match the climate-nationalist approach because it focuses on local solutions and nation-based decision-making processes.

The main topics dealt with by this conservative approach, however, share similarities with globally urgent climate issues – questions of energy policy, pollution, etc. – but also construct a special discursive framework in harmony with the main governmental discourses on an international level, namely, those of national sovereignty and the important position of nations with regard to every global question; the narrative of “protection” – of families, Hungarian people, culture, etc. – and the importance of eastern economic relations. Moreover, it may seem like a national characteristic, but discussing climate change as a “threat to national sovereignty,” a “plot by global elite groups,” and transforming a scientific debate into a political one on an ideological level and highlighting the unequal effect of actions taken to counter climate change on people living in poverty on a structural level is typical in the discourses of conservative politicians and right-wing populist parties around the world. (Zuk, 2020; Forchtner, 2015, 2018)

2 <https://www.politico.eu/article/christian-conservative-green-policy/>

Previous research results and their application

Sociological research on climate change in Hungary has been relatively limited, with studies primarily focusing on two key areas: 1) the perceptions of youth regarding climate change as a dominant issue and future threat (Bíró-Nagy & Szabó, 2021) and 2) the position of climate movements within the Hungarian public sphere (Geró et al., 2023; Mikecz, 2017). The intersection of these two research strands was identified in a study conducted by Vochocová and colleagues (2023), who examined the online media representation of the Fridays for Future movement, comparing the Czech Republic and Hungary. The results concerning Hungary showed that climate activist youths are not taken seriously, and minors are criticized for lacking enough knowledge concerning climate issues, in parallel with critiques of their parents for letting “kids” into the field of politics (Vochocová et al., 2023). This discourse fits into the governmental narrative about protecting youth and kids in every domain.

In a more recent study, Mikecz and colleagues (2023) analyzed the media framing of climate change within the context of populist political discourse in Hungary. Their comprehensive literature review identified dominant framing strategies, which were then examined related to the Hungarian media discourse. The results showed that the Hungarian media framing follows a conservative approach embedded in the actual dominant governmental discourse rather than the international framework of the conservative climate approach.

For the present analysis, we have considered this framework, particularly emphasizing the frames related to the European Union. However, we kept in mind that our database is not limited to right-wing populist discourses and that frame analysis differs from qualitative content and discourse analysis. Therefore, these frames are investigated as integrated elements of certain discourses, not separate entities.

METHODS AND DATA

It is important to note that the media market is asymmetrically polarized in Hungary (Bátorfy & Urbán, 2020; Urbán, 2022; Lengyel et al., 2021); it is distorted by the state. Public service media regularly spread government propaganda while independent media outlets struggle for their existence. Due to the strong interrelation between politics and the media, political opinions and discourses are clearly identifiable in online media and show a dualistic “pros and cons” system with weak and marginalized alternative discourses. The media

framing of climate change is embedded in this system of discourses in which the main topics are dictated by the government's communication strategy. This situation had an impact on the data collection and analysis.

For the climate change topic, we used additional keywords in the pre-existing corpus: climate (*climate crisis, climate protection, climate tax*), *energy policy (energetics)*, and environment (*environmental protection*). The final database (Table 1), after cleaning for relevance and balancing the massive weight of governmental interpretations, consisted of 100 units.

Table 1. Database used in the analysis

Media Outlets	Abbreviated name	Type	Political position (pro-government: G; government-critical: C; Neutral: N)	Number of analyzed articles
Magyar Televízió Esti Híradó, V4 Híradó, Unió27	M1	Television	G	13
RTL Klub Esti Híradó, Fókusz	RTL	Television	N	3
Magyar Nemzet, magyarnemzet.hu	MN	Newspaper/ Newspaper online	G	29
Népszava, nepszava.hu	NSZ	Newspaper/ Newspaper online	C	10
Heti Világgazdaság, hvg.hu	HVG	Newspaper online	C	9
origo.hu	ORIGO	Newspaper online	G	21
ATV Egyenes beszéd	ATV	Television	C	5
Hír TV Híradó, Csörte	HÍR TV	Television	G	10

Source: MEDEU Research, authors' compilation

We employed a combination of qualitative content analysis and discourse analysis methodologies to examine the integration of the climate change topic within the context of the European Union (EU). The first is valuable for exploring both explicit (frequency of words, topics, references to actors, institutions) as well as implicit meanings (emotions, context, etc.) (Mayring 2014). These characteristics make content analysis useful for analyzing discourses in the public sphere (Krippendorff, 2018). The second considers language not only as a means of communication but also as a form of social practice in terms of both reflecting and creating social reality (Gee, 2014; Fairclough, 2013).

Discourse analysis investigates this role in maintaining or changing certain social structures and power relations (van Dijk, 2011) by emphasizing unfolding ideologies and the power structures behind them.

As part of a comparative research project within the EU, qualitative content analysis supported the creation of concrete and comparable findings regarding key actors, institutions, and prevailing topics in news media discussions about the European Union. Simultaneously, discourse analysis offered advanced insights into the positioning of these characteristics and the use of pragmatic and symbolic argumentation by reflecting on distinct social and political contexts across the studied countries.

Events during the period of analysis

In the analyzed period, four events shaped the discourse on climate change and energy policy in relation to the EU in the Hungarian news media. During the summer of 2021, a novel national consultation campaign started dealing with “Life after the epidemic,” mostly focusing on economic decisions and incorporating a statement concerning climate change, the Global Climate Summit (COP26) in Glasgow, Planet Budapest 2021 Sustainability Expo and Summit³, and the outbreak of the Ukrainian-Russian war at the end of the period in February 2022.

The relevance of the national consultation requires further brief explanation as it is strongly related to the issues of democracy and national sovereignty discourses in the country. National consultations have served as unique deliberative practices since the 2000s in Hungary, initiated by Fidesz (in opposition at the time), ostensibly to highlight the importance of listening to and reflecting on Hungarian people’s voices. However, these consultations are now criticized as they have become simple instruments intended to strengthen the party’s position and mobilize people, including their supporters, while they have lost their deliberative function (Pócza & Oross, 2022). They include no questions but only politically constructed statements followed by the binary answer options “agree” or “do not agree.” In this context, the statement was the following: *“Brussels wants to impose new taxes on us to make Hungarian families pay for the costs of pollution and climate change caused by multinational corporations*

³ Planet Budapest is a ‘local’ Central European trade-fair intended to be a platform for discussing climate issues with experts, decision-makers and companies. It aims to call attention to climate change and represents a possibility for a number of professional exhibitors from the Visegrad countries to introduce technological developments, innovative products and services concerning climate change.

through higher utility bills.” This event significantly influenced the discursive framing of climate change during the initial three months, exemplifying the key role of political communication in shaping the narratives presented by the pro-governmental news media.

Dominant discourses

The dominant discourses presented in the analyzed news media are the following: *the discourse of protection the discourse of responsibility, the discourse of the anti-global versus global dichotomy, the discourse of ideology vs. reality, and the discourse of the weakness and legitimacy of the EU.*

Among these, the *discourse of protection* and the *discourse on responsibility* are central discursive frameworks employed by the Hungarian government across a wide spectrum of political issues. While the discourse on *protection* is crucial but has no specific actors in the case of climate change discussions (the same people and political action are to be protected as in many other governmental discourses), the *discourse of responsibility* plays a prominent role in discussions surrounding climate change, involving actors of the political opposition and numerous sub-discourses.

The discourse of anti-global versus global dichotomy also appears as a recurring theme in various political contexts; in the case of climate change and energy policy, this dichotomy is particularly significant. It highlights the global nature of climate change and the supranational character of European Union (EU) solutions related to climate change and their effect on policy-making processes.

The EU is frequently criticized by the Hungarian government for being driven by ideological frameworks, particularly those associated with liberal ideologies. In contrast, the Hungarian government positions itself as grounded in pragmatism, reacting based on social and economic reality. This discursive framework, *Ideology vs Reality*, plays a critical role in shaping climate-related discourse in the EU context, confronting ideology, politics, and science.

Furthermore, in the context of the EU’s approach to climate issues, several critics have noted the balance between national sovereignty and federalist structures. These debates are part of a broad critique regarding the *weakness and legitimacy of the EU*. While the sovereignty-federalism discourse is present in the previous discourses as well, it assumes a distinct logic in relation to the EU’s authority, thereby creating a separate discourse in the analysis.

Discourse of responsibility

One of the main challenges associated with climate change is finding easily targetable actors responsible for it since the whole globe is involved and affected by it. Therefore, the discourse of responsibility is, per se, a discourse on the externalization of responsibility, too. This discourse is one of the most common types in this area and can be identified in almost all the analyzed content in some form. The question of responsibility is connected to the debate on the future of Europe, the position of sovereign nations in the fight against climate change, the role of local-global actors and actions, the responsibility of everyday people, politicians, power actors, and so on. We focus on the most dominant sub-discourses in the context of the EU. For several years, the discourse on the externalization of responsibility has been present in Hungarian political communication mainly in case of global issues such as migration (Melegh et al., 2019) and economic processes but also concerning international relations, including the relationship between Hungary and the EU (Sata, 2023). This means that external – non-national, non-governmental – actors are the ones to be blamed for the difficulties the nation is facing. There are several positions (questions) related to this discourse: (1) who is responsible for climate change? (2) Who is responsible for acting against climate change, and on what level? And (3) who should *not* have to take responsibility?

Most articles we analyzed deal with the complicated relationship between Hungary and the EU concerning the climate issue. However, the media reflection on the Climate Summit (COP26) in Glasgow changed the narrative about the position of the European Union on the global climate issue.

Climate protection is typically a story in which even the EU is a small fish. So, this is something that can only be solved globally. The fact that we agree on anything here at a European level or that we push or screw up has very little relevance. The biggest players here are in Asia, the biggest polluters. (RTL, 2021. 11. 16.)

and after the COP26 event:

At the same time, the EU again failed to play a decisive role and could not contribute to the North-South rapprochement, the “big players” being the US, China, India, and other countries. (MN, 2021. 11. 17.)

The Hungarian government seems to systematically underestimate everyone's potential contribution at all societal levels in Europe concerning direct action

against climate change. The European Commission is strongly criticized for its ideological position to lead the world in the fight against climate change. However, it has no actual power to force anyone outside the EU to act; it only regulates and gives direction to its members. This is also part of the process of externalization on a different scale, associated with no actual solutions or ideas for acting.

In the case of climate change, three main actors are named as the perpetrators in political communication represented in the news media. Two of them are global actors.

- big companies should shoulder responsibility

The cost of a climate-neutral economy should primarily be borne by the climate wreckers – the large polluting countries and large companies. (Origo, 2021. 05. 25.)

- countries with high emissions are responsible for climate change

The European Union is responsible for around 8% of global emissions, and as its emissions continue to fall, those of other developing countries are increasing dramatically. This share will continue to fall significantly in the coming years and decades. (M1, 2022. 02. 01.)

These two sub-discourses are typical anti-globalization discourses – not part of anti-EU discourse – since neither the European Union nor Hungary is found to be responsible for the situation. First, this seems to contrast with the unique governmental “externalization of responsibility” discourse about migration (Melegh et al., 2021), involving blaming Brussels for the crisis in 2015, but it fits well with the anti-globalization discourse concerning migration in general. This approach to climate change is pragmatic by pointing to actors while avoiding responsibility.

- Brussels is blamed for overemphasizing the need for climate consciousness

The third actor to be blamed is the EU. Criticism often centers on Brussels –not for causing the climate crisis itself, but for its energy policies and their alleged contribution to rising inflation, thus contributing to another form of crisis, the energy crisis. These issues are frequently framed within the broader discourse of combating climate change. Two dominant arguments emphasize Brussels’ role in climate-related matters. The first focuses on interpreting why Brussels

is advocating for a specific approach to addressing climate change, which is further elaborated in the discourse on the *EU's weakness and legitimacy*.

The second argument – discussed in this section – emphasizes Brussels' role as an educator and leader in fostering environmental awareness and promoting sustainable practices among its Member States.

I see that in the European Union, and particularly in the narrative of the European institutions of the European Commission, there is a very strong narrative that they are a kind of climate bully of the world, setting an example for other big regions... Certainly, it [the EU] doesn't dictate the pace, but it has been an important reference point for Europe for the last two thousand years, and it can and should be perceived as such, so I think that this kind of guidance as an intention is important. (HírTV, 2022. 01. 10.)

This perspective also reflects the global positioning of the EU, which seeks to act as a leader in climate policy. However, the EU is challenged to have a tangible influence on actors outside its borders due to its relatively limited cultural and economic weight. At the same time, the EU places substantial pressure on its Member States to comply with ambitious climate policies.

There is a marginal sub-discourse related to Brussels's responsibility, involving stressing the voting membership of Hungary in the EU in contrast to positioning the country as an external actor.

- Those who bear the public burden and those who should not be responsible

While the primary governmental discourses center on identifying those with responsibility, an alternative perspective emphasizes the shared burden of addressing these challenges. This view acknowledges the unequal circumstances among nations and societies while recognizing that all individuals and countries bear some level of responsibility for the future of the planet. Timmermans is quoted in one of the articles:

Climate is everyone's business: it's not always a question of who's responsible but of what the public spending should be, not in the same way [for all countries/actors], of course. (MN, 2021. 12. 09.)

Discussion of the responsibility of all is represented only by the political opposition in highlighting the following:

The EU climate plans, climate targets, explicitly put a lot of emphasis on the social dimension [...] There is a mechanism for a just transition and, within that, a fair transition fund. So, the EU has a very strong political will and a strong set of measures and financial frameworks specifically designed to ensure that climate transition is not an unbearable burden for people. (ATV, 2022. 01. 06.)

A marginal discourse exists regarding the potentially positive effects of climate change in relation to addressing social inequalities – a perspective systematically absent from the dominant climate change discourses in Hungary. The latter's dominant discourses fail to address specific social groups based on their economic status; instead, they focus primarily on families and refer to them by the number of children they have.

The former approach was mentioned only occasionally, primarily by members of the political opposition, such as Benedek Jávor, a former Member of the European Parliament and an expert in environmental law.

The green turn is not a luxury for the rich but a chance for the poor to catch up. (NSZ, 2022. 01. 11.)

One of the most dominant narratives in global climate crisis discussions arises in relation to the tension between individual and collective responsibilities. However, this narrative is largely absent from the Hungarian discourse. While the political opposition tries to introduce this perspective, it is often labeled a “green ideology” and criticized for allegedly opposing the interests of Hungarian families. The dominant governmental narrative interprets families as the smallest social unit. However, their responsibility – both as those who contribute to climate change and as actors who can combat climate change – is not acknowledged. Instead, families are portrayed as passive entities that require protection. This passive interpretation aligns with the broader governmental narrative that positions the state as the primary protector of its citizens, reinforcing its role as a guardian rather than engaging citizens as active participants.

There is an interesting dichotomy concerning the attitude to protecting families or degrading the role of individuals, as the governmental framing also introduces a conservative approach to climate change based on local and individual actions.

While the liberals virtually eliminate the responsibility of individuals by empowering supranational institutions, the conservative side thinks in terms of a local solution: the role and the attitude of the individual.
(MN, 2021. 11. 30.)

Meanwhile, in the dominant governmental discourse, people and individuals cannot be “educated” or dictated to and should not be told to shoulder responsibility for the issue of climate change.

The discourse on responsibility is complex, with several actors and sub-discourses, yet the majority of the latter share one common element: anyone can be responsible for climate change or for poorly managing the topic – except for local actors and everyday citizens.

Discourse of protection – the securitization of families and Hungarian households

The discourse on protection is essentially related to the *discourse on responsibility* as the other side of the coin, namely, who is responsible for protection and who needs to be protected, as previously referred to.

Since the migration crisis, the issue of protection has dominated Hungarian political discourse. This includes the protection of people from migrants (Szalai, 2016), Christianity from liberalism (Vancsó, 2020; Sata, 2023), children from “LGBTQ+ propaganda” (Gera, 2023), and the nation from the effects of war. In each case, Hungarian families—or the concept of family—are positioned as the central target of protection (Sata, 2014), albeit from different perspectives.

The discourse on protecting families is also important concerning climate change, as the latter is alleged to enhance generational conflict and destroy traditional family structures and the future of youth. As Viktor Orbán said in an interview in 2019, “*The family protection action plan offers Hungarian people unprecedented support and an opportunity to plan for their future*” (Origo, 2019. 02. 10; Viktor Orbán Prime Minister announces the family protection program).

Protection happens on both ideological and economic levels. Concerning the topic of growing inflation and energy policy, overhead reductions are one of the keys to protecting Hungarian families, which are being targeted by Brussels, and since the economic regression and even the start of the war in Ukraine, the topic is strongly connected to the topic of climate change.

The “policy of artificial price increases in Brussels” must be suspended because until the effects of the war have passed, families cannot be exposed to a three to four-fold increase in energy prices. Let us stop this process now, let us suspend it, let Brussels stop raising energy prices, and then suddenly, the price of energy will be affordable, or at least more manageable. (NSZ, 2022. 03. 27., based on an interview on Kossuth Radio with the Viktor Orbán).

This governmental discourse on the protection of families is part of the discourse on national sovereignty from many perspectives. Who has the right to decide about the concept of families or the conditions of how people live, or how to make economic decisions on topics such as overhead reductions, even more so when they are related to global issues such as the climate crisis?

According to Prime Minister Viktor Orbán, energy prices had already started to rise; the war just added to this, but in fact, energy prices are rising in Europe because the EU is raising prices.

The European Commission is saying that the way to protect the climate is to force people to use as little energy as possible, so they are raising energy prices centrally every year. [...] And I don't think that the European Commission should raise the costs for families and try to force households to change their lives. (NSZ, 2022. 03. 27., based on an interview on Kossuth Radio)

and

According to Judit Varga, Hungary's performance in the fight against climate change is exemplary, as, in addition to our environmental protection measures, we have managed to defend the overhead reductions and the sovereignty of the Hungarian economy. (HÍR TV, 2021. 11. 03.)

This is closely related to the sub-discourse about who should not be responsible for climate change but from a protection point of view. The “overhead reduction scheme” is a Hungarian “invention”; not only should Hungarian people be protected from EU decisions, but such initiatives as well.

Discourse on the anti-global/global dichotomy

We need to act globally and locally; global action can be made effective through nation-state action. (NSZ, 2021. 11. 30.)

The global-local dichotomy is strongly embedded in the discourse of responsibility within climate policy. While the global nature of climate issues often leads to the externalization of responsibility, the associated discourse frequently emphasizes local and regional roles without directly addressing the concept of responsibility.

The crucial role of local decision-making and actions associated with addressing climate issues is positively emphasized in almost all the analyzed articles when it appears, albeit with and without any specificities or actual examples. Pro-government news media highlight the necessity of developing unique, nation-specific energy policies tailored to each country's distinct characteristics. The narrative suggests that localized approaches are essentially linked to anti-globalization discourses, positing that the local cannot exist independently of opposition to global frameworks.

As the global character of energy policies cannot be overlooked, the discourses emphasize the necessity of enhancing international cooperation. However, the proposed solutions tend to favor bilateral agreements or alignments with nations that share a critical stance about Brussels' climate policies, such as the members of the Visegrád Group (V4) or France. In these debates, climate change is often treated as only a contextual issue, subject to the priorities of economic decision-making and international relations. This dynamic reflects the dominance of pragmatic political considerations over environmental needs, revealing the broader tension between ideology and practical realities in Hungary's approach to the climate crisis.

Counter-arguments also enhance the special characteristics of the country while calling attention to the importance of unified action in case of this global crisis. The general negative approach to anything "global" is part of the pro-governmental narrative that stresses that global action cannot exist without local/national level action⁴; that global is in opposition to local/national; that global forces and processes are "suspicious" (as in the governmental discourse, global refers to "the global elite," and that the leaders of Brussels are part of this group of people). "National" and "local" mean anti-global, which is definitely counter

⁴ 'Local' is sometimes the synonym of national, but in a V4 context, it also means Central-Eastern European.

to the intentions of the European Union, who only “exacerbate problems.” In this global/anti-global discourse, the European Commission and its climate policy are sort of a global enemy that is systematically destroying “local” communities/nations’ own energy sources; these processes make the different countries unequally vulnerable. Meanwhile, the issue of global dependence on nationally supported forms of energy sources – in the case of Hungary, nuclear energy or gas, for example – seems to be no more than an economic decision to keep energy costs as low as possible.

In this discourse, the importance of protecting “sacred land,” or as Mikecz and colleagues put in their framework, “the idealization of the natural landscape,” is present, connected to the political landscape of the region, referring to V4 countries and the Carpathian Basin.

If we cannot solve these issues globally, we will not be able to solve them at the European level either. (RTL, 2021.11.6)

The general pro-governmental narrative maintains a negative stance toward anything “global,” claiming that global initiatives are unachievable without actions at local and national levels. This narrative constructs a dichotomy where “global” is positioned as in opposition to “local/national,” and global forces and processes are portrayed as “suspicious.”

In the dominant pro-governmental media, local and national are interpreted as inherently anti-global, standing in opposition to the European Union’s policies, which are blamed for “exacerbating problems.” Within this global anti-global discourse, the European Commission and its climate policies are introduced as enemies contributing to the systematic degradation of local communities and solutions and undermining national energy autonomy and sovereignty.

Discourse on ideology vs reality

The issue of global dependence on certain energy sources—such as nuclear energy or natural gas—is interpreted not only as an economic decision intended to maintain low energy costs but as a solution built on reality, in contrast to an ideological approach. The categorization of green and renewable energy sources is also highly politicized at both national and international levels based on the main energy resources that countries use. Arguments on this matter concern the binary opposition of ideology vs reality.

[...] Last year, Europe was forced to face the prospect of climate and energy policy decisions driven by green ideology, politics, and lobbying interests backfiring and leading to a serious energy crisis. (Origo, 2022. 01. 06.)

The European and the Hungarian left led by “philos” cannot understand that energetics is not a question of philosophy or emotions, but stark reality. (MN, 2022. 03. 30.)

“Ideology,” like “global” – they are also strongly related – is an expression with negative interpretations in governmental communication, connected to processes such as unification or standardization that oppose a specific or tangible reality. The EU’s decisions on climate policies are interpreted as being aligned with the “green ideology” created in Brussels or the global elite that ignores the energy systems of the different nations. Ideology cannot deal with the specifics. However, this “ideology” also comes from a certain reality – in this discourse, the interest of the global elite –, which is increasing inequality (e.g., the proposal for energy taxation would affect more negatively countries like Hungary with unique energy policies, thus increasing the gap between the East and the West – a discourse which also has importance in right-wing political communication) (Mikecz et al., 2023). In contrast, decisions based on realities would better fit the different characteristics of countries. By the end of February, with the Russo-Ukrainian war, this debate became much louder, with discussion of the appropriateness of moral action based on Western ideologies – namely, involving the sanctions against Russia – which was evidently unequally harming the various EU countries. The oft-repeated statement of Hungarian governmental politicians that *“Hungary is on the side of the Hungarians”* strengthened this claim for an approach to energy policy based on economic reality. It also reflects the specific position of post-socialist countries in global energy policy.

According to this discourse, “green ideology” is based on the desire of the global elite to gain control over energy policy. Thus, it is a luxury of the rich/people in power and is far from addressing the growing needs of the poor. As inflation is strongly connected to energy policy, it has also become part of this discourse on ideology vs. reality. Inflation is caused by decisions made by the global elite, thus is artificially created.

So, if the Brussels bureaucrats did not artificially raise the price of energy, we would find a means of curbing the pace of price rises. (NSZ, 2022. 03. 27., based on an interview with Viktor Orbán on Kossuth Radio).

In the dominant pro-governmental discussions, the EU should prioritize addressing economic crises and war and supporting national governments to take responsibility for their own countries before focusing on the challenges of climate change.

During this period, discussions surrounding the climate crisis primarily arose regarding its economic domain concerning issues such as taxation and energy policies. The climate crisis, a global and ongoing concern, is often perceived as less tangible and pressing, diminishing its urgency in political agendas. Solutions and actions require long-term strategies and cannot be achieved through rapid political decision-making that mobilizes instant political support.

An interesting element arises in relation to the dichotomies of ideology versus reality, and universal versus particular values, as governmental communication simultaneously applies both dimensions. On one hand, decision-making is grounded in particular realities; on the other, it is justified by universal values. This dynamic is particularly evident in the contrast between the European Union's universal ideology and Hungary's claim to uphold universal values. In the discourse on climate change, the EU's universal values are framed through ideological narratives and moralization. In contrast, Hungary's approach is portrayed as rooted in pragmatic realities, emphasizing the protection of the nation, its position in the global energy policy, and the reinforcement of familial welfare.

Discourse on the EU's weaknesses and legitimacy

Although Hungary is often criticized for having a political system that is backsliding from democracy into autocracy, its position in the EU is still strong, and as a result, the EU functions as a "regime[-]legitimizing factor for Hungary, which compels us to describe the current political system of Hungary as an externally constrained hybrid regime" (Bozóki & Hegedűs, 2018, p. 1174). At the same time, Hungary strongly criticizes the democratic system of the EU, calling attention to the federalistic approach to the EU, disfavoring the role of the nations as independent actors.

Regarding climate protection, the allegedly real cause behind the new plan for environmental taxation is to extend Brussels's power institutionally and economically.

The primary driving force behind the new environmental tax on households is not climate protection, but an extension of Brussels' powers. The environmental impact of the proposed centralized regulatory instrument is small, but it could provide the European institutions with new powers and [...] revenue streams. (Origo.hu, 2021. 07. 26. and M1, 2021. 12. 21.)

The Hungarian government criticizes the European Commission for being anti-democratic in regard to several decision-making processes.

Let's be honest, the sanctions were not imposed in a democratic way. The sanctions were decided by Brussels bureaucrats and European elites. The European people were not consulted. (2021. 09. 26., speech of Viktor Orbán before addressing the agenda in Parliament, represented on several news sites)

and a few weeks later:

European democracy is being put at risk by those who are driving up the price of electricity and gas. These plans must therefore be withdrawn and rethought. (Origo, 2021. 10. 22.)

Again, the changes in energy prices are interpreted as being the result of the actions of an elite group, which accusation is part of the externalization of responsibility. However, in this section, the focus is on democracy.

An interesting contrast is that while the EU is criticized for being anti-democratic, its democratic nature is represented as of the main sources of its weakness. The constant aim of finding common ground on every issue with all EU Member States, which requires flexibility and the ability to renegotiate anything, hinders rapid action.

The characteristic of the European Union, which perhaps makes the Orbán government less afraid that the country will sooner or later find itself in a difficult situation, is that it likes to renegotiate things. So, when a member state says I've changed my mind, I'm going to change it, it says let's sit down, let's renegotiate the terms. (MN, 2022. 01. 24.)

The discourse on this weakness was present in both pro-governmental and government-critical websites' discourses. The opposition point of view is that this system makes possible the emergence of actors such as Viktor Orbán and

the Polish leader of the Law and Justice party, Jarosław Kaczyński, who are called the builders of authoritarian systems.

The complexity of the decision-making process is also debated, as it makes rapid action impossible in urgent cases. In contrast to this overly bureaucratic, too-complex mechanism, the federal structure of the United States seems to be perceived more positively. At the same time, the Federal EU concept is constantly criticized by referring to the cultural richness of the region and the importance of national sovereignty.

The source of this weakness is, therefore, the anti-democratic attempts of the EU to simplify decision-making processes with issues such as climate change, which supposedly affects all EU countries. Meanwhile, this complexity of decision-making processes is also criticized. It is interpreted as a sign of the decreasing legitimacy of the EU in discussing issues that affect differently the Member States. According to the governmental communication, the EU must be reformed. However, the way it should be done is not elaborated in the discourses present on the news sites.

RESULTS

In the analyzed corpus, articles rarely represent the explicit opinion of the newspaper or the journalist. Instead, their messages predominantly depend on quoting political speeches or expert opinions without providing additional interpretations. The topic of climate change rarely appeared as the primary focus; rather, it was framed in the context of broader issues such as economic challenges, European Union regulations, or the Russo-Ukrainian conflict.

It was an independent subject only in the cases of reporting about events such as COP26 in Glasgow or the Planet Budapest Summit.

The results further reveal that the topic of climate change, or environmental topics in general, are not represented independently in media coverage. They are intertwined with dominant governmental discourses on families, energy policy, economic performance, or scientific progress. For example, when inflation, new taxation policies, or rising energy prices become the center of political communication and thus the news media, climate-related topics become incorporated into pre-existing dominant governmental narratives. Consequently, during such periods, the number of articles addressing climate change increases, as does the presence of this topic on pro-governmental websites.

Positions and actors

Since climate change has recently attracted substantial attention in the Hungarian public sphere, discussions regarding the present and the potential future of climate policy – despite explicit political statements – have essentially featured experts’ opinions. However, these experts are not entirely independent of politics either. As previously noted, the strategy of politicizing scientific issues (Bolsen & Druckman, 2015) is quite common concerning climate-change-related issues, and the disagreement between liberal and conservative political approaches is becoming ever more visible (Pepermans & Maesele, 2016). Following the 2010 elections, the Hungarian government established various state-aligned research institutes and networks. This network of researchers supports governmental strategies across several fields, including climate change. Related to our case, it emphasizes the key role of nuclear energy over renewable sources, framing it as a reflection of “reality.” This narrative opposes “green ideologies” and the “forced greening” advocated by the idealistic European elite, including Hungary’s political opposition, who support the development of green energy sources. Both political groups deploy researchers who communicate in align with their opinions through the news media. In the case of the political opposition, the experts represented are also political actors – e.g., Benedek Jávor – further emphasizing the connection between science and politics.

Apart from this small group of experts, the dominant actors in the discourses are politicians from two distinct groups: 1) actors directly related to the topic, such as the State Secretary for Energy and Climate Policy, Attila Steiner; members of the Green party Politics Can Be Different (LMP); and internationally, Frans Timmermans, who led the climate policy of the EU; 2) actors in leading positions in the national and international landscape such as Viktor Orbán, the Hungarian PM, Judit Varga, the minister for foreign affairs at the time, and on the international level, Angela Merkel. Viktor Orbán is a leading/heroic figure when it comes to energy policy and overhead reduction, as it is said that “he is the one who personally invented the policy of overhead reduction” (2022.02.09., Szilárd Németh, Fidesz politician), one of the most dominant topics concerning climate change.

Institutions also play a significant role as actors, including the Hungarian government, the European Commission, and often generalized entities such as “Brussels” or the “bureaucrats of Brussels.” Aligned with previous research results, Brussels is referred to as a faceless, independent entity “ruled by those who want to replace an alliance of free nations with a European empire...” aiming to gain imperial power (Csehi & Zgut, 2021). As Krastev described it,

the Hungarian government “uses Brussels as a rhetorical punching bag while benefiting from its financial largess” (Krastev, 2018, p. 3). The Hungarian government acts as an outsider, as someone far away from this faceless entity; meanwhile, Hungarian politicians discuss and vote as members of this community.

Language

The polarization between pro-governmental and non-governmental discourses can also be grasped in the linguistic choices. Pro-governmental experts and politicians tend to favor using expressions such as *environmental protection*, *energy policy*, or *energy crisis*, whereas experts with opposing political perspectives commonly use expressions like climate change, climate crisis, or *climate protection*. Notably, the term “climate” in any form is associated with negative connotations within pro-governmental communication. Furthermore, the use of “war” rhetoric, a typical characteristic of the Hungarian government’s political communication (Szabó & Szabó, 2022), is commonly associated with this topic, particularly in the context of the governmental overhead reduction scheme discussed at national and international levels.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The topic of climate change is associated with no specific, inherent discursive framework, nor was it taken too seriously before the national elections in April 2022. However, it is deployed to support and strengthen other major discourses, such as the discourse of responsibility, the discourse of protection, the discourse about the weakness of the European Union, and political discourses of major importance in the Hungarian public sphere. These results are partly in line with those of Mikecz and his colleagues (2023), who claim that the narratives that are used concerning the climate crisis and climate movement rather follow the Hungarian government’s general discourses and communication strategies than the discursive patterns of populism globally. Mikecz’s results also discuss how this discourse fits the climate-nationalist approach. Our results, however, show that it is rather a climate-conservative approach that is deployed to reinforce the claim that “current new environmentally conscious technological innovations can

address the changes and that there is a role for the national and EU levels to play, but only to the extent that this is done at minimum cost to nation-state economies and national sovereignty” (Vihma et al., 2020). This conservative perspective highlights the importance of local solutions – local can mean cooperation between V4 countries as well – and criticizes the urge to act globally, calling this a left-liberal approach (Antal, 2021, p. 221), associated with claims that liberal actors want to expropriate the issue of climate change (Featherstone, 2013; Båtstrand, 2015).

In looking at the discursive approach to the current European integration process of the government and the political opposition, we can see both sides lack any real pro-EU discourse. Previous research shows that Hungarian political communication tends to personalize the EU and Brussels as an opponent or a bully but not as an ally. At the same time, Central-Eastern Europe is a positive character (Benczes & Szabó, 2020; Szabó & Szabó, 2022). In the case of climate change, this bully-ally dichotomy should be difficult to use. However, by transforming this issue into one of pure energy policy by enhancing the elements of overhead costs and protecting families, Brussels can easily be castigated as a bully or, even more, an incompetent and ideologically guided elite.

The discussions surrounding climate change also highlight the nation’s geopolitical positioning between East and West. This dual alignment is characterized by a pragmatic approach to the East and ideologically driven affiliations with the West.

When looking at these discourses of Europeanization using a pragmatic and value-based or identity framework (Toshkov et al., 2014), the political opposition’s discourses seem to be pragmatic by enhancing the positive role of the EU in supporting and framing the fight against climate change within the context of the values of the European Union. However, on the pro-governmental news sites, it is interpreted as an ideological stance favoring “green ideology.” The governmental discourse is more complicated because it constantly uses both pragmatic and identity frameworks. The discussion of decision-making processes concerning climate change is governed by pragmatic questions – who is responsible? how should we act? – but explained and masked using an identity approach based on values, such as the role and protection of families and the importance of national sovereignty.

The results indicate that discourses surrounding climate change continue to be mainly associated with economic and political themes rather than part of an independent discursive framework. However, it is evident that the former topic is becoming increasingly important, suggesting that it will be valuable to monitor shifts in its framing over the coming years.

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THE PLACE OF HUXIT IN HUNGARIAN ELITE DISCOURSE. LESSONS FROM A Q-ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT: *This study summarizes research experiences regarding the views on the EU of the Hungarian political and media elite. Using Q-analysis, we tried to clarify the weight of these views and the relationship between them. The interviewees were asked to rank statements from the media according to their degree of agreement and then to justify their choices. The two dominant factors – Integrationist and Sovereigntist – were joined by two marginal ones: Multi-Speed and Huxit. The factors were clearly interpretable according to the polarization position and nature of the discourse. Huxit emerged normatively among the far-right elite, which was critical of the government. Otherwise, it was discussed in a more contemplative manner or strongly critically rejected.*

KEYWORDS: *elite, integrationism, sovereigntism, multi-speed, Huxit, Q-analysis, normative and contemplative modes of discourse*

INTRODUCTION

Regarding the European Union and the Europeanization process a variety of views prevail both in the media and among the elite. ‘Elite’ here is used to refer to those who, due to their position or prestige, are able to significantly influence nationwide reproduction processes through their personal opinions and decisions (Higley-Burton 1998, Higley-Lengyel 2000). In terms of ideological orientation, the literature often distinguishes between hard and soft forms of Euroscepticism (and optimism) (Szczzerbiak-Taggart

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2008). Pragmatic, rational-calculative EU criticism can be described as soft, while identity-based EU skepticism can be described as hard EU skepticism, as the former is easier to change and the latter more difficult (Lengyel-Göncz 2010). As regards forms of governance, there are also a number of distinctions between supranational and – old and new – intergovernmental solutions (Stone-Sandholtz 1997, Lengyel-Ilonszki 2008, Lengyel-Göncz 2009, Ilonszki 2010, Bickerton et al. 2015, Schimmelfennig 2015). Due to the endogenization of international policies and interference of national political forces, Europeanization is not only a concern for EU politicians (Mair 2004, Radaelli 2004, Mérand 2021). The literature on European integration convincingly argues that functionalist and pluralist views tend to crystallize around political standpoints and are arranged along identity-based or pragmatic considerations. Our research aims to examine these views among the Hungarian political and media elite by utilizing – like Robyn (2005) – Q methodology.² In the first step, we selected 25 statements that frequently appear in Hungarian media outlets, and we asked the interviewees to evaluate them according to their acceptability and level of agreement. The paper is exploratory in nature. We do not test hypotheses but are interested in how elites interpret media claims and how these views are shaped. The statements used in the study are presented in abbreviated form in the figures, and their full text is available in the Appendix.

In the following section, we shall first briefly describe the methodology and the sampling. Afterward, with the quantitative approach, we elucidate the factors that were formed on the basis of statements. Then, the report will introduce and interpret the comments connected to the statements with specific reference to the Huxit discourse.

Quantitative Q factor analysis complements the qualitative discourse analysis well, and the techniques are mutually strengthening. In fact, the Q-set comprised 25 statements based on the content and discourse analysis of the EU-related information that prevailed in the Hungarian media between July 2021 and March 2022. Our Q-based research took place between 2022 November and

² Q methodology is especially applied in attitude research to investigate subjective views. Its application appeared first in the works of William Stephenson in the 1930s (Brown 1993, 1996). The method can be utilized to unfold and analyze the particular attitudes that form in a group concerning a certain topic or issue, and it works well in relatively small groups as well. Stephenson's work was further developed by his disciple Steven R. Brown, who had a major role in the method gaining popularity in sociology and political science research. The study of C.M. Dieteren and her colleagues (Dieteren et al., 2023) confirmed the latter process when, in an overview of the publications from the last two decades, they found that in addition to the more extensive application of the Q method, the variation in its applications has also increased.

2023 March with the participation of 60 interviewees, including 31 members of the Hungarian media and 29 members of the Hungarian political elite.

We asked the participants to place the 25 statements in a grid containing 25 cells; thus, they could place one statement in each cell. The cells were displayed in seven rows and seven columns in the form of a reverse pyramid. The numerical value of each column appeared on the top of the columns in increasing order from left to right (from -3 to +3). The participants were asked to award a point to each statement and place them accordingly in the grid. They established this ranking based on how much they agreed or disagreed with the statements and the level of importance they attached to them. Participants were not allowed to divert from the grid pattern when placing the statements, so the pattern would be uniform according to the research design.

Due to the reverse pyramid format, the participants could place two statements at the two endpoints (marked by -3 and +3, respectively). At the same time, they could insert more statements at the locations of other values. For example, the largest number of statements – seven – could be placed at value 0. Participants could move around the statements until they established the final statement pattern that fully reflected their preferences. Afterward, they commented and explained their selection pattern, particularly the extremes located at the +/-3 and +/- 2 values. It was a fundamental stipulation that the interviewer should not influence the participants in arranging the statements and the follow-up discussion. As the arrangement is subjective, it cannot be contextually wrong from the perspective of the analysis if the grid arrangement formally matches the requirements.

For the statistical analysis of the data, we used the desktop version of the KADE (KEN-Q Analysis Desktop Edition version 1.2.1, Banasick 2019) computer software, which provides fast and precise analysis and allows the researcher to make refined decisions at a number of points. In the process of the Q analysis, following the instructions in the methodological section, we opted for the principal component method (QPCA). The principal component analysis started from a correlation matrix and investigated the correlation between the participants' subjective opinion patterns, creating factor groups that included the participants themselves. Thus, this method, by ranking and prioritizing the pre-defined statements and identifying similar thought patterns, reduced them to a smaller number of factors and diminished the multitude of individual opinions that would be challenging to analyze using statistical methods. In contrast to traditional factor analysis, where latent variables are formed from the variables and their meanings unfolded by researchers, here, those respondents whose views correlated were grouped (Brown, 1993). Thus, the interviewees were sorted into different factors, the goal being to identify the commonalities

and central leitmotifs of their opinions that defined the groups and were central enough to distinguish the latter – at least partially – from the other groups.

The sample reflects the two-thirds versus one-third proportion of the government–opposition divide. The political elite sample included members of the Hungarian Parliament (MPs), members of the European Parliament (MEPs), and high-ranking ministerial civil servants (heads of departments and similar or higher positions). The media elite comprised chief editors and leading journalists of printed and online papers, television, and radio, in addition to members of the boards representing the owners. We wrote an invitation letter to 60 members of the political and media elite describing the purpose and references underlying the research. We applied the snowball method to reach more respondents. Twelve interviewers took part in the process. They followed up on the additional interview suggestions until the third contact point, when – after adjustment with the research leader – they met the interviewees according to the quota requirements. We ensured anonymity throughout the process; both the interviewers and the interviewees were assigned a code number. At the end of the interviews, we asked for socio-demographic data. Due to the small number of interviews and anonymity criteria, we cannot provide accurate party affiliation data beyond distinguishing between the governing elite, opposition, and far-right opposition in the case of the politicians and a pro-government, neutral, or government-critical classification of the media elite. However, we also asked the respondents to describe their political orientation on a seven-point left-right scale. These data, together with the results obtained from the KADE factor analysis, were processed with the SPSS 22 program package. We later relied on these when briefly describing the social profile of the elite members representing the factors. Here, we would like to preliminarily note that the 60-member sample consisted of 49 men and 11 women; half of the sample was over 50 years old, 29 belonged to the political group and 31 to the media elite. Education was not a differentiating factor, as all but one participant had a university degree. A more detailed review shows that MPs and MEPs were represented by 17 and civil servants by 12 persons, while editors and journalists were the largest group, including 24 persons, and 7 interviewees represented the media owners. Fifty-five individuals were active in their positions at the time of the interview. In terms of political self-classification, 60 percent belonged to the right and roughly a quarter to the left, while the remainder belonged to the center (marked as ‘4’ on a 7-point scale). If the center category is extended to the values of 3 to 5 on a 7-point scale, roughly two-thirds of the sample belonged to this category, a quarter to the right, and a tenth to the left according to their own understanding.

PRESENTATION OF THE FACTORS

Factor analysis

As a result of the principal component analysis, we identified eight unrotated factors. Fewer factors can improve interpretation capacity; thus, we applied Varimax rotation, which maximizes the factors' eigenvalues and the sum of the variance explained. The aim was to place each individual into one factor only, with a large weight, and for the factors to have the largest possible information content (each variable appears in a standardized form in the analysis, with 0 average and 1 standard deviance). After applying this technique, we identified four factors that describe the opinion groups within the Hungarian political and media elite. A screen plot also supports our decision. These four factors do not correlate with one another, and they contain the largest proportion of information content. After rotation, the four factors together explain 70 percent of the variation (that is, of all the information). The program grouped participants in the relevant factors at a statistical significance of $P < 0,05$. The weight and direction of factor values explain how the variables shape the factors. A variable can be rightly regarded as an element of the factor if its factor weight is larger than 0.25 (Székelyi, Barna 2008 pp.47-48). This requirement is fulfilled for all four factors. In the first three factors, the variables that define the factors all belong to the factor with a positive weight, while in the fourth factor, one of the two defining variables has a negative weight. Although this is an important variable that defines the factor, its opposing direction should be taken into consideration in the analysis.

The analysis identified four main factors, which we call *Integrationist*, *Sovereignist*, *Multi-Speed*, and *Huxit standpoints*, described in detail below, complemented with information from the thematic interviews.

We presume that the following descriptions pinpoint the characteristic views of the Hungarian political and media elite about European integration. This presupposition is not self-evident; we cannot simply argue that the factors reflect the authentic opinions of the elite groups as the interviewees – due to the methodology of Q analysis – were obliged to choose between the statements. Nevertheless, two substantive arguments support the view that the findings closely describe elite opinion patterns. First, the statements themselves were imported from media discourses where elite opinions dominate. Second, the interviewees commented on their choices, and their arguments convincingly supported and refined the decisions relating to the factor classification.

Integrationism

The first factor represents those who share the *integrationist* standpoint. This is the strongest factor that explains one-third of the variance. Some elite members attribute symbolic historical importance to European integration. Defining features are that EU membership is advantageous for Hungary, European identity is important, NATO and the EU ensure the safety of Hungary, and the EU is the best guarantor of democracy, human rights, and the rule of law in the Member States. In contrast, this perspective opposes the idea that the EU might threaten the energy safety of Hungarian households or pursue LGBTQ propaganda, which is harmful to children, and it also rejects that the EU should return to a situation of cooperation between sovereign nation-states. Integrationists criticize the government in several areas and reject stereotyping aimed at the West.

Figure 1. Structure of the 'Integrationists' factor

Source: MEDEU, authors' compilation

The views of those represented in this factor are weakly significant in terms of believing that migration may solve the labor shortage problems in the EU. This factor does not involve a firm standpoint either about the multi-speed alternative or about the asymmetries within the EU – that is, about the dominance of big firms and Western states. Although members have a firm negative view of Huxit, this is not a distinguishing feature because they share this view with members of two other factors. What can be seen as a distinguishing feature of the Integrationist factor is the positive view about strengthening the EU's central institutions, in contrast to the other three factors (although this view is not shared by everyone within the Integrationist position either).

Arguments supporting the typical claims associated with the factor may be highlighted with the following statements:

We receive 4% of Hungary's GDP from the European Union; without EU support, there would be a very serious recession in Hungary, which is also to be expected if we could not agree very quickly on the original funds – and then we did not discuss the next seven-year cycle of the funds. So, we are absolutely, a net beneficiary of the European Union financially. This is one, the financial side, and the social side is mobility. The fact that anyone can go to the West to learn, to learn, to live. The boundaries have become more or less formal ... So, the world opened up (member of the political elite, opposition).

For Hungary, EU membership is beneficial, and being a small, weak country, its security can only and exclusively be guaranteed by its Western allies, so this is out of the question. (member of the political elite, government).

The integration of the EU should be continued... I put it here among the strongest 'yeses' because I think that European integration was one of the greatest achievements of the 20th century. (member of the government-critical media elite).

If there were no EU [here], it would be a hybrid democracy of the 1930s and a mixture of the Putin era. (member of the government-critical media elite).

Among those who hold integrationist views, younger individuals, men, and those born in the capital were slightly overrepresented, although these associations were not significant.

In contrast, there was a strong and significant correlation between integrationist perceptions and political attitudes. Left and centrist attitudes were significantly over-represented among those with integrationist views. There was also a weak significant correlation between the integrationist factor and elite position, with members of the media elite being slightly over-represented among those holding these views. In contrast, civil servants were under-represented among those who took an integrationist stance. Almost half of the 60 elite members interviewed (29 persons) held integrationist views. Among them, 19 belonged to the media elite and 10 to the political elite. Two of the latter group were (former) civil servants. It should be noted that the vast majority of the sample were active incumbents: of the 60 respondents, only five were no longer in their positions at the time of the interview. In other words, the majority of opposition politicians and government-critical media elites hold positions similar to the integrationist view. On the other hand, only a minority of governing politicians and the pro-government media elite shared these ideas.

Sovereignism

In the *second* factor – which explains 23% of the variance – the respondents gather around *sovereignist* standpoints representing views about national defense. One key statement that represents this position is that the EU is threatening the energy safety of Hungarian households, and another one is that the EU should return to a format of cooperation between sovereign nation-states. *Sovereignists* think that immigration threatens Europe's cultural identity, that the EU is engaged in LGBTQ propaganda, and Hungary is the custodian of traditional European values. At the same time, they positively value the statement that NATO and the EU guarantee safety in the context of war. They think more highly – above average – about the economic performance of Hungary and vehemently oppose the criticism that the Hungarian government does not use European resources in a transparent way. Furthermore, they reject – again, above the average level – the view that migration can solve the labor shortage problems in the EU or that the EU should step up against Russian and Chinese disinformation in the Member States. At the same time, the statement that European identity is an important value and can be compatible with national identity does not appear negatively, although the intensity of the identification with this statement is below average. We should note that the sovereignist standpoint receives an explicitly positive interpretation here, while it is negated in the Integrationist factor.

Figure 2. Structure of the 'Sovereignists' factor

Composite Q sort for Factor 2

-3	-2	-1	0	1	2	3
We should leave the EU sooner or later.	The EU is the best guarantee for the preservation of democracy.	The EU should not interfere in any minority issues in the Member States.	The EU mainly serves the interests of large companies.	The countries of Central Europe represent common values	** ► The current policy of the EU threatens the energy security of	The EU must return to cooperation between sovereign
* ◀ Migration solves the EU's labor market problems.	** ◀ The Hungarian government used EU funds in an insufficiently transparent	** ◀ The EU must act effectively against Russian and Chinese disinformation	** The EU threatens Hungary's national sovereignty.	The Western European "old" member states of the EU dominate over	Hungary is the custodian of true European values, Christianity	Immigration from non-EU countries threatens Europe's
	The central institutions of the EU must be strengthened.	European integration must be a multi-speed process.	* ► Hungary's economy performs better than that of most EU	EU membership is beneficial for Hungary.	The EU's so-called LGBTQ propaganda is harmful to children.	
		The EU must stand against authoritarian tendencies in individual	* ◀ European identity is an important value for us and is compatible with	* Hungary's security in a war situation is guaranteed by the EU and		
			During the Covid epidemic, Hungarian epidemic management			
			The operation of the West is chaotic, ineffective and declining.			
			EU integration must continue.			

Legend

- * Distinguishing statement at P < 0.05
- ** Distinguishing statement at P < 0.01
- z-Score for the statement is higher than in all other factors
- ◀ z-Score for the statement is lower than in all other factors

Source: MEDEU, authors' compilation

The option of Huxit receives a strong negative evaluation by members of the Sovereignist group. On the other hand, statements like “the EU is the best guarantee for democracy in the Member States” and “the central institutions of the EU should be strengthened” are also strongly rejected.

The defensive position of the Sovereignist point of view is presented in the following interview excerpts:

This is a debate between two concepts, the Europe of nations and a federal Europe, and I firmly believe that , as the founders of the European Union and coal and steel community, and the founders of the European Community in the 1950s Christian-democratic politicians

thought that the right path was the Europe of nations and nation-states, and this federal Europe, this is a non-existent fiction and nothing good will come out of it. (member of the political elite, government).

On the part of the European institutions, the two very common accusations are the rule of law accusations in general, and especially the use of European Union funds... not so much their transparency, because I think this transparency is clear, as the Hungarian laws, such as the Public Procurement Act, is one of the strictest... in the entire European Union. So, it cannot be said that resources are used in a non-transparent manner. ... the EU institutional system launches political attacks against Hungary. (member of the political elite, government).

I don't think the EU uses its existing power well in economic matters, and it does use it terribly in political matters. (member of the political elite, government).

Sovereignists are the second largest opinion camp. Of the 60 respondents, 25 (that is, more than two-fifths) belong here. A more accurate picture emerges if we look at the composition of the political and media elite separately. We can observe that Sovereignists are the absolute majority within the political elite. This is not surprising, given that active civil servants are unanimous in this view, and two-thirds of MPs are pro-government. Those who define themselves as right-wing are significantly-, while women, the elderly, and those born in smaller municipalities are not significantly over-represented among the Sovereignists. In other words, we can say that the majority of the governing politicians and pro-government media elites support the sovereignist position.

The Multi-Speed view

It appears as a defining statement in the *third factor* – which explains 8% of the variance – that European integration should be a *multi-speed* process and thus should continue according to the preparedness and interests of the Member States. Similarly, it is considered positive and accentuated that European integration should endure.

It is of defining significance that the representatives of this factor do not agree with the statement that the EU's current policy threatens the energy safety of Hungarian households.

Figure 3. Structure of the Multi-Speed factor

Source: MEDEU, authors' compilation

Also above the average but at a somewhat lower level, the members of this factor oppose the idea that immigration threatens the cultural identity of Europe and that the safety of Hungary is ensured by NATO and the EU. Thus, overall, the representatives of the Multi-Speed perspective support the integration process but are skeptical about the EU's performance on a number of policy issues. They share the views that "Hungary is the custodian of true European values" and "the EU must return to [a system of] cooperation between sovereign nation-states." Relatively few respondents represent this factor, and the explanatory value of this factor is also smaller than that of the Integrationist and Sovereigntist factors. The following quotes shed light on the tone of the interviews related to the Multi-Speed factor.

I think European integration should be multi-speed because the state, preparedness, attitude, history, and past of the Member States are very different. (member of the neutral media elite).

I think that the current energy policy of the European Union has not been thought through and that the energy policy apparently puts the entire European Union at a competitive disadvantage and causes very serious problems for some Member States... Not only is it specifically stated in the rule of law procedure that the European Union subsidies are used in a transparent manner, but it is also important from the point of view of the government's acceptance, legitimacy, and people's well-being that new measures are now being taken, such as an integrity authority, I don't know what, what it will be able to change, we will see, but I think it is a step in the right direction. (member of the political elite, government).

Now there is a very, very big difference between paying in Euros three years from now or never paying in Euros. And that this is an existing goal that we want to achieve, we are working on it, we just don't know yet. The first one is obviously an understandable, multi-speed process, there are more speeds because there is a constraint, but they will grind together somehow. The other one says that it's good that way, that it's here there it is. [...] It's really not good. (member of the pro-government media elite).

The Huxit factor

In the period leading up to the 2022 elections, the media research suggests that the possibility of Huxit was only marginal and conditional. In the campaign, Fidesz, which was in government until then, based its criticism of the EU on a sovereigntist viewpoint, but left no doubt that it saw the country's future within the European Union. The elections not only saw the governing party win another two-thirds of the vote but also saw the entry into parliament of a small far-right party, Mi Hazánk, which does not reject Huxit. This is not the most important item on their agenda, but there is no doubt that they could represent this alternative if necessary. With this parliamentary legitimacy, however marginal, it seems justified to analyze the elements of the Huxit discourse in their own right.

This discourse is based on the assertion that Hungary’s exit from the EU is a realistic and desirable alternative. It contains, and as we shall see, links criticism of the EU and criticism of the government. Representatives of this position doubt the benefits of EU and NATO membership, and these are the main ideological and pragmatic discourses that characterize the Huxit discourse. Few people hold this view, but elements of it also appear in the comments of many other interviewees. Sometimes, it appears as a way of calculating the odds, but in other cases, mostly as a form of rejection, as a bad, unrealistic, or only a negative vision of the future.

Figure 4. Structure of the Huxit factor

Source: MEDEU, authors' compilation

The defining statement in the *fourth* factor is that sooner or later, *Hungary should exit* the EU. This view – contributing 6% of the explained variance – is represented by a small number of respondents from the extreme right opposition. They regard the EU as the embodiment of negative trends and tendencies; therefore, they oppose it. Further important elements of this factor are that the respondents think that the EU is threatening the independence of Hungary and the energy safety of households. They contest that EU membership is advantageous for Hungary or that it is a guarantee of safety. They argue that the EU should not intervene in minority issues within the Member States. The opinions that are prevalent in this factor are close to some of the Sovereigntist standpoints, especially in the areas of migration and gender issues, but they represent a more radical version. At the same time, its proponents also advocate views that are critical of the government, and particularly, they posit that the government does not handle EU resources in a transparent way.

PROS AND CONS CONCERNING HUXIT

Arguments in favor of Huxit

The views of those who would support Huxit are illuminated in the following interview passages.

They are colonizing us, I think, especially Germany. The Prime Minister also tends to dwell [on] this, that they take more money out of the country than comes here as EU support...

Well, if we talk about the Union, then the princely winner should be that European Union membership is beneficial for Hungary, – I really cannot identify with that. ...even the policy of Fidesz, which is very critical of the EU, accuses Brussels of bureaucratization, places all responsibility on Brussels, and makes Brussels the scapegoat, ultimately says that [Hungary] is much better within the Union and there is a completely excluded, absurd idea that [Hungary should leave the Union]. However, the example of Great Britain also shows that there is life outside the EU. Even after the Union, I think you should mostly prepare for that. (member of the political elite, far-right opposition).

The claims that make up this discourse often apply geopolitical analogies to a stylized historical past. Both the EU and the Hungarian government are criticized for inefficiency and for their turning away from 'real' values.

- Well, we should leave the EU sooner or later, that's obvious to me ... I don't want to be a reformer of the EU, I want to be a survivor of the EU ... I think the EU has no future for the most part, so I would prepare for life after the EU, on the other hand, it colonizes us, it exploits us. Not to our advantage...

- Is there any aspect that is salient about how it is exploiting us?

- Mostly economically. But at the same time, the most powerful lobby in the world is the homosexual lobby, or the LGBTQ lobby, whatever lobby, because of that they interfere in our other internal affairs. (member of the political elite, far-right opposition).

An important element of support for the Huxit view is the emphasis on how the old Member States, the big ones, the ones in a central geopolitical position, take advantage of the new, smaller countries on the European periphery.

One could say it's a cliché, but nevertheless, because of the seriousness of the problem, I would still affirm that the old Member States dominate the new Member States. ... not to mention the fact that what comes in is for specific purposes, for multinational companies, which is why they can take it out, or for spectacular investments, So we do not have it ourselves, these are not so much job-creating investments, in my view, as they are often for multinationals, and then this is the next point I would like to make here, that the EU serves the interests of large companies, and certainly not, let us say, those of small and medium-sized enterprises, which provide two-thirds of the jobs. (member of the political elite, far-right opposition)

The old Member States are the ones that got the horrific money on entry. This money was not given to the central and eastern European Member States. What is an important Commissioner in the European Union will never be given. Eastern and Central Europeans have never been asked to lead the European Union. (member of the government-critical media elite)

In this narrative, the Brexit solution is used as a good example of exit, and the claims are that the current EU plans were not outlined at the time of entry and that arguments for the benefits of EU membership have been given one-sided emphasis in international communication.

... The EU public communications foundation only financed the campaign for the 'yes' vote, even though the name of the foundation implies that it could have provided balanced information before the referendum, Now we can feel it on our own skin and make a more realistic decision, and now it is no longer legally possible to hold a referendum on leaving the EU, and I think it is a little absurd that it was possible to hold a referendum on entering the EU, and then, when people wake up from their own experiences, they are prevented from doing so. But I think the campaign for a yes vote was already quite one-sided. (member of the political elite, far-right opposition)

The arguments in favor of leaving are not always coherent ideologically, but one such point of coherence is the far-right view of the EU as an exploiting, decaying empire that destroys national traditions. Therefore, one of the representatives of this view wants the EU to *'survive, not reform'*.

When weighing up the pros and cons, the Huxit politician is not operating in the pragmatic field. He doubts the existence of the benefits offered by the EU because he sees the EU as an empire that subjugates the sovereignty of the nation-state and the individual. Yet there is a pragmatic aspect to the ideological argument against the EU, and that is the issue of security. In this respect, too, the EU is seen as a rather disadvantageous constraint, as is NATO, which is unable to guarantee peaceful conditions in this evaluation.

Well, taking all the above into account, it is obviously not only a question of monetizable aspects, but it is also an emotional issue that – representing the desire for freedom and national independence of the youth of March of 1848 and the young guys of 1956 in Pest – I consider it important that they do not take away our self-determination and that we do not become part of a world empire, we then see the Russian crisis dragging us into [some]thing along the lines of great power interests....

...the alarm bells should be sounded because there is not monetizable cost, so when the EU balance sheet is drawn up, whether we are net contributors or subsidized, most of the time it does not include, this can include those priceless values that we cannot even decide for ourselves

how much they are worth. At the level of the individual, it is worth so much that, okay, we get a salary, but it is worth so much that I can decide whether – in the context of the provision of health care, we can talk here about the COVID dictatorship, or anything else – individual freedom, that is also a difficult thing to monetize, but it is still valuable...

I think that when there is a threat of war, it is mostly NATO members [involved], and the Turkish-Greek conflict shows that NATO is helpless there, so I would like to bring in a little NATO criticism. (member of the political elite, far-right opposition)

Some of those who share this view see an irreconcilable conflict between supranational and national identities. Others, however, do not dispute the possibility of multiple identities but reframe the topic as a primordial racial issue.

...it may cause a little confusion in the coordinate system, but European identity is important for us. It is an important value; it is not only European, but we also call it Nordic civilization. I think that saving white humanity could also be a value, it is not correct to talk about today, but if the alarm bell can be sounded for the endangered great white shark, I think it can also be sounded for the white man.... (member of the political elite, far-right opposition)

The interviewee uses the synonyms of patriotism, local patriotism, and pride to interpret European identity. He softens his radical critique with the phrase “a bit.” In an analogy, he refers to Budapest, which, under the leadership of its liberal mayor, proclaimed a vision of a metropolis. The effect was, according to this interpretation, to strengthen local patriotism in the districts and weaken the sense of metropolitan pride. By analogy, he feels that the European Union is not strengthening European identity but destroying it due to the opposition of nation-states.

...because it's a bit of a declaration of war on nation states, so I think that the EU [implies] also a bit of destruction of the European identity [...it] embodies that, I mean, Karács... – [...] Gábor Demszky was the mayor of Budapest and he was building a bit of a world city then too, perhaps this was one of his slogans, and, if this is not offensive to him, then he has more or less squeezed the local patriotism out of the patriots. I don't see many people in Hungary, in Budapest, who are proud Budapesters. There

are proud people from [the districts of] Kőbánya, Újpest, Ferencváros, and Belyáros, but there are very few who are proud of being a Budapest citizen and have the identity of a Budapest citizen. Now, I have a similar feeling that there is less local patriotism or patriotism or identity at the EU level, although otherwise, it would be important for us. (member of the political elite, far-right opposition)

Structure of arguments against Huxit

The arguments against Huxit are multi-faceted, ranging from economic disadvantages and geopolitical isolationism to the challenge of values. Most often, the economic disadvantages and the negative experience of Brexit emerge (although, as we have seen, there were also pro-Huxit voices that saw positive lessons in Brexit). Economic and geopolitical concerns are intertwined in this set of arguments; isolationism would increase the chance of exposure to Eastern autocracies. The other part of the counterarguments is linked to the extreme escalation of internal divisions within the country that Huxit could lead to, which may be comparable in impact to the trauma of the post-World War I period. It would lead to serious social conflicts and mass emigration.

I think it would be an orbital mistake. Hungary clearly belongs in the European Union and NATO. Our place is clearly in the West. That is why we should break with this 'ferry' position between East and West. It is essential, not only financially but also in terms of social mobility, for Hungary to be a member of the European Union. Otherwise, what is left? Moldova? Russia? The despots of the East? So, I think we should definitely stay in the EU. (member of the political elite, opposition)

The moment Hungary leaves the European Union, it will be broken. It is an economy that is fully exposed to international processes, that depends on international relations for a thousand strands, economically. I'm talking primarily about, at this moment, so a very open economy. The moment these doors close, the moment it is back among the poorest ... European countries. (member of the government-critical media elite)

I think that Hungary's exit from the EU..., well, for those who are thinking about it, I'll put it in a way that they can understand, would be a second Trianon. In every way. It would cause such a terrible national

trauma, even in the medium term, that...now incidentally, the country would go bankrupt, but let's leave aside these silly economic aspects... so it would be such a national trauma in every way, and it would further divide an already very divided society so irreparably, not to mention I am convinced that there must be more than 1 million people who would leave Hungary, which would be a fateful event in history, again in a negative direction, I would venture to say more tragic than Trianon, and I find it totally absurd in every respect. There was an article ... a few weeks ago, or 2-3 months ago, about how during the Austro-Hungarian Monarchy, the entire Hungarian intelligentsia constantly criticized the Monarchy, but they did not even think of leaving because everyone knew that the Monarchy was the only chance to catch up, yet they constantly criticized it. My view is that anyone who leaves the EU is a traitor. But this is also absurd. I know I am a bit of an idealist, but obviously, as we see it here today, towards the end of November 2022, we have a Ukraine that is pulling towards Europe; it may even become a candidate country, maybe in 20 or 30 years, I do not think sooner. Does anybody really think that we should be surrounded on all sides by EU Member States and we would have customs and everything? People don't even think about what that means. The British don't think about it either, and it is a rich country. It would be tragic in every way. A lot of people have already left, so how many people would leave this country? We have one and a half million people who have emigrated to America; I can absolutely understand them. I don't think it is something that would occur to any normal person. (member of the neutral media elite)

Some claim that it is dangerous that even the idea of Huxit has been raised on the margins of political discourse. They consider that this could contaminate public thinking. For some, it is an alternative that threatens democracy and the rule of law. Others see it as a “*departure from a thousand years of St Stephen's Way*”, who led the country towards the adoption of the Roman Catholic religion and accession to the West.

I think it's a terrible thing; I think it's a terrible thing that it has entered the political discourse and the vernacular at all; I think it's a bad thing because it's [the EU is] not perfect, it has many flaws, every institutional system, every structure has flaws, but without it, we would be living in a much worse world if the European Union didn't exist. ... So we should not even raise the possibility of that. (member of the government-critical media elite).

There are two ways of arguing the case against Huxit. One is normatively based, rejecting the possibility of Huxit from an alternative ideological position. Proponents of this stance are emphatically negative and sometimes dramatic. The other viewpoint is more contemplative-analytical, seeking to consider the likely effects and unintended consequences of exit. This position is also negative about Huxit but more restrained, and the formulated thoughts are based on reflection about the chances of this. An important aspect of this consideration is the chance to influence public opinion.

I think there could easily be a format where the majority of people... how shall I put it... will be persuaded by the government. Or a mood could develop where a narrow majority decide to, say, quit. I think that's basically conceivable. But obviously, a lot depends on the economic situation...a lot can change, and if you look at how much the attitude of Hungarians has changed on a lot of issues, not with the EU but with, say, the FIDESZ voters, who would obviously be the most receptive to such an argument. That say FIDESZ voters have become Russian friends within a couple of years...so if you can make such a turnaround on both sides in a couple of years...then anything can happen, I think.. (member of the pro-government media elite)

Another set of arguments invokes geopolitical conditions and their possible effects. Among these, the fiscal crisis and, as a consequence, an internal political crisis is one element. The other is the threat of falling under the influence of the East, especially Russia, and of a repeated loss of independence.

Since the end of the Second World War, we have seen a global struggle between West and East on the planet. The European Union has, in fact, annexed Hungary to the Western sphere of interest, even if there is Eastern influence in Hungary. And this status quo, which I think is optimal, would be upset if we were to leave the EU. But there would be other serious consequences of leaving the Union, such as, in my opinion, state bankruptcy or serious exposure to countries that would otherwise cause a serious democratic deficit for the country, and there is a danger that after decades of great independence, we could again be under the hand of a foreign power, if we think about the ambitions of Russia, Hungary could easily come under serious Russian influence. (member of the government-critical media elite)

A further form of reflection considers the reality of exit. By all inferences, the reality of this is minimal in the short to medium term, although there are many residual uncertainties. Intertwined with this, but different in nature, is the rational perspective that involves weighing up the pros and cons. Due to the nature of the interview situation, this is not systematically explained, but its structure follows the logic of cost-benefit analysis. There are elements of the EU that can be criticized in this, but the balance of pros and cons ultimately leads to the conclusion that the EU is the less disadvantageous option.

I put this at 'minus three' because I don't think it's realistic, so I don't think Hungary really has any room for maneuver in this respect among the current large federal systems. And I have obviously included statements in the columns on agreement that are negative for the EU, but I still think it is the lesser of two evils. (member of the pro-government media elite)

In addition to the economic benefits, there are other aspects to consider such as the protection of democracy and the convergence of values. All this fits in with the fact that the interviewee interprets the Hungarian government's vetoes in EU referenda and the conditionality of EU budget funds as mutual blackmail maneuvers and condemns them from both sides.

I categorically disagree with this [that we should leave]. You know, the European Union has only brought positive things, including the fact that we expected more in terms of catching up, but Hungary did receive European funds. Without European money, there would have been far less construction and modernization here, and I'm not just talking about construction. Well, education is not a good example, but even in education, without which the money would not have been so much, or in health care. Or let's say modernization in the broad sense, so I wouldn't limit it to paving roads and buildings, but this is the most visible part, and this is one of the economic parts. Yes, the European Union does not represent negative values in terms of democracy or values, so that is progress. In a European sense, the common market creates economic opportunities for us and the possibility of joint action. I am saying this, of course, despite the fact that I do not agree that the money for catching up or, heaven forbid, for the post-pandemic reset is subject to political conditions, and there are rules for that. I do not agree with that, but I do agree that the European Union should represent fundamental values, just not like this way. Well, that is blackmail; that is what it is called.

And Orbán says I'll veto it. They're blackmailing each other; it's going too far! But the European Union is also doing well because sooner or later, we really will veto them, and this European Union is not lacking in that.. (member of the political elite, government)

The rejection of Huxit can also be linked to a kind of criticism of the government. In this, the exit alternative becomes a possibility when the government elite can no longer channel EU funds to their clientele without interference. However, from this analytical point of view, the chances of Huxit are also small because the loss of the fraudulently acquired wealth that is being extorted would be associated with international isolation and a loss of prestige.

We don't need to leave the EU, we will only leave if staying endangers the criminal ... criminality of the current ruling party, of its individual members. Yes, I think that's what it's all about, after the money has been skimmed off.. Yes, I think there is propaganda going on, and there is a kind of preparation already... And several people have said the referendum presented by Orbán, the migration referendum, for example, which was already a test of leaving the EU, and I heard comments like that from the delegates of the governing party. It is conceivable that if this Russian-style propaganda is successfully pushed on Hungary, it is conceivable that the EU will be portrayed as the enemy and that people in the countryside will vote for it if a referendum is called... but I don't think it's a realistic chance, because watching this... let's say this peacock dance, or this swing policy of the government, they know very well when they can turn a part of the citizens against them, and when this reaches a certain preponderance or mass, they tend to dance back. And I don't think Orbán would dare to do that... What I have seen is that they are trying to bail out wealth, and I see and hear these efforts from many places. I'm reminded a little bit of Fujimori ... our current regime... it is very similar to the way the regime was set up and the way the Prime Minister behaved... I think that, in practice, leaving would be about exempting a certain class of people from certain criminal consequences – having robbed the EU – who have benefited very well from that. I think it would obviously be very damaging to a lot of people. (member of the government-critical media elite)

CONCLUDING REMARKS

This paper was written to sum up the main findings of interviews conducted with 60 members of the Hungarian political and media elite between November 2022 and March 2023. Besides the dominant discourses of Integrationism and Sovereignism, Multi-Speed and Huxit discourses also appeared in the elite interviews. The majority of the Hungarian political and media elite had a positive evaluation of EU membership, and Huxit was perceived as a marginal alternative.

We can refine our analysis here by recalling that we can observe two types of utterances in elite interviews: contemplative (analytic, descriptive) and normative. Although one might expect that the contemplative type would characterize the journalists and the normative approach the politicians, we found that the differences were not attached to such group differences. Rather, these are contrasts between habits and are connected to how the respondents think about the task, that is, the interview situation itself. Thus, one type of perspective is demonstrated by the analysis of what is seen as feasible and the other by a consideration of the 'right' behavior. The reflexive interview situation and the limited time span guided the interviewees toward adopting one of the two approaches. Huxit is occasionally associated with the contemplative approach when participants who have a critical view of the government speak about for how long it would be in the interest of the governing elite to remain in the EU or for how long the EU will tolerate veto and EU-critical propaganda. Sometimes, these approaches are connected: a normative conclusion might be built on gauging opportunities in addition to moral, religious, identity-based, or emotional considerations. They may be connected in a reverse sequence when a pro-government sovereignist or a government-critical integrationist member of the elite begins to weigh the potential causes and chances of leaving the European Union.

The most important indicator of the pragmatic perspective is the degree to which the respondents regard EU membership as advantageous for Hungary. Those with integrationist views highly esteem the advantages of EU membership, and – although less enthusiastically – those with sovereignist and multi-speed views also think positively in this regard. The arguments span investment and finance to mobility issues at the macro level, and in relation to mobility, even personal and microlevel viewpoints appear. In contrast, the political extreme right regards membership as disadvantageous; they advocate exit and claim their goal is to “*survive the EU*.” The arguments are abstract and appear in a macro-level economic and social frame. Identity-based interpretations are less divisive than pragmatic ones.

An interesting lesson from our analysis is that, although polarization typically relies on the identity-forming dichotomy of “them and us”, in these elite interviews, the relation to supranational identity did not prove to be divisive compared to the pragmatic aspects. European identity and its compatibility with national identity are not negatively evaluated by members of the Sovereignists. Even the views of the advocates of the Huxit alternative appear positive regarding supranational identity, but they understand supranational identity in a primordial, racial frame. European identity is most strongly favored among the Integrationists. In their case, identity frequently attracts a civic interpretation that emphasizes individuals’ choices and decisions. Cultural and historical discourse fragments also emerge regarding the compatibility of the two identities, similar to macrolevel pragmatic and security considerations.

Overall, despite all the strident criticism by the government of the EU, the Hungarian political and media elite was characterized to a greater extent by recognition of the EU’s benefits and EU identity and, to a lesser extent, by soft EU skepticism. Until 2024, Huxit appeared only on the periphery of the political elite. In that summer, however, in a contemplative speech, the Prime Minister, for the first time, considered the possibility that if we received an offer from the US (which he said was unlikely), Hungary could consider leaving the EU.³ Huxit thus became an imaginable alternative for the governing elite. The question is whether its media dominance will enable the governing elite to change the public mood until the next elections in 2026, or whether an alternative political elite can emerge that is more in tune with public mood and international conditions.

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APPENDIX. Q-STATEMENTS

- 1 Hungary is the custodian of true European values, Christianity and the institution of the family.
- 2 The EU threatens Hungary's national sovereignty.
- 3 The central institutions of the EU must be strengthened.
- 4 The EU must return to cooperation between sovereign nation-states.
- 5 Immigration from non-EU countries threatens Europe's cultural identity.
- 6 The Western European "old" Member States of the EU dominate the Eastern European "new" Member States.
- 7 The countries of Central Europe represent common values and traditions that the EU should respect.
- 8 We should leave the EU sooner or later.
- 9 European integration must be a multi-speed process, according to the readiness and interests of the Member States.
- 10 The EU's so-called LGBTQ propaganda is harmful to children.
- 11 Hungary's economy performs better than that of most EU countries.
- 12 Migration solves the EU's labor market problems.
- 13 Hungary's security in a war situation is guaranteed by the EU and NATO.
- 14 The current policy of the EU threatens the energy security of Hungarian households.
- 15 During the Covid epidemic, Hungarian epidemic management performed better than that of most EU countries.
- 16 The EU is the best guarantee for the preservation of democracy, human rights and the rule of law in the Member States, including here.
- 17 The EU should not interfere in any minority issues in the Member States, including issues related to gender, race and sexual orientation.
- 18 The EU must stand against authoritarian tendencies in individual Member States, regardless of the economic interests of national or international actors.
- 19 European identity is an important value for us and is compatible with national identity.
- 20 The EU must act effectively against Russian and Chinese disinformation in all Member States.
- 21 EU membership is beneficial for Hungary.
- 22 The Hungarian government used EU funds in an insufficiently transparent manner.
- 23 The operation of the West is chaotic, ineffective, and declining.
- 24 EU integration must continue.
- 25 The EU mainly serves the interests of large companies.

